

RESEARCH ON LIMITING FACTORS OF LANDSCAPE PRODUCTIVITY IN ABRAM LOCALITY, BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

The researches regarding the limiting factors of the grassland productivity were carried out between 2016 - 2019. The correlation of the data obtained in the field during the research interval with the meteorological data made available by the ANM made it possible to identify the main limiting factors of the grassland productivity, to study them as a whole and to elaborate them. of the complex of agro-pedo-ameliorative measures to improve the trophic properties of these soils, in order to increase the fertility potential of the meadows and to establish the assortment of plants used for sowing.

Key words: taxonomic soil unit, climatic regime, fertilizers, plant associations, productivity

INTRODUCTION

The town of Abram presents the following geographical coordinates: 47 degrees, 94 minutes, 05 seconds latitude and 22 degrees, 22 minutes, 49 seconds longitude, being located in the northwestern part of Romania, Bihor county, being geographically located in within the cross-border river basin Crișuri, the river basin of the Barcău river, occupying an area of 67.67 Kmp of which the grasslands occupy 760.23 ha. It is located in the northeastern part of Bihor county, being administratively composed of eight villages: Abram (common residence), Cohani, Dijir, Iteu, Iteu Nou, Margine, Satu Barbă, Șuiug. It is contiguous to the east with the locality of Balc, to the N-E with the locality of Boianu Mare, to the north with the locality of Vișoara, to the west with the localities of Marghita and Tăuteu, to the south and southeast with the locality of Tăuteu and the locality of Popești supply, fertility, taxonomic unit, trophicity, limiting.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The following aspects were taken into account during the research:

The collection in the field of a sufficient number of elements related to the soil and the natural conditions, so that the basic data for the soil and the environment can allow the solution of any practical problems related to the better use and capitalization of the soil resources.

Defining as precisely as possible the elements of soil and environment that are collected in the tern and serve as elements for separating the taxonomic units from the soil and expressing them in quantitative aspect, so that the intervals established after the analysis have ecological significance, or reflect changes of practical importance.

The organization of the basic elements collected from the field in a systematic form, so that the subsequent processing and use can be facilitated and the subsequent interpretation of the results for various purposes.

Establish a way of presenting the pedological data on the map in accordance with the obtained results and a form of table of characterization of the soil units shown on the map by the elements collected in the field and by the data obtained by soil analysis or by derived characteristics.

Elaboration of criteria of specific criteria for data interpretation in order to evaluate the land for various purposes and to establish improvement requirements under different conditions of land use and territorial planning.

The correct systematization of data, so as to allow their insertion in the database for the purpose of storage and processing and subsequent use.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Elements regarding the natural framework of soil formation and evolution

In order to identify the limiting factors of grassland productivity, it was necessary to define as precisely as possible the soil and environmental elements so that the intervals established following the analysis have ecological significance, or reflect changes of practical importance and the correct storing of data, to allow their introduction in the database for further storage and processing and use.

Geology

The lithological substrate on which the soils were formed and evolved is represented by Neogene deposits from Panonian, Pontian and Pleistocene, being made up of marls, agile, calcareous clays, loesside clays, sandstone, gravel as varied as granulometry, coarse sands, fluvial sediments (alluviums, sludge sands) and rarely chemical facies sediments (limestone, soda ash and limestone).

Geomorphology

The territory of Abram is located in the Carpathian Province, the Sub-Province of the Panonian Depression, the Western Piedmont Region, the Hodişa-Oradea Hills district on the western side of the Crasnei hills. The complex forms of relief, the general appearance, the altitude and the general exhibition of the territory, allowed the classification of the relief step “up the hill”. The terrain configuration is generally wavy or flat, less fragmented

(except for small areas located in the forest floor), the simple forms of relief being generally represented by meadows, plateaus, slopes, rarely ridges, ridges or other forms of relief. The maximum altitude is 370m,

Hydrology

The territory of the locality is a component of the river basin of the Barcău river, the hilly sector (the boundaries of the hilly sector are located along the Barcău river between the localities Nușfalău upstream and Marghita downstream).

The average water depth is 0.5-1m, except for certain portions, where the water depth can reach up to 2m. It is characterized by great unevennesses regarding the water depth, the nature of the bottom, the shape of the shore, etc. The flow of the river is very variable from 0.5 mc / sec to 15 mc / sec during the floods. The average flow is around 1.5-2 cubic meters / sec. In the years characterized by high rainfall, frequent spills occur, causing floods.

The groundwater is found at different depths depending on the relief, so in the meadow area of the Barcău river the depth is 0.5 - 2 m, on terraces 4-6 m, and on the higher relief units it is greater than 6- 8 m, not influencing the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil, respectively the floral composition of the grasslands. It presents a low to medium degree of alkaline, bicarbonate-sulfate-calcium-magnesium type, low chlorine content.

The hydrological regime is variable during the year, with higher spring flows, as a result of the melting of snow, followed by floods caused by the rains at the beginning of summer, with low flows throughout the summer, autumn and early winter.

Climatology

The communal territory of Abram is characterized by a temperate continental-moderate climate of hills, included in the climatic province Cf, the sub-province Cfbx.

The thermal regime

The average annual temperature is 8.5C. The average temperature in seasons is -1,2C in winter, 10C in spring, 19C in summer and 10C in autumn. The number of summer days (max. 25C) is 82 and the number of winter days (max. 0C) is 38. The number of frost days is maximum 118. The average temperature during the vegetation period is 15.8C, the first frost occurs in around October 11 and the last freeze around March 21.

The multiannual average temperature on the surface of the soil has values of 10.76C with a maximum recorded in 2000 of 11.6C and a minimum of 9.8 at the level of 1996.

The rainfall regime

The average annual rainfall is 644 mm with a minimum recorded in 2000 of 410 mm and a maximum of 834 mm in 1996, during the vegetation period of the plants having a value of 430 mm. The first snowfall is around November 15 and the last one is around March 15. The number of snow days on the surface of the soil increases from December to the end of January, after which it decreases until the end of March, the annual average being 35 days, the snow layer having a protective role on the soil, influencing the thermal conditions and implicitly the biochemical processes in soil. Following the multiannual monthly analysis of precipitations, there is an unequal and uneven distribution, presenting a minimum interval for the months of January-February, it registers a progressive increase from March to June, it stays constant in September at the level of May, in October. A new decrease is registered, so that later in December there will be an increase. It is highlighted as a month rich in rainfall in January and poor (dry) in June.

Wind regime

The predominant winds are recorded from the West and North-West direction, having an annual average frequency of 12.6%, respectively 11.4% with an average speed of 2-4,2m / s. The calm period during the year has an average of 40%.

Synthetic indicators of climate data

The aridity index of Martonne achieves an annual average value of 34.8 Nebulosity, expressed in tenths of covered sky has an annual average of 6.2.

The bioactive period is between March 15 and November 30, lasting about 270 days.

The vegetation period is between April 20 and October 30, with an average duration of 175 days.

The presented climatological data place the territory of Balc in an area characterized by mild winters and quite hot summers.

Vegetation

For the purpose of in-depth study of the vegetal carpet, phytocenological surveys were carried out here. In all cases, bioforms, geo-elements, as well as ecological indices (humidity, temperature and soil reaction) were analyzed.

The fruit trees mainly cultivated are plum, apple, cherry, cherry, peach, apricot, walnut, clove and mulberry.

The natural meadows are varied from a floristic point of view, the dominant being the mesophile and mesoxerophil groups, and in the areas with groundwater closer to the surface, the mesophile and hydrophilic groups prevail. The grasslands of the hilly area are composed of species

such as *Festuca pseudovina* and *F. pratensis*, *Agrostis tenuis*, *Poa pratensis*, *Alopecurus pratensis*, *Bromus* spp., *Cynodon dactylon*, *Lotus corniculatus* and *L. tenuis*, *Medicago falcata*, *Trifolium repens*, *Andropogon ischaemum*.

On sunny slopes species such as *Agropyron repens*, *Rubus caesius*, *Stipa* spp. are encountered. These meadows are found in the nemoral area, namely in the sub-areas of pedunculated oak forests *Quercus robur*, of the sky forests. *Quercus cerris*, *Quercus petraea*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Fagus sylvatica*, lime *Tillia parviflora*, *Sallix*, *Populus* sp. To which the jug was added (*Acer campestre*), *A. tataricum*, *Ulmus foliacea*, *Fraxinus angustifolia*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Populus tremula*, *Cerasus avium*, *Tillia tomentosa*, *T. cordata*, etc., and on the northern slopes of the higher hills there is *Fagus sylvatica*.

Among the shrubs we mention: the *Corylus vellana*, *Cornus mas*, *C. sanguinea*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Prunus spinosa*, *Rosa canina*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Clematis vitalba*. Along the valleys, a meadow vegetation formed from softwood flakes: *Salix alba*, *S. fragilis*, *Populus alba*, *P. nigra*, *Alnus glutinosa*.

Dows in the studied area are made up of species such as *Festuca valesiaca* and *Festuca rupicola*, *Agrostis tenuis*, *Poa bulbosa*, *Lolium perenne*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Alopecurus pratensis*, *Bromus* sp., *Cynodon dactylon*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Trifolium repens*, *Medicago lupulina*, *L. tenuis*, *Vicia angustifolia*, *Medicago falcata* (*culbuceasa*), *Astragalus onobryumis*, *Tragolius*, *Andropogon ischaemum*. *Agropyron cristatum*, *Rubus caesius*, *Stipa* spp., *Crataegus monogyna*, *Rosa canina*. The species from other botanical families are: *Plantago lanceolata*, *Cichorium intybus*, *Taraxacum officinale*, *Gallium verum*, *Achillea millefolium*, *Daucus carota*, *Fragaria viridis*, *Carum carvi*, *Pimpinella saxifraga*, etc.

Among the most common non-valuable species are: *Salvia pratensis*, *Pulsatilla montana*, *Thymus glabrescens*, *Prunella vulgaris*, *Linum austriacum*, *Eryngium campestre*, *Carduus acanthoides*, *Echium vulgare*, etc.

Associations of *Carex* spp., *Juncus effuses*, *Juncus conglomeratus*, *Luzula campestris* and rarer of *Typha latifolia*, *Phragmites communis*, accompanied by *Gratiola officinalis*, *Mentha piperita*, *Bides tripartite*. Also rare species were identified: *Sparganium erectum*, *Alisma gramineum*, *Sagittaria heterophylla*, *Juncus x royeri*, etc.

Commonly grown plants are wheat, barley, corn, soy, potato, beans, alfalfa, clover.

The meadows of *Festuca valesiaca* and *Festuca rupicola* have a pastoral value between 0.75 and 1.25 after the specific cover, respectively

15-25 after the specific contribution, falling in the category of weak meadows from a productive and qualitative point of view.

Naturally without any technological intervention, 0.6-1.0 t / ha are obtained from these grasslands. (3-5 t / ha M.V.) and 65-160 kg / ha P.B.D., achieving an average load of 0.3-0.5 U.V.M./ha.

The forest area of Abram belongs from an administrative point of view belongs to the National Board of Forests-Romsilva, Oradea Forestry Direction, Marghita Forestry District, Production Unit III Fagu-Balc.

The Production Unit III Fagu-Balc is located on the F.D.-2 vegetation floor - hilly of oak (GO, CE, GÎ and mixtures of these - gorun, sky, grous.

The vegetation of the forest area

The woody vegetation is made up of deciduous forests, along with small areas of softwoods. In the composition, deciduous forests have the following species: Quercus robur, Quercus petraea, Quercus cerris, Fagus silvatica, Fraxinus excelsior, Carpinus betulus, Acer pseudoplatanus, Robinia pseudocacia, Tilia argentea, Juglans nigra, Populus alba and Populus tremula, Salix sp.

The researches revealed the existence in the study area of 6 subtypes of soils, belonging to the Luvisoluri class.

In order to carry out the rehabilitation work in order to establish the favorability classes for pastures for each unit of territory, the units of homologous ecological territory were established according to the intensity with which the natural factors are manifested.

Table 1

The units of homogeneous ecological territory

Crt. No.	Nr. Unit. TEO	Area (ha)	Soil units	topo. No. (constituent plots)
1	TEO 1	56.58 ha	Luvosol tipic	192, 195, 196, 197, 205, 206, 211, 214, 215, 216, 219, 226, 227, 228, 229, 230, 231
2	TEO 2	130,07 ha	Preluvosol tipic	682, 683, 727, 732, 733, 734, 735, 736, 738, 742, 753, 759, 760 776, 777, 778, 781, 793, 794, 795, 796, 797, 798
3	TEO 3 B	45,89h	Luvosol tipic	1258,1263,1262,1246,1247, 1251,1249, 1166,1170,1171,
	TEO 3 A		Luvosol tipic	1274/1
4	TEO 4 A	72,03 ha	Luvosol stagnic	1315, 1281,1274
	TEO 4 B		Luvosolalbic tipic	1305,1306,1311, 1307,1312, 1302,1369, 1375,1378, 1493, 1495
5	TEO 5 A	162,47	Luvosol tipic	2285/1, 2285/2, 2287/1, 2287/2, ,2288, 2289/1, 2289/2,
	TEO 5 B		Luvosolalbicstagnic	2325,2267,2269,2266,2378,2283,2270/3, 2320,2300, 2307, 2309,2270/2
6	TEO6A	131,55 ha	Luvosol tipic	2607, 2609, 2728, 2729, 2735, 2731, 2757,
	TEO6B		Preluvosol tipic	2601,2602, 2604,2605/1, 2610, 2611, 2579/2, 2583, 2579/1, 2579/2, 2596
7	TEO7A	97,06 ha	Preluvosol tipic	2832, 2820, 2831, 2829/2, 2829/3, 2850, 2852, 2829/4
	TEO7B		Luvosol tipic	2788/1, 2788/2, 2793, 2794, 2795, 2797, 2831,
8	TEO8A	128,32 ha	Preluvosol tipic	1903/2, 1902, 1888, 1880, 1879, 1878, 1874, 1925, 1926, 1809
	TEO8B		Preluvosolstagnic	2025, 2065, 2000, 2032, 2033, 2036, 2037, 2027

Table 2 shows the favorability classes for grassland, at the level of the entire locality.

Table 2

The favorability classes for grassland, determined at the level of the entire locality

Crt. No.	Nr. territorial unit	Nr. cadastral plot	Grade of favorability
1	TEO 1	192, 195, 196, 197, 205, 206, 211, 214, 215, 216, 219, 226, 227, 228, 229, 230, 231	II
2	TEO 2	682, 683, 727, 732, 733, 734, 735, 736, 738, 742, 753, 759, 760, 776, 777, 778, 781, 793, 794, 795, 796, 797, 798	II
3	TEO 3 A	1274/1	I
	TEO 3 B	1258,1263,1262,1246,1247, 1251,1249, 1166,1170,1171,	II
4	TEO 4 A	1315, 1281, 1274	III
	TEO 4 B	1305,1306,1311, 1307,1312, 1302,1369, 1375,1378, 1493, 1495	III
5	TEO 5 A	2285/1, 2285/2, 2287/1, 2287/2, ,2288, 2289/1, 2289/2,	II
	TEO 5 B	2325,2267,2269,2266,2378,2283,2270/3, 2320,2300, 2307, 2309,2270/2	II
6	TEO 6 A	2607, 2609, 2728, 2729, 2735, 2731, 2757,	II
	TEO 6 B	2601,2602, 2604,2605/1, 2610, 2611, 2579/2, 2583, 2579/1, 2579/2, 2596	II
7	TEO 7 A	2832, 2820, 2831, 2829/2, 2829/3, 2850, 2852, 2829/4	II
	TEO 7 B	2788/1, 2788/2, 2793, 2794, 2795, 2797, 2831,	I
8	TEO 8 A	1903/2, 1902, 1888, 1880, 1879, 1878, 1874, 1925, 1926, 1809	III
	TEO 8 B	2025, 2065, 2000, 2032, 2033, 2036, 2037, 2027	III

Correction of acidity

Soils in permanent grasslands with an acidic pH need to correct the reaction by applying carbonate amendments. The main substances with which grasses are amended to correct acidity are: calcium carbonate (CaCO₃); lime dust (CaO); extinguished lime dust [Ca (OH) ₂]; manure removal foam from sugar factories and calcium residues from 55 chemical fertilizer factories. The average recommended doses (the need for calcareous amendments, expressed in tonnes CaCO₃ / ha) for the grasslands of Balc are presented in table 3, applied every 10-12 years.

The amendments can be applied especially late autumn after the grazing season and sometimes in the winter windows as well as early spring, with mechanized means or in extreme cases with manual means. The modification of acid or alkaline soils is a mandatory condition for the radical restoration of degraded meadows and the establishment of high productivity sown meadows

Table 3

Need for limestone amendments (tonnes / ha)							
Crt. No	Terit Unit	Plot No.	pH	Ah me/ 100g sol	Sb me/ 100g sol	Emergency	CaCO ₃ t/ha
1	TEO 1	192, 195, 196, 197, 205, 206, 211, 214, 215, 216, 219, 226, 227, 228, 229, 230, 231	5.9	4.4	14.8	III	4.95
2	TEO 2	682, 683, 727, 732, 733, 734, 735, 736, 738, 742, 753, 759, 760 776, 777, 778, 781, 793, 794, 795, 796, 797, 798	6.1	7.9	17.6	I	8.88
3	TEO 3 A	1274/1	6.3	5.1	11.3	III	5.74
	TEO 3 B	1258,1263,1262,1246,1247, 1251,1249, 1166,1170,1171,	5.8	7.4	14.2	I	8.32
4	TEO 4 A	1315, 1281, 1274	5.8	7.2	15.9	I	8.10
	TEO 4 B	1305,1306,1311, 1307,1312, 1302,1369, 1375,1378, 1493, 1495	5.8	7.6	13.6	I	8.55
5	TEO 5 A	2285/1, 2285/2, 2287/1, 2287/2, ,2288, 2289/1, 2289/2,	5.85	6.1	12.4	III	6.86
	TEO 5 B	2325,2267,2269,2266,2378,2283,2270/3, 2320,2300, 2307, 2309,2270/2	6.1	6.6	14.4	II	7.42
6	TEO 6 A	2607, 2609, 2728, 2729, 2735, 2731, 2757,	5.7	6.1	12.4	III	6.86
	TEO 6 B	2601,2602, 2604,2605/1, 2610, 2611, 2579/2, 2583, 2579/1, 2579/2, 2596	6.2	6.9	15.9	II	7.76
7	TEO 7 A	2832, 2820, 2831, 2829/2, 2829/3, 2850, 2852, 2829/4	6.3	5.7	17.2	III	6.41
	TEO 7 B	2788/1, 2788/2, 2793, 2794, 2795, 2797, 2831,	5.8	7.7	14.4	I	8.66
8	TEO 8 A	1903/2, 1902, 1888, 1880, 1879, 1878, 1874, 1925, 1926, 1809	5.9	6.4	13.8	II	7.20
	TEO 8 B	2025, 2065, 2000, 2032, 2033, 2036, 2037, 2027	5.9	7.0	15.3	II	7.87

Soil fertilization

The most important factor of degradation of the grass carpet is the lack of fertilizing elements of which the most important are nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. The cheapest method of fertilization of a pasture is the dragging with the animals during the grazing period. Traditional, normal, scientifically confirmed twinning is done with sheep: -2-3 nights 1 adult sheep / sq m on grass with corresponding grass carpet -4-6 nights 1 adult sheep / sq m on pastures invaded by *Nardus stricta*. However, this method, during the grazing season, can only improve 10% of the total area, once for 4-5 years as long as the dragging effect lasts. For a ton of green mass, 5 kg of N, 1 kg of P, 5 kg of K and 1 kg of calcium are extracted from the soil. If after several years of grazing, the organic fertilization is not supplemented with the chemical one, the content in the nutrients decreases, which leads to the radical change of the vegetal carpet in the sense of the disappearance of the plants with fodder value, more demanding to the soil supply with NPK and the gradual appearance until the domination of some ungodly weeds, who replace them. The application of chemical fertilizers

based on nitrogen, is done in fractions, in annual doses to avoid losses by leaching. Due to the very slow leaching of phosphorus, the administration of phosphate fertilizers can be done only once for several years (4-5), the grass plants tolerate high doses well if the other nutrients (N, K) are provided to the required level. Phosphatic and potassium fertilizers are applied on meadows in autumn, except when we use NPK complex chemical fertilizers when PK is applied concurrently with N in spring. The average quantities of fertilizers / ha / year required for grassland fertilization are: • 150 kg N • 50 kg P₂O₅ (P) • 60 kg K₂O (K) active substance

Table 4

Situation regarding the state of soil supply in N, P, K

Crt. No.	Territorial Unit	Plot No	N %	P ppm	K ppm
1	TEO 1	192, 195, 196, 197, 205, 206, 211, 214, 215, 216, 219, 226, 227, 228, 229, 230, 231	0,106	6,0	120
2	TEO 2	682, 683, 727, 732, 733, 734, 735, 736, 738, 742, 753, 759, 760 776, 777, 778, 781, 793, 794, 795, 796, 797, 798	0,140	8,0	90
3	TEO 3A	1274/1	0,102	8,0	140
	TEO 3B	1258,1263,1262,1246,1247, 1251,1249, 1166,1170,1171,	0,073	12	100
4	TEO 4 A	1315, 1281, 1274	0,100	3,4	120
	TEO 4 B	, 1305,1306,1311, 1307,1312, 1302,1369, 1375,1378, 1493, 1495	0,086	3,4	50
5	TEO 5 A	2285/1, 2285/2, 2287/1, 2287/2, ,2288, 2289/1, 2289/2,	0,125	12	100
	TEO 5 B	2325,2267,2269,2266,2378,2283,2270/3, 2320,2300, 2307, 2309,2270/2	0,098	5,7	50
6	TEO 6 A	2607, 2609, 2728, 2729, 2735, 2731, 2757,	0,190	9,0	120
	TEO 6 B	2601,2602, 2604,2605/1, 2610, 2611, 2579/2, 2583, 2579/1, 2579/2, 2596	0,180	9,0	120
7	TEO 7 A	2832, 2820, 2831, 2829/2, 2829/3, 2850, 2852, 2829/4	0,118	8,0	170
	TEO 7 B	2788/1, 2788/2, 2793, 2794, 2795, 2797, 2831,	0,118	9,2	90
8	TEO 8 A	1903/2, 1902, 1888, 1880, 1879, 1878, 1874, 1925, 1926, 1809	0,106	17	170
	TEO 8 B	2025, 2065, 2000, 2032, 2033, 2036, 2037, 2027	0,105	12	120

The average calculated amounts of fertilizers, kg / ha / year, expressed as active substance required for grassland fertilization are: 150 kg N, 50 kg P₂O₅ (P),60 kg K₂O (K) active substance

Organic fertilizers

Table 5 shows the optimal doses of organic fertilizers recommended for application depending on the optimal dose of N, P, K, and the type of organic fertilizer used. Doses between 10 and 22t / ha are recommended.

Table no. 5 Optimum doses of organic fertilizers recommended for application depending on the optimal dose of N, P, K, and the type of organic fertilizer used.

Table 5

Optimum doses of organic fertilizers

Mode of fertilizer.	Optimal doses applied						N kg/ha	P P ₂ O ₅ kg/ha	K K ₂ O kg/ha
	organic fertilizer								
	Ferment.3-4 month t/ha	Sheeps t/ha	Cows t/ha	Pigs t/ha	fresh t/ha	Ferment complet t/ha			
mixt	10	-	-	-	-	-	95	25	-
	-	10	-	-	-	-	67	27	-
	-	-	10	-	-	-	105	27	10
	-	-	-	10	-	-	105	31	-
	-	-	-	-	10	-	100	25	-
	-	-	-	-	-	10	52	-	-
chemical	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	50	60
mixt	12	-	-	-	-	-	84	20	-
	-	12	-	-	-	-	50,4	22,4	-
	-	-	12	-	-	-	96	22,4	-
	-	-	-	12	-	-	96	27,2	-
	-	-	-	-	12	-	90	20	-
	-	-	-	-	-	12	32,4	-	-
chemical	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	50	60
mixt	14	-	-	-	-	-	73	12,5	-
	-	14	-	-	-	-	33,8	17,8	-
	-	-	14	-	-	-	87	17,8	-
	-	-	-	14	-	-	87	23,4	-
	-	-	-	-	14	-	80	15	-
	-	-	-	-	-	14	12,8	-	-
chemical	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	50	60
mixt	16	-	-	-	-	-	62	10	-
	-	16	-	-	-	-	17,2	13,2	-
	-	-	16	-	-	-	78	13,2	-
	-	-	-	16	-	-	78	19,6	-
	-	-	-	-	16	-	70	10	-
	-	-	-	-	-	16	-	-	-
chemical	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	50	60
mixt	18	-	-	-	-	-	51	5	-
	-	18	-	-	-	-	-	8,6	-
	-	-	18	-	-	-	69	8,6	-
	-	-	-	18	-	-	19	15,9	-
	-	-	-	-	18	-	60	5,0	-
	-	-	-	-	-	18	-	-	-
chemical	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	50	60
mixt	20	-	-	-	-	-	40	-	-
	-	20	-	-	-	-	-	4	-
	-	-	20	-	-	-	60	4,0	-
	-	-	-	20	-	-	60	12	-
	-	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	-
	-	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-
chemical	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	50	60
mixt	22	-	-	-	-	-	29	-	-
	-	22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	-	-	22	-	-	-	51	-	-
	-	-	-	22	-	-	51	8,2	-
	-	-	-	-	22	-	40	-	-
	-	-	-	-	-	22	-	-	-
chemical	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	50	60
mixt	24	-	-	-	-	-	18	-	-
	-	24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	-	-	24	-	-	-	42	-	-
	-	-	-	24	-	-	42	4,4	-
	-	-	-	-	24	-	30	-	-
	-	-	-	-	-	24	-	-	-
chemical	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	50	60

Another factor that contributes significantly to the decrease of grassland productivity is the manifestation of the vertical phenomena recorded during the summer periods on the soils affected by humidity. In the panels no. 1, 2, 3, the effects of the swelling phenomena are presented with the appearance of a gilgay relief.

Fig. 1. Soil affected by vertical phenomena

Fig. 2. Soil affected by vertical phenomena

Fig. 3. Relief of gilgay

CONCLUSIONS

In order to achieve high productions of fodder and of adequate quality, the grass carpet of permanent (natural and semi-natural) and temporary (sown) grasses needs to be supported by fertilization (organic and / or chemical) correction of the reaction. The most important factor of degradation of the grass carpet is the lack of fertilizing elements of which nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (NPK) are noted. Therefore, after several years of harvesting, if it is not fertilized, on the meadow the nutrients in the soil are reduced, the vegetation is changed radically in the sense of the disappearance of plants with high nutritional value, more demanding when supplying the soil with NPK, a phenomenon that favors the gradual emergence, until the domination, of some species of unpretentious weeds, which take their place. The superficial mobilization of the soil will be carried out on the surfaces covered with works of deforestation of the woody vegetation and the application of amendments and chemical fertilizers. The replacement of degraded natural meadows with sown meadows is done only in cases where the methods of improvement by means of surface (fertilization, amendment, sowing) do not give the expected results.

Recommended grass mixtures for grassland sowing Mixtures of grasses of the species listed below will be used for planting and sowing operations listed below: *Phleum pretense*, *Festuca pratensis*, *Festuca rubra*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Lotifusum cornatus*.

Elimination of excess moisture General considerations.

Excess humidity is one of the most unfavorable factors that decrease grassland production and quality. Most of the good forage species in the grass carpet are mesophilic, that is, they prefer resorts with average soil moisture. The elimination of the temporary excess of humidity in the meadows is done by drying by means of open channels, of different sizes, which are placed at different distances between them depending on the characteristics of the soil, the intensity of the rains, etc. The permanent excess is eliminated with the help of drains of different materials (slabs, large stone, fascines, ceramic and plastic reflecting tubes, etc.) placed at different depths and distances depending on the level of the groundwater and the intensity of drainage we want specialists from the field of land improvements.

On soils with excess moisture, the removal of excess moisture can be done by:

- making drainage ditches for surface water whenever necessary, especially in spring after the melting of snow or heavy rain;

- avoidance of grazing on wet ground which further impairs the soil, making it impervious to rainwater;
- corman plows before the establishment of the sown meadows and the directing of excess water in a collection channel and further in an emissary;
- cultivation of moisture-loving species such as willows, poplars, arines, etc. which make biological drainage, as well as some herbaceous species resistant to excess water such as *Phalarisa rundinacea*, *Festuca arundinacea*, *Trifolium hybridum*.

Fighting other weeds in the meadows (harmful plants)

Spread and harmful effect In the grass meadow of grassland together with perennial grasses and legumes, species from the "diverse" or "other species" group also participate, some of them have low feed value, and others are practically non-consuming, or have an animal feed. high toxicity. The appearance and propagation of weeds in the grassland vegetation is favored by the manifestation in excess or deficiency of some ecological factors, as well as by the inadequate management of the grasslands: non-execution of the cleaning works, the non-use of a load with animals suitable for the production of grasslands and non-livestock grazing, non-uniform fertilization with organic or chemical fertilizers, delayed harvesting of hay, use of overgrown seeds with weeds, etc. The control of weeds in the meadows is another specific work for the meadows that due to the complex floristic composition (grasses, legumes, other plants) in which a harmful species is usually fought, the remaining fodder species are kept as far as possible and then the meadow is continued through grazing, mowed or mixed. These require the knowledge of both the effect that the control measures have by mechanical or chemical means on the species that make up the grass carpet and of the herbicide remnant in order not to cause disturbance to the animals, under the conditions of the use of the respective surfaces by grazing.

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STUDY ON AGRICULTURAL SUPPORT BENEFICIARIES GRANTED IN BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

The agricultural support granted to the farmers is of interest, firstly because agriculture in Romania is a risky activity, being a branch dependent on the weather conditions and secondly, because it offers the food source to the people. For these reasons the European Union financially supports granting funds for cultivation of agricultural land.

This subject needs to be treated from a legal point of view, as it contributes to a better knowledge of the agricultural activities that are carried out on the agricultural lands in Bihor county.

In Romania, agricultural support is granted to farmers starting with 2007, respectively funds for agriculture from the European Union in the form of direct payments on the surface.

Agricultural support can be requested by farmers by submitting an unique payment requests to the Agriculture Payments and Intervention Agency. This application is submitted only once a year within the specific terms established by normative acts.

Key words: support, Bihor, land, agricultural, agriculture

INTRODUCTION

According to this study, we will analyze the beneficiaries of agricultural support, limiting me territorially to Bihor county.

In Romania, agricultural support was granted, both during the pre-accession period to the European Union and after. Prior to 2007, the agricultural support was granted with financing from the state budget to the agricultural producers who requested support in the vegetable sector in the form of direct payments on the surface, through the award of value vouchers. Starting with 2007, the agricultural support was granted in the form of direct surface payments through the Single Surface Payment Scheme of the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF). This consists in granting a uniform amount per hectare, payable once a year, completely decoupled from production in order to support agriculture and investments in this area.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The paper aims to evaluate the situation of allocating the financial support granted to the applicants from Bihor county, in relation to the

benefits brought to Bihor agriculture. The Agency for Payment and Intervention for Agriculture (APIA) is the institution involved in managing European funds to these beneficiaries.

The research, related to a period of 5 years, offers some results from which a series of information emerges, both about the beneficiaries of agricultural support granted in Bihor county, as well as about the agricultural areas that are subject to payments. The data were taken from the records of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MADR), the National Institute of Statistics (INS) and the Agency for Payments and Intervention for Agriculture (APIA). We also used the information sources by accessing the websites: MADR, INSSE , APIA, and online publications with agricultural profile.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the level of Bihor County, during 2019, were submitted a number of 35,750 applications to APIA by farmers. A total of 30,771 applications were submitted by individuals, and 4,979 applications were submitted by legal entities. Of the legal entities, the limited liability companies requested 1817 applications, the family enterprises requested 544 applications, the authorized natural persons requested 1851 applications, the family businesses requested 767 applications, the associations / composers requested 167 applications, the joint stock companies requested 5 applications, and the agricultural companies requested 9 applications.

Fig. 1. Number of applicants at APIA level Bihor County Center for 2019

Both in our country and in Bihor county, - the beneficiaries of agricultural support - the economic agents that carry out agricultural activity take different forms. According to the *Government Emergency Ordinance no.44/2008 regarding the economic activities carried out by the authorized natural persons, the individual enterprises and the family enterprises* can

carry out agricultural activity: natural persons, authorized natural persons, family enterprises and individual enterprises. According to the *Law no. 31/1991 regarding trading companies, modified and completed*, carries out agricultural activity the following companies: in collective name, in simple partnership, in shares, in limited partnership in shares and with limited liability. *Law no.36/1992 regarding agricultural societies and other forms of association in agriculture* establishes the possibility of association, in order to exploit agricultural lands, in the form of agricultural societies. Can also carry out agricultural activity the forms of property ownership constituted on the basis of the Law of the land fund, respectively: composeorate and urban associations.

I will present below, for Bihor County, compared to the years 2015-2016-2017-2018-2019, the situation of the number of applicants for agricultural support respectively applications, submitted to APIA Bihor County Center.

Fig. 2. Number of applicants at APIA level Bihor County Center for 2015-2019

The APIA subventions are granted in the form of payment schemes, as mechanisms for supporting and guaranteeing agricultural producers and economic operators, respectively the direct payment schemes and the transitional national aid applied in agriculture in the period 2015-2020, as provided. in the *Emergency Ordinance no. 3/2015 for the approval of the payment schemes that are applied in agriculture between 2015-2020 and for the modification of art. 2 of Law no. 36/1991 on agricultural companies and other forms of association in agriculture.*

Direct payment schemes are:

Single payment scheme on SAPS surface;
 Redistributive payment scheme;
 Payment scheme for climate-friendly agricultural practices(Payment for greening);
 Payment scheme for young farmers;

Table 1

The comparative situation of the number of applications submitted to APIA Bihor County Center for the years 2015-2019

REQUESTS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Total	39421	37800	37411	36572	35750
Individuals	35545	33909	33201	31714	30771
Legal entities, of which	3876	3908	4210	4858	4979
Limited liability company (SRL)	350	322	412	465	1817
Individual enterprise(II)	198	241	337	169	544
Authorized natural persons (PFA)	1674	1880	1819	1914	1851
Family enterprise (IF)	14	24	60	119	767
Associations / composesorate	255	128	154	156	167
Joint Stock Companies (SA)	8	6	5	6	5
Agricultural Companies	4	2	7	2	9

Coupled support - Soybean; Lucerne; Grain peas for industrialization; Beans for industrialization; Hemp for oil and fiber; Rice; Seed potato; Hop; Sugar beet; Tomatoes for industrialization; Cucumbers for industrialization; Cherries/cherries for industrialization; Solarium crops (tomatoes, cucumbers, cabbage, eggplants and peppers); Plums for industrialization; Apples for industrialization; Greenhouse crops (tomatoes, cucumbers, peppers and cabbage); Apricots/apricots for industrialization; Early, semi-early and summer potatoes; Silk worms; goats; Meat bulls; Dairy cows; Milk buffaloes; sheep;

Market and foreign trade measures are:

Reconversion/Restructuring;

Assurance;

Distillation of by-products;

Investments in the wine sector;

Promoting wines;

Actions to inform and promote agricultural products in the internal market and in third countries;

Financial aid for milk distribution in schools;

Financial aid for fruit distribution in schools;

Financial aid evaluation of the fruit program in schools;

Financial aid adjacent measures for fruit in schools;

Financial aid Producer groups in the fruit and vegetable sector;

Financial aid Producer organizations in the fruit and vegetable sector;
 Temporary exceptional financial aid granted to agricultural producers in the fruit and vegetables sector;
 National Beekeeping Program;
 Financial aid to reduce milk production;
 Exceptional aid (pigs/milk quota).

Transitional national measures as an additional form of payment are:

- ANT 1 - Transitional National Aid for arable land crops;
- ANT 2 - Transitional National Aid for fiber for flax;
- ANT 3 - Transitional National Aid for fiber hemp;
- ANT 4 - Transitional National Aid for Tobacco;
- ANT 5 - Transitional National Aid for Hops;
- ANT 6 - Transitional National Aid for sugar beet;
- ANT 7 - Transitional National Aid - Decoupled production scheme, bovine species - Meat sector;
- ANT 8 - Transitional National Aid - Decoupled production scheme, bovine species - Milk sector;
- ANT 9 Transitional National Aid - sheep / goat species.

State aid:

- State aid for diesel fuel used in agriculture;
- State aid in the animal breeding sector;
- Exceptional aid (pigs / milk quota);
- State aid granted to the agricultural renter who alienates or leases the extra-urban agricultural lands owned by him, or concludes an agreement with the investor.

Table 2

The comparative situation of the area used by farmers who submitted applications to APIA Bihor County Center for the years 2015-2019

Year	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Area used (ha)	357.319,257	320.526,87	324.306,14	321.672,17	325.080,95

The measures delegated by AFIR to APIA are:

- Measure 8 - Investments in the development of forested areas and in improving the viability of forests - only the Sub-measure is eligible 8.1 - Forests and creation of forested areas;
- Measure 10 - Agro-environment and climate;
- Measure 11 - Organic farming;
- Measure 13 - Payments for areas facing natural constraints or other specific constraints;
- Measure 14 - Animal welfare payments;

Measure 15 - Forest-environment services, climate services and forest conservation - can only be applied for Sub-measure 15.1 - Payments for forest-environment commitments.

In recent years, the total area used by farmers in Bihor county is different, but with close values.

CONCLUSIONS

The agricultural support can be requested by an unique payment application that is submitted annually to the Agency for Payment and Intervention for Agriculture, in order to obtain subsidies for cultivating the land they own or for animals breeding.

As it results from Law no. 1/2004 *regarding the establishment, organization and functioning of the Agency for Payment and Intervention for Agriculture*, at art. 1 is foreseen: *1) establishes the Agency for Payments and Intervention in Agriculture, hereinafter Agency, a specialized body of central public administration, the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, with legal personality, fully financed from the state budget. art. 2 paragraph 1 the Agency is the public body responsible for managing certain forms of support aimed at supporting agriculture, financed from the state budget in accordance with the provisions establishing them.*

For the years studied, are noticed differences in the number of beneficiaries of agricultural support, differentiated according to the legal form of organization.

However, the areas of agricultural support granted in Bihor county in recent years have suffered modifications, but not major ones.

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9. Law no. 315/2004 regarding the regional development in Romania
10. Law no. 17/2014 regarding some measures of regulation of the sale-purchase
11. GEO no. 44/2008 on the conduct of economic activities by the authorized natural persons, the individual enterprises and the family enterprises

AGRIFOODSTUFF CONTROLS IN BIHOR COUNTY BETWEEN 2015 - 2019

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Abstract

Foodstuff production was increasing during last decade in order to answer to the higher demands of the world population increasing and use of agrifoodstuff for energetical purpose. Due to globalisation, emergent economies production increasing and domestic production variation the agrifoodstuff are supplied in romania and bihor county as well from all over the world. From european union were there are severe regulation regarding agrifoodstuff production the imports are quite safe for consumers but there are quality issues regarding extracomunity imports. The products that come from uncertain sources are not 100% according with our regulation and in this way must be very strictly monitorized and the corrective measures must be taken. This study present the evolution of national authority for consumer protection controls in bihor county from 2015 to 2019 to provide safe products for local market.

Key words: foodstuff, controls, Bihor county, programed actions, complains.

INTRODUCTION

Agrifoodstuff are the most important aspect of the consumers welfare. In last decade there was a change in supplying of global and local markets. Online supplying, in increasing the volume of foodstuff comerce, imports from outside of European Union, increasing the costs of raw materials and energy, extending the lenght of the trade routes and duration of transport and storage become issues and critical points in the actual supplying chains. In this way is important to have an overview of the state controls in the sector of agrifoodstuff in order to have a feedback of the agrifoodstuff market. There is also important to have an overview about the efficiency of the measures that state trough his control entities apply.

Methods used for controls are according with romanian standards and are quottation in latest studys.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methodology of controls was selected in accordance with the Romanian regulations that are similar with European regulations.

Below are presented the documents and regulations that are at the base of the state control in the field of foodstuff.

Government Decision no. 700/2012 on the organization and functioning of the National Authority for Consumer Protection, as amended, Law no. 245/2004 (r1) on general product safety.

Government Ordinance no. 21/1992 (r2) on consumer protection, as amended and supplemented. Law no. 608/2001 (r2) on product conformity assessment, Government Ordinance no. 2/2001 regarding the legal regime of contraventions, as amended and supplemented.

Law no. 363/2007 on combating unfair practices of traders with customers and harmonization of regulations with European legislation on consumer protection, as amended and supplemented.

Law no. 449/2003 (r1) for the sale of goods and associated guarantees, as amended and supplemented.

Law no. 7/2004 (r1) on the code of conduct for civil servants, Government Ordinance no. 27/2002 on regulating the resolution of petitions, as amended and supplemented.

The research was conducted for the years 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018 and 2019. The following items were taken in to study: Milling and bakery sector - physical and chemical parameters; Milling and bakery sector - microbiological parameters; Soft drinks - physical and chemical parameters; Pastry - physical and chemical parameters; Pastry - microbiological parameters; Milk and dairy products - physical and chemical parameters; Fish and canned fish - physical and chemical parameters; Rice - physical and chemical parameters; Water - physical and chemical parameters; Alcoholic beverages - physical and chemical parameters; Cocoa - physical and chemical parameters; Meat and meat stuff - physical and chemical parameters; Honey - physical and chemical parameters; Fruits and vegetables - physical and chemical parameters; Coffee - physical and chemical parameters; Oil - physical and chemical parameters; Vinegar - physical and chemical parameters.

The analysis were conducted in LAREX Bihor and Bucharest laboratories and DSP Bihor laboratory.

All the controls were undertaken during all of the years in the frame of programmed actions and also in case of complains.

RESULTS AND DISSION

The controls that were conducting were according with national regulations and the procedures listed above and were grouped on the items also presented in the Matherial and method chapter.

The results shown an variable dynamic of the number of controls. In this way it is noticeable that there is a decreasing of the number of controls during studied period.

Table 1

Number of controls for 2015 - 2019

Type of actions	Number of controls				
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Milling and bakery sector - physical and chemical parameters	5		3	4	
Milling and bakery sector - microbiological parameters	1		2	1	3
Soft drinks - physical and chemical parameters	1		1	2	
Pastry - physical and chemical parameters	1	7	2	7	
Pastry - microbiological parameters	8	10		2	
Milk and dairy products - physical and chemical parameters	5	4	2	5	
Fish and canned fish - physical and chemical parameters	4	1	4		
Rice - physical and chemical parameters	5				
Water - physical and chemical parameters	4	3	1		1
Alcoholic beverages - physical and chemical parameters	4				
Cocoa - physical and chemical parameters	5				
Meat and meat stuff - physical and chemical parameters	5	3	5	5	1
Honey - physical and chemical parameters	4	6			3
Fruits and vegetables - physical and chemical parameters		4		1	
Coffe			1		
Oil			1		
Vinegar					1
Total	52	38	22	27	9

Fig. 1. Evolution of the controls number during 2015 - 2019

The main concern of the controls in was the Milling and bakery sector, Pastry sector and Meat and meatstuff sector due to short shelf life.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions that can be drawn by this study are diverse.

It was recorded an decreasing of the controls because of changes that occurs in the suppliers .

The study was shown that severe controls are very important tool that enhanced the fair trade practice and the equilibrium on the market.

The most important effects were recorded in the agricultural products.

Because high number of controls were undertaken as a result of complains the reduction of controls number lead us and confirm the conclusion that controls are best guardian of agrifoodstuff quality.

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12. ***Ordonanța Guvernului nr. 2/2001 privind regimul juridic al contravențiilor, cu modificările și completările ulterioare,
13. ***Legea nr. 363/2007 privind combaterea practicilor incorecte ale comercianților în relația cu consumatorii și armonizarea reglementărilor cu legislația europeană privind protecția consumatorilor, cu modificările și completările ulterioare,
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RESEARCH OF EVOLUTION OF AREAS WITH MAIZE CULTURES IN ROMANIA DURING 2014-2018

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Abstract

Maize has a production capacity of about 50% higher than other cereals, but also a wide spread area, because it is little influenced by climate change. Moreover, maize has a high resistance to drought, heavy rains, but also to diseases and pests, and the agrotechnical and harvesting works can be fully mechanized.

Genetic progress has allowed to increase the density constantly in the maize crop, the new hybrids emerging having a lower sensitivity to the stress caused by the competition observed at high density, this directly influencing the increase of the production potential.

Key words: (maximum 6): cultivated area, maize, production.

INTRODUCTION

Maize is a valuable plant both from the point of view of productivity and from the point of view of its economic importance, having multiple uses in human nutrition, animal husbandry and industry.

This plant occupies the third place, as importance, among the plants grown on Earth. This position is acquired through a series of particularities: it has a high production capacity, it has a great ecological elasticity, which allows it a wide spreading area, it is a good precursor plant for most crops, it supports monoculture, it can be grown 100% mechanized, the harvesting is done without shaking, makes good use of fertilizers and water.

In Romania, maize began to be grown late, around 1700, replacing the old proso millet farms. The reasons why this plant was interesting were high productivity, it could be cultivated in less favorable areas, and more than all in one place, it was not of interest to the Ottoman Empire, it was not used as a tribute.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study analyzes the evolution of maize surfaces and the yield of production during the years 2014-2018. In our country, maize is the second

crop as important as wheat. Of the 23.8 million acres of Romania area is concerned, the agricultural area used in agricultural holdings is about 13.3 million acres (55.9%), of which about 8.3 million acres are arable land. By use, the arable land occupies about 62.5% of the agricultural area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The areas cultivated with whole grain cereals for the period 2014-2018 are found in table 1.

Table 1

Area cultivated with whole grain cereals for the period 2014-2018

2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
5443k acres	5319k acres	5487k acres	5107k acres	5174k acres

Fig. 1. Graph of the areas cultivated with whole grain cereals over the years 2014-2018

The largest area cultivated with whole grain cereals was harvested in 2016 with an area of 5487k acres, 7.4% more than in 2017, 6% more than in 2018, 0.8% and 3.1% respectively for 2014 and 2015.

From this area cultivated with whole grain cereals the second crop after wheat is represented by maize.

Table 2

Surface cultivated with whole grain corn 2014-2018				
2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
2512k acres	2605k acres	2581k acres	2402k acres	2371k acres

Fig. 2. Graph of maize cultivated areas over the years 2014-2018

The largest area cultivated with maize was harvested in 2015 with 2605k acres, 3.7% more than in 2014. In 2016, 2017, 2018 a decrease of maize area was observed compared to 2015 with 0.9%, 8.4% and 9.8% respectively.

Fig. 3. Evolution graph of the areas cultivated with maize in relation to the areas cultivated with whole grain cereals.

In 2014 and 2018, the area cultivated with maize represented 46% of the total area cultivated with wholegrain cereals and in 2016 and 2017 the area cultivated with maize represented 47% of the total area.

The highest share of the area cultivated with maize in relation to the area cultivated with wholegrain cereals was recorded in 2015, as of 49%.

Table 3

Maize crops 2014-2018					
Average	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Average production kg/acres	4770kg	3462kg	4159kg	5959kg	7740kg
Average production k tones	11988	9021	10746	14326	18353

Fig. 4. Graph of total production recorded over the years 2014-2018

The highest maize production was harvested in 2018, 18353k tons, and the lowest production was harvested in 2015, 9021k tons, as well as the highest average production per acre was recorded in 2018, 7740 kg/acre and the lowest average production per acre was harvested in 2015, 3462 kg/acre.

CONCLUSIONS

The research of the evolution of the areas cultivated with maize during the period 2014-2018 was carried out on the basis of the data recorded at the Ministry of Agriculture and Development and of the data recorded in the Statistical Yearbook of Romania.

The largest area cultivated with wholegrain cereals was achieved in 2016, 5487k acres, with 0.8% and 3.1% higher than in 2014 and 2015, respectively, and for 2017 and 2018 the area cultivated compared to 2015 decreased by 7.4% and 6%, respectively.

The areas cultivated with maize between 2014-2018 are between 45% -50% of the total area cultivated with wholegrain cereals.

In 2017 and 2018 the area cultivated with maize represented 46% of the total area cultivated with wholegrain cereals and in 2016 and 2017, the

area cultivated with maize represented 47% of the total area cultivated with whole grain cereals.

The smallest maize production, both average 3462 kg/acre and average production 9021k tons was recorded in 2015 when the area cultivated with maize was the largest of the four years studied, namely 2605k acres.

The largest maize production, both average 7740 kg/acre and the total 18353k tons, was harvested in 2018 when the area cultivated with maize was the lowest cultivated area of the four observed years 2371k acres.

In 2018, Romania harvested the largest maize production in the European Union, France being on the second place and at the same time the largest maize crops in history.

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THE INFLUENCE OF SOIL UPON PRODUCTION OF WINTER WHEAT IN THE REGION OF CAREI, SATU MARE COUNTY

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Abstract

*The present paper aims to analyze the behavior of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) under varying soils in the region of Carei, Satu Mare county, Romania in the agricultural years, 2017-2018, 2018-2019. The climatic years were excellent due to the fact that sowing was done late in autumn, and the emergence of the plants occurred in early spring, that determined the specific reactions of the wheat varieties, expressed in the productions as well as in morphological characters. The average production of wheat was between 5400-6750 kg/ha.*

Key words: winter wheat, soil, production

INTRODUCTION

Wheat is one of the oldest cultivated plants and the most important food plant. Wheat is an important food crop and is by far the most popular cereal in Europe, Romania being among the six important producers.

Wheat flour bread is a basic food for the world's population, representing food for 35-40% of the world's population (Szekely et al., 2010).

Wheat is of great importance as a food, providing much of the carbohydrates and proteins needed to man and more than half of the calories consumed by mankind. The forms under which wheat is used in human food are very diverse, the most widespread being bread, followed by pasta and pastry (Szekely et al., 2010).

Wheat quality is not constant from one year to another, from one field to another, due to variety of varieties (genetic potential) and climate change yearly. Wheat production and quality indices are influenced by technological factors, variety, meteorological conditions and interactions between them (Racz et al., 2013).

Nowadays, not only yield amount but also the quality of the produced grain is important, because the quality of the grains determines their direction of use. That is why farmers are trying to get high grain yields in line with food (accepted for bread baking) quality, while minimize production costs and using environmentally friendly technologies.

Optimal nutrient provision is an important factor to get high yield with grain quality. Nitrogen is one of the most important elements of plant

nutrition, which often to a great extent determines not only wheat yield level, but especially grain baking quality. It is also one of the most mobile plant nutrients in the soil.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The present paper aims to analyze the behaviour of eight winter wheat varieties (Glosa, Falado, Akteur, Combin, Sorrial, Exotic, Renan, Lorenzo) in the region of Carei, Satu Mare county, on the basis of a comparative crop test. The observations were made in crop years 2017-2018, 2018-2019, the plot is of 8 ha each type of wheat was sowed on 1 ha in each year of the study the wheat varieties were adapted to the specific climatic conditions with a normal fertilization without excesses.

The experimental soils were: Cambic chernozem, poorly gleissed, rich in humus and with a normal content in total nitrogen, low in phosphorus and mediocre in potassium. The other soil types here a typical clay soil with normal contents of clay and humus, histosol that was rich in organic content, so it was a nutrient rich soil. There were other two types of soil: rendzinas and loam soil that were cultivated in this region. The statistical processing of the production results was made by variance analysis. The variance analysis revealed differences between the eight varieties studied, the different soil types and the climatic conditions having significant effects on the behaviour of studied wheat varieties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the experimental years 2017-2018, 2018-2019, the production differences between the studied varieties were due to a significant extent both to the genetic potential of the varieties and the location conditions the level of fertilization, the level of applied technologies and last but not least the types of soil. Grain weights (production), had a mean variation so there are significant differences between the 8 variants studied.

Table 1

Grain yields obtained from the 8 wheat varieties in the years 2017-2018

Nr. crt	Variant	Type of soil / Production (kg/ha)				
		chernozem	histosol	loam	rendzinas	clay
1	Glosa	6750	6010	5800	6220	5710
2	Falado	6420	5750	5650	6110	5680
3	Akteur	6310	5600	5570	6070	5590
4	Combin	6580	5930	5640	6120	5670
5	Sorrial	6120	5590	5510	5970	5400
6	Exotic	6230	5840	5620	5850	5450
7	Renan	6270	5760	5490	5910	5550
8	Lorenzo	6360	5590	5580	5980	5610

Analyzing the efficacy of typical chernozem, we obtained the highest efficacy, this was followed by histosol, loam soil, rendzinas and clay soil.

So the wheat crops are linked to all these mentioned before.

From Table 1 where we analyzed the influence and Table 2 of soil types over the wheat production, it was found that significant differences were achieved on typical chernozem in comparison with the other soil types.

Table 2

Grain yields obtained from the 8 wheat varieties in the years 2018-2019

Nr. crt	Variant	Type of soil / Production (kg/ha)				
		chernozem	histosol	loam	rendzinas	clay
1	Glosa	6650	6000	5700	6120	5610
2	Falado	6310	5650	5550	6200	5560
3	Akteur	6220	5400	5400	5910	5490
4	Combin	6480	5730	5540	6010	5590
5	Sorrial	6020	5490	5410	5730	5410
6	Exotic	6130	5740	5570	5580	5410
7	Renan	6160	5560	5410	5670	5440
8	Laurenzio	6220	5490	5430	5710	5520

Regarding the production results on each studied type of soil, significant production increases were obtained in the variant Glosa on chernozem soil and there is also a slight difference in production on the other soil types. The prospective line of winter wheat oscillated between 6650 kg/ha in the Glosa perspective wheat variety and Exotic perspective wheat variety.

From the all soil types, the best efficacy was obtained by Glosa on cambic chernozem soil followed by the other types as you can see in the tables.

CONCLUSIONS

In the agricultural year 2017-2018, 2018-2019, climatically exceptional, the sowing took place in late autumn, late November and the emergence of the plants was made in early spring, which determined the specific reactions of the wheat varieties, expressed in the produced production, as well as morphological characters.

Research was carried out on five soil types in wheat crops. The experiments were located in Satu-Mare county, Carei region on a basis of comparative crop test.

The varieties under study differently reacted to the environmental conditions, the climatic conditions and the types of soil they were sown in each year of the study.

Results show a very significant yield increase of certain types of wheat (Glosa and Combin) in some types of soils and also the favourable climatic conditions of these two years.

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ASPECTS OF BATTERY POWERED FARM MACHINES FOR FARMING 4.0

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Abstract

The pressure to produce more food has led to the need for identification of applicable solutions, to solve, to improve the sustainability of production processes and accelerate innovation in the agriculture. These solutions based on the technical revolution can be characterized by the Farming 4.0 concept.

This concept is primarily based on the application of precision agriculture methods with the help of new technical achievements such as IoT (Internet of Things), AI (Artificial Intelligence), Big Data, Cloud and battery modernization.

Among the important technological achievements, we list the automatic steering based on GPS, autonomous tractors and agricultural machines, the replacement of the thermal motors with electric motors, using batteries as the main source of energy, robots and drones for agriculture, direct communication between agricultural machines and centralization of all information in Cloud-based software applications.

This article gives a brief overview of the achievements based on the use of batteries in agricultural machines and tries to synthesize the main future directions.

Key words: battery, Farming 4.0, IoT, precision agriculture, robots for agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, of the United Nations, (United Nations, 2017) has predicted that the global population will reach 8.55 billion people by 2030 and almost 10 billion people by 2050. In order to feed this growing population, according to FAO, food production must increase with 70 percent by 2050 and a 60 percent increase in demand for high quality protein such as milk, meat, and eggs.

Agriculture is energy intensive and the pressure to produce more food requires more energy, an increasingly costly input to the production process.

Electric driven farm vehicles are nothing new. Probably the first attempt to use electricity to power field equipment was in 1894, when the Zimmermann Company in Germany demonstrated its self-propelled electric ploughs. They were common in the 1930s but were tethered to the supply by trailing cables. Today, John Deere's developed GridCON, a tractor which operates autonomous and therefore has no cabin. It is supplied with a 1 kilometer long cable which rolls on and off automatically. This tractor was built after the battery problems of the Sesam, a fully electric 6R-series tractor, in which the engine and fuel tank were replaced by a huge battery package.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study analyzes the stage of achievements and the possible directions of battery powered farm machines, in accordance with the requirements of the new agricultural revolution.

In the case of passenger cars, every major automotive company currently has such a vehicle produced in series. It is a good prognosis for electric drives to have a significant market share in the future in the agricultural machinery sector as well.

Farming requires powerful machinery to perform ground preparation functions and other energy intensive operations, so the tractor is the heart of most farming operations. The tractor not only provides transport and traction power, but is also used to drive attached machinery in a stationary operation.

Several agricultural machinery manufacturers have introduced battery powered tractors into the market. Examples are in Table 1.

Table 1

Battery powered tractors on the market or under trial.

Manufacturer	Model name	Power rating kW	Battery size kWh	Operation time h	Recharge time	Charging cycles
John Deere	Sesam	130	150	4	3 h	3100
Solectrac	eUtility (and eFarmer)	15	26	5 to 8	3 h to 80%	3000
Rigitrac	Rigitrac SKE50	50	80	5	–	–
Agco / Fendt	Fendt e100vario	50	100	5	0,75 h to 80%	–
Escort	Farmtrac				6 - 10 h	

Another new category of battery powered farm machines are telehandlers (telescopic handlers).

Table 2

Battery powered telehandlers on the market or under trial.

Manufacturer	Model name	Max. Load kg	Max. Height m	Operation time h	Recharge time h	Charging cycles
Faresin Industries	Faresin 6.26	2600	5.9	6	4	2000
Manitou	MHT-790E	9000	6.84	8	8 (1.5h fast charge)	3000
JCB	JCB 30-19E	3000	4.1	8	2-minute battery change	-

To extend battery life have appeared the so-called solar powered tractors, which have power derived from PV panels attached to the tractor.

Options for battery swap out are also considered, i.e. one battery can be on charge during the morning session and swapped at the midday break for a second battery that would then charge during the afternoon shift.

One of the biggest impacts of the decreasing cost of solar panels and batteries is in the field of robots for agriculture. These systems range from small low weight machines powered entirely by solar, used for weed eradication, to larger machines using stored energy for more complex tasks, such as sowing, fertilization, crop assessment, harvesting etc. They use a very small amount of power, have electric motors, they can be positioned very precisely. One of the advantages of battery-powered robots is that they can operate continuously and do not require daylight for operation. These robots have the advantage of small size and low weight, causing less soil compaction than would happen if tractor based planters and cultivators were used, as well as a massive savings in time and energy.

There are several weed eradication robots on the market, some entirely solar powered and others relying on battery storage. The robots detect the presence of weeds and eliminate them either by a controlled dose of herbicide, mechanical removal, or mechanical destruction.

A typical example would be the machine designed and under test by Ecorobotics of Switzerland. The robot is completely solar powered and can operate by detecting weeds and delivering a controlled amount of herbicide to the weed. The robot can cover 3 ha per day, up to 12 hours a day. It is powered by a 380 W solar array and an on board battery is fitted. It has 2 x 15 l herbicide tanks and is a relative lightweight, at approximately 130 kg.

Similar is RIPPA (Robot for Intelligent Perception and Precision Application) which is equipped with VIIPA™ (Variable Injection Intelligent Precision Applicator), which is capable of autonomously shooting weeds at high speed using a directed micro-dose of liquid.

Among the more powerful robots we must remember Bonirob, designed and developed by a Bosch company “Deepfield robotics”. The unit can operate for eight hours and can cover up to five hectare per day. Another example are the French-made Dino robot which is guided by accurate GPS signals to follow a pre-programmed route, straddling vegetable beds while two cameras assess the plant growth and identify weeds to be mechanically dug out from crops. Once under way, the battery-powered unit can work for up to ten hours on a full charge, covering up to five hectare in a day, without the need for further human interference – even sending its operator a text message when the job is finished.

A different concept are represented by the Digital Farmhand robot, developed by University of Sydney engineers, which uses low-cost robotics technology to increase food quality and production output for small-scale farmers.

Mobile agricultural robot swarms MARS, developed by Ulm University of Applied Sciences, the EU research funding, AGCO and Fendt, is an approach for autonomous farming operations by a coordinated group of robots. One key aspect of the MARS concept is the low individual intelligence, meaning that each robot is equipped with only a minimum of sensor technology in order to achieve a low cost and energy efficient system that provides scalability and reliability for field tasks. The key advantage of this approach is the energy efficiency compared to other methods using robots. The robot swarms is coordinated by a centralized entity, which is responsible for path planning, optimization and supervision. It also serves as a mediator between the robots and different cloud services responsible for the documentation of the procedure. The swarm approach allows robots to concentrate on areas where action is required and devote less attention to areas not needing attention, whereas individual robots have to cover the whole area.

An entire system, including small robots operating in swarms and a cloud-based system control, is available under the product name Xaver, which fits in with the swarm concept of using a large number of small autonomous machines to do precise agricultural work.

Australian-based SwarmFarms is building modular system of small self-driving frame to which components can be added or subtracted.

The most complex robots are those made for harvesting in horticulture. An example is BayWa picking robot for apple harvest developed by the US start-up Abundant Robotics, in which Munich-based BayWa Group acquired a stake in 2017. Another example is AI-equipped tomato harvesting robots from Panasonic.

Designed for strawberry fields, Agrobot E – Series has twenty – four robotic wireless arms that can not only quickly pick strawberries, but can also identify a strawberry’s maturity in the field.

Sweeper, backed by the EU as part of its Horizon 2020 innovation program, is built to pick ripe peppers in a greenhouse. To do his job, Sweeper uses a camera that recognizes a pepper’s color. Computer vision then helps the robot decide whether to pick the fruit. If so, Sweeper uses a small razor to cut the stem before catching the fruit in its “claws” and dropping it in a basket below. The Technology University of Queensland developed a prototype robotic sweet pepper harvester nicknamed Harvey, combining robotic vision and automation expertise to benefit farmers. The camera system and harvesting tool are mounted at a standard robotic (arm) manipulator end. Combining robotic-vision techniques and crop manipulation tools are key factors in harvesting these crops.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All over the world is a growing concern for the development of intelligent machines for agriculture. This concern is given on the one hand by the increasing need for food to feed the population but also due to the decrease in the workforce in agriculture and the need to protect the environment.

This concern has materialized through the emergence of precision agriculture technologies and Digital Farming or Smart Farming concepts, which has transformed into Farming 4.0, the fourth revolution in agriculture.

In contradiction with the present tendencies, based on agricultural machines as high as possible to have the highest productivity but which strongly pollute the environment, we try to make smaller agricultural machines, less polluting, to apply precision agriculture and to protect the environment. One of the challenges facing development of electric farm machines is the need for sufficient stored energy to run a large vehicle for a full day on a single charge. This has currently restricted the sector to small and medium sized machines. Small machines have an advantage of reducing soil compaction and unlike their larger counterparts, can be used in wet conditions without creating as much damage on soil. The ability to work just after rain when weeds are beginning to sprout can translate to less herbicide being needed. This machines need around 70% less energy to do the same work as diesel driven machinery, and since neither diesel nor oil is required to operate the machines, there is no leakage and there are no local emissions.

CONCLUSIONS

We can conclude that the agricultural industry is about to be disrupted and will transform into a high-tech industry and will need a high skilled farmers.

With the exception of large energy-consuming agricultural works, such as plows, most agricultural machines will be electrically powered and will have the battery powered by solar panels as an energy source. Even for the plowing it is possible to have a machine with a single furrow, working 24 hours a day, by replacing the battery, to cover the farm needs. Battery research is being supported by all governments around the world and will change that situation.

These machines will be modular, meaning there will be the possibility to perform several types of agricultural work and will be able to work in a team, communicating both with each other and with a command center. The farmer will be able to access the control center and drive this machines

through a mobile phone or tablets. Harvesters, which will be primarily robots, will specialize in a range of similar products.

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SELECTIVITY AND EFFICIENCY OF DIFFERENT HERBICIDES FOR WEED CONTROL IN PEA CULTURES UNDER THE CONDITIONS EXISTING IN ARDS LIVADA

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Abstract

The present paper presents results obtained in the pea culture from 2019.

In order to achieve an effective control of the monocotyledonous and dicotyledonous weeds from the pea crop in this experience the selectivity, the effectiveness of the herbicide treatments and the influence of the herbicide treatments on the germination were pursued.

Key words: pea, herbicide selectivity, herbicide efficacy, germination

INTRODUCTION

The pea is a crop with a short vegetation period, which is a very good precursor plant for hairy cereals.

The cultivation of peas sown in frequent rows and in the early spring, is enriched with a large number of weed species, which consequently reduces the production by 30-50%, diminishes its quality and hinders the harvesting work. On the other hand, considers that in the control of weeds from this culture has a contribution the competition of well-developed pea plants at the expense of infestation with species such as Echinochloa, Setaria, Cirsium, Amaranthus etc, which invade the culture towards the maturity phase (Ciobanu, 2003).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experimental field was located at Agricultural Research and Development Station (ARDS) Livada, Satu-Mare county on a stagnogleized preluvosol with a pH of 5.19, a clay content of 20.9% and a humus content of 2.82.

The experiments were located according to the Latin rectangle method, 12 variants in three repetitions, the plot area being 21 m².

The variety Magistra Liv was sown in the last decade of March, registering after the pre-emergent treatments in 30 days an amount of 22.9 mm / m².

The variants in which the selectivity and efficacy of herbicides were tested in pea culture were:

Table 1

Herbicides applied to pea crop 2019			
No. Var	Herbicides	Dose l,kg/ha	Active substance
1	Untreated	-	-
2	Dual Gold 960EC	1,5	S – metolachlor 960g/l
3	Dual Gold 960EC	2	S – metolachlor 960g/l
4	Pendigan 330 EC	5	pendimethalin 330g/l
5	Corum + Gramin 5EC	1,2+1	(bentazone 480g/l + imazamox22,4g/l)+quizalofop- P-ethyl 50g/l
6	Pulsar 40 + Gramin 5EC	1,2+1	imazamox 40g/l + quizalofop- P-etil 50g/l
7	Pulsar 40	1,2	imazamox 40g/l
8	Pendigan 330 EC+ Pulsar 40	3,5+1,2	pendimethalin 330g/l + imazamox 40g/l
9	Stomp Aqua + Pulsar40	3+1,2	pendimethalin 455g/l + imazamox 40g/l
10	Stomp Aqua + Butoxone M 40	3+2	pendimethalin 455g/l + MCPB – Na 400g/l
11	Stomp Aqua + Butoxone M 40	3+2,5	pendimethalin 455g/l + MCPB – Na 400g/l
12	Dual Gold 960EC + DMA Extra 600SL	1,5+0,2	S – metolachlor 960g/l + acid 2,4D of dimethylamine salt 600g/l

The age of herbicide application was pre-emergence, pre-emergence + post-emergence and post-emergence.

For herbicide administration the equipment used was Plot Sprayer PSGF 4.3, teejet nozzle type, 0.2 nozzle size, and the displacement speed was 6 km / h.

The norm of solution used was 500 l / ha, the administration being done for all variants at the same working pressure, ie 2 bars.

During the vegetation period, after making the treatments, observations were made regarding the degree of selectivity and effectiveness on the weeds.

The selectivity of the tested herbicides was noted following visual observations after the EWRS scale (grades 1 to 9; 1 = selective, 9 = phytotoxic), and the assessment of herbicide effectiveness was made by counting the weeds by species in each plot per 1 m².

The processing of the experimental results was done by analyzing the variance to determine the influence of the treatments on the production.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained regarding the selectivity of the herbicide treatments were found that in each treated variant very good selectivity was obtained, the EWRS score being 1 for each variant (Table 2).

Analyzing the efficacy of herbicides it is found that the best weed control was performed on the variants treated with herbicides: Stomp Aqua 3l / ha applied in pre-emergence associated with the herbicide Pulsar 40 1.2l / ha applied in post-emergence, Pendigan 330 EC 3.5l / ha plus Pulsar 40 1.2l / ha and Dual Gold 960 EC 1.5l / ha applied in pre-emergence associated with DMA Extra 600 SL applied early post-emergence (when pea is in the sting phase, BBCH 11) (Table 2).

In the variants in which we applied two treatments, pre-emergence associated with a post-emergent treatment obtained better efficacy than in the variants where we applied a single treatment regardless of the time of application.

Table 2

Selectivity and effectiveness of herbicide treatments in pea crop 2019

No. Var	Herbicides	Dose l,kg/ha	Application time	Selectivity EWRS notes	Effectiveness %
1	Untreated	-	-	-	0
2	Dual Gold 960EC	1,5	preem	1	10
3	Dual Gold 960EC	2	preem	1	15
4	Pendigan 330 EC	5	preem	1	15
5	Corum + Gramin 5EC	1,2+1	post	1	25
6	Pulsar 40 + Gramin 5EC	1,2+1	post	1	32
7	Pulsar 40	1,2	post	1	10
8	Pendigan 330 EC+ Pulsar 40	3,5+1,2	preem+post	1	35
9	Stomp Aqua + Pulsar40	3+1,2	preem+post	1	47
10	Stomp Aqua + Butoxone M 40	3+2	preem+post	1	30
11	Stomp Aqua + Butoxone M 40	3+2,5	preem+post	1	32
12	Dual Gold 960EC + DMA Extra 600SL	1,5+0,2	preem+ early post	1	35

The results regarding the influence of herbicide treatments on pea production indicate that the best variants are the variants in which the herbicides were applied: Pulsar 40 1,2l / ha + Gramin 5 EC 1l / ha, Stomp Aqua 3l / ha + Pulsar 40 1.2l / ha, Stomp Aqua 3l / ha + Butoxone M 40 2.5l / ha and Dual Gold 960 EC 1.5l / ha + DMA Extra 600 SL1l / ha, variants in which the production increase was very positive . From our experience we have come to the conclusion that all herbicide variants have increased production of statistically assured production, with the exception of the

variant treated with Pulsar 40 1,2l / ha applied in postemergence, which is due to the infestation of the crop until the time of treatment with monocotyledons and dicotyledons and especially with monocots (Table 3).

Table 3

The influence of herbicide treatments on pea production 2019

No. Var	Herbicides	Dose l,kg/ha	Application time	Production q/ha	Difference +/- to Mt.	Significance
1	Untreated	-	-	4,3	-	-
2	Dual Gold 960EC	1,5	preem	8,3	4,0	x
3	Dual Gold 960EC	2	preem	7,7	3,4	x
4	Pendigan 330 EC	5	preem	9,7	5,4	xx
5	Corum + Gramin 5EC	1,2+1	post	9,3	5,0	xx
6	Pulsar 40 + Gramin 5EC	1,2+1	post	11,4	7,1	xxx
7	Pulsar 40	1,2	post	5,8	1,5	-
8	Pendigan 330 EC+ Pulsar 40	3,5+1,2	preem+post	9,5	5,2	xx
9	Stomp Aqua + Pulsar40	3+1,2	preem+post	10,4	6,1	xxx
10	Stomp Aqua + Butoxone M 40	3+2	preem+post	10,0	5,7	xx
11	Stomp Aqua + Butoxone M 40	3+2,5	preem+post	11,0	6,7	xxx
12	Dual Gold 960EC + DMA Extra 600SL	1,5+0,2	preem+early post	10,8	6,5	xxx

DL 5% = 3,17 q/ha 1% = 4,31 q/ha 0,1% = 5,85 q/ha

We also studied the influence of herbicide treatments on pea germination, and then it can be concluded that for each herbicide treatment the germination was equally sensitive (Table 4).

Table 4

The influence of herbicide treatments on germination in pea culture 2019

No. Var	Herbicides	Dose l,kg/ha	Application time	Germination %
1	Untreated	-	-	87,6
2	Dual Gold 960EC	1,5	preem	84,3
3	Dual Gold 960EC	2	preem	79,0
4	Pendigan 330 EC	5	preem	84,3
5	Corum + Gramin 5EC	1,2+1	post	83,3
6	Pulsar 40 + Gramin 5EC	1,2+1	post	81,0
7	Pulsar 40	1,2	post	82,3
8	Pendigan 330 EC+ Pulsar 40	3,5+1,2	preem+post	86,6
9	Stomp Aqua + Pulsar40	3+1,2	preem+post	82,0
10	Stomp Aqua + Butoxone M 40	3+2	preem+post	82,0
11	Stomp Aqua + Butoxone M 40	3+2,5	preem+post	80,0
12	Dual Gold 960EC + DMA Extra 600SL	1,5+0,2	preem+early post	83,3

CONCLUSIONS

The researches were carried out in the year 2019 in the pea culture.

The experiments were located in Satu-Mare county at the Agricultural Development Research Station Livada on a stagnogleized preluvosol with a pH of 5.19, a clay content of 20.9% and a humus content of 2.82.

The herbicides applied to the crop of peas showed a very good selectivity for each variant.

The most effective herbicides were Stomp Aqua 3l / ha applied in pre-emergence associated with the herbicide Pulsar 40 1.2l / ha applied in post-emergence, Pendigan 330 EC 3.5l / ha plus Pulsar 40 1.2 l.2 / ha and Dual Gold 960 EC 1 , 5 l / ha applied in pre-emergence associated with DMA Extra 600 SL applied early post-emergence (when the pea is in the thorn phase, BBCH 11).

Treatments only on the vegetation of a single herbicide ensure a reduced control, due to the monocotile species, partially controlled by the Pulsar 40 herbicide.

It can be concluded that statistically assured production increases were obtained in each herbicidal variant, except in the variant treated with Pulsar 40 1,2l / ha, where the production increase was not statistically insured.

The herbicides tested did not have a negative influence on germination.

The production obtained at Netratat shows that no increase of production can be obtained in pea culture without combating weeds.

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RESEARCH REGARDING THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE TECHNOLOGY IN THE CULTURE OF THE ECOLOGICAL SPINACH GROWN IN THE SOLARIUMS

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Abstract

Organic farming aims to increase the quality and quantity of production, and minimize the negative effects of agriculture. Spinach, a vegetable whose leaves are edible, is rich in vitamins and mineral salts and highly appreciated by consumers. The present research aims to establish an optimum density, using more distances between rows. The ecological culture was established in the solarium, with variants and repetitions. The results showed that both increasing and decreasing the distance between rows led to a decrease in production. The quality of production has shown that an increase in density leads to a decrease in quality, and a decrease in density up to certain limits has the effect of a qualitative increase.

Key words: spinach, density, production

INTRODUCTION

Organic farming aims to harmonize the dynamic interactions between soil, plants, animals and humans or, in other words, between the ecological, economic and social supply of agro-ecosystems and human needs for food, clothing and housing. Being a type of sustainable agriculture (Toncea, 1999), the purpose of organic farming can be expressed through a mini-max type function: maximizing yields and minimizing the negative side effects of agricultural activities (Toncea, 1997, 1999).

As a rule, agricultural systems are constantly moving and changing, their evolution following a path whose final coordinates are different from the initial ones (Toncea and Alecu, 1999).

Spinach, a dioecious plant, very resistant to low temperatures, is cultivated for its leaves, eaten raw, but especially cooked in various forms. According to FAOSTAT (FAO) data from 2012-2013, China produces 91% (21 067 800 t) of world spinach production, followed by the US with 1% (336 200 t).

Spinach is known for its high iron content, it also has high levels of provitamin A, vitamin B9, vitamin K, vitamin C and antioxidant compounds, with health protection effects.

With 23 calories per 100 g of product, spinach is a low-calorie vegetable, but it is a good source of minerals and trace elements: it contains a lot of iron, magnesium, calcium, potassium, copper, zinc, iodine, selenium.

Contrary to a persistent legend, spinach is not the best source of dietary iron. The iron content of spinach was greatly overestimated in the 19th century. According to Aprifel com. (Agency for Fruit and Vegetable Research and Information) spinach contains 2.14 mg / 100g. Spinach iron is also much better absorbed by the body when accompanied by a source of vitamin (N. Lowry), for example with lemon juice. Spinach also contains a large amount of oxalic acid that inhibits iron uptake.

Spinach is rich in nitrates that turn into nitrites through bacteria in the mouth. These nitrites are involved in vasodilation and blood thinning, which improves blood flow to certain areas of the brain that, over time, are less perfused.

A daily dose of spinach can prevent dementia and cognitive decline by improving this cerebral blood flow (Tennille D. Presley et al.).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to reach the proposed objectives, in the autumn of 2017 (November) a comparative competition culture was established, with six variants in three repetitions, in a micro-vegetable farm, certified ecologically. The location of the mono factorial experience was made in a solarium 50 m long, 10 m wide and 4.5 m high. The variation of the variants in the experience was done according to the method of the subdivided blocks. The statistical processing of the experimental data was done by analyzing the variance.

The biological material was represented by the spinach variety Géant d'hiver, a productive, cold-resistant variety (ecologically certified seed).

The experimental variants targeted different densities materialized by different distances between rows, the distance between plants in a row was the same (7 cm, made by thinning).

Experimental variants:

- V1 Mt. - the distance between rows of 15 cm
- V2- the distance between rows of 10 cm
- V3- the distance between rows of 20 cm
- V4- the distance between rows of 25 cm
- V5- the distance between rows of 30 cm
- V6- the distance between rows of 35 cm

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The technology applied in the experimental culture was the ecological technology of spinach culture. In spring 2018, three leaf crops were made. The analysis of the total spinach production is presented in table 1. Even if it is an ecological culture, it is observed that the total production approaches some variants of the solarium productions in the conventional culture. As mentioned the distance between rows in the control variant was 15cm, and at V2 an even higher density was tried, respectively 10cm. This variant was the only one that recorded a leaf production below the control production level. In relative production this meant 80.46% of the production of variant V1. The difference was provided statistically, negative distinctly significant. To this small production is also added the smaller size of the leaves which resulted in a lower yield at harvest.

The variant with the largest production of spinach leaves, was V4 at which the distance between the rows was 25 cm. Compared with the control, this variant registered a production increase of 77.09%, in absolute production meaning over 10 t / ha. The difference from the witness was statistically assured, very significant positive. The high production of leaves shows that in this variant the nutrition space was well balanced, each plant benefited from sufficient light, harvesting easily.

The next variant with high leaf production was V2. This version yielded 2.05 kg / m² in absolute production, more by 0.74 kg / m² than the control variant. The difference was ensured statistically, positive very significant. The greater distance between the rows allowed the plants to develop bigger, heavier leaves, but at m² the production did not reach the production level from V4. In the case of V3, the production increase compared to V1 was 32.82%, this difference was statistically assured, very significant positive.

Table 1

Spinach production Husasău de Tinca 2018

Cr. no.	Variant	Absolute production of spinach kg/m ²	Relative production of spinach %	± d kg/m ²	Significance
1	V1 Mt.	1,31	100,00	0,00	-
2	V2	1,03	80,46	-0,28	oo
3	V3	1,74	132,82	+0,43	xxx
4	V4	2,32	177,09	+1,01	xxx
5	V5	2,05	156,48	+0,74	xxx
6	V6	1,57	119,84	+0,26	xx

LSD 5%=0,15

LSD 1%=0,22

LSD 0,1%=0,31

The greater the distance between rows (35 cm) from the V6 variant, marked an increase in the production of leaves, but not as large as in the other variants. Thus, 1.56 kg / m² was harvested more by 0.26 kg / m² than in the case of the control. The difference was statistically assured, positive distinctly significant.

Table 2

The quality of spinach production Husasău de Tinca 2018

Nr crt.	Variant	Total production	Cal.extra from total		Cal.I from total		Cal. II from total	
			Kg/m ²	%	Kg/m ²	%	Kg/m ²	%
1	V1 Mt.	1,31	0,67	51,14	0,34	25,95	0,30	22,90
2	V2	1,03	0,48	46,60	0,23	22,33	0,32	31,06
3	V3	1,74	0,93	53,44	0,59	33,90	0,22	12,64
4	V4	2,32	1,68	72,41	0,47	20,25	0,17	7,32
5	V5	2,05	1,75	85,36	0,21	10,24	0,09	4,39
6	V6	1,57	1,12	71,33	0,23	14,64	0,22	14,01

An important parameter that was then analyzed was the quality of spinach leaves harvested from all variants and repetitions. Table 2 presents the quality of leaf production for each variant, divided into the three qualitative stages. The qualitative production was expressed both in kg / m² and in% of total production for each variant and quality step. Regarding the extra quality, it can be seen that, except for the V2 variant, all the variants registered over 50% of the total production. The too small distance between the rows, so a higher density from the V2 variant, did not bring a higher quality, making only 46.60% of the total production. The highest production of extra quality was obtained by the V5 variant, where 85.36% of the total production, represented by the leaves of spinach of superior quality.

The production of spinach of the first quality, had values between 10.24% in the variant V5 and 33.90 in V3. Regarding the leaves of the second quality, it registered values between 4.39% in v5 and 31.06% in the V2 variant.

CONCLUSIONS

The researches regarding the establishment of an optimum density at the ecological culture of the spinach cultivated in the solariums, allowed to draw some conclusions.

1. The density of spinach plants, realized by the distance between rows and between plants in a row, influences both the production and the quality of the leaves.

2. The best distance between the rows is 25cm from the V4 variant, which has achieved a production of 2.32 kg / m² and a production increase over the control of over 70%.

3. Several plants per unit area, respectively a distance between rows of 10 cm, from variant V2, do not generate a higher production. Only 1.3 kg / m² was the amount of leaves harvested from this variant.

4. The decrease in density, that is to say 30cm and 35cm between the rows of the V5 and V6 variants, led to the decrease of the production, to 2.05 kg / m² respectively 1.57 kg / m² to V6.

5. The high density caused not only a small production but also a lower quality. This happened at V2, where the production of extra quality reached only 46.60 di total production.

6. With a percentage of 85.36% extra quality leaves, the V5 variant obtained the best quality among the analyzed variants.

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DEPENDANCE OF GROWTH OF APPLE TREES MEASURED BY OFF-SEASON PRUNING IN KOSOVO CLIMATE CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Apple fruit productivity is depended in many factors such as is the influence of pruning for apple fruit productivity. "Red Delicious" and "Idared" apple varieties growth can differ even though they are planted in same year. This can cause as well different fruit production and vegetative growth. How many fruits are produced depends as well from the vegetative growth of the trees, calculation the volume of canopy determine what is the growth of the trees and what can be the fruit production. As we evaluated the growth of the apple orchard in the previous years with pruning we gave the crown shape and later to determine which would be the canopy growth, lowering the bearing volume so in next year we would see the tree response, directed in fruit bearing or vegetative growth. Canopy volume of "Idared" was higher compared to "Red Delicious" and in this case we would have higher fruit production in the first fruit than the second variety. Apple orchard had a normal growth in the first years, from the results of measurement that in the coming years fruit productivity will be according to the variety. Orchard is expected to have average fruit production and growth, even though varieties had different growth on previous years.

Key words: apple orchard, pruning, tree growth, productivity, MM-106

INTRODUCTION

Apple fruit productivity is depended in factors such as rainfall, irrigation, soil type, wind, but as much as in the agricultural practices applied in the orchard.

The performance of cereals and vegetable in recent year has been decreased, farmers find themselves into a new market, changing from cereals to fruit trees is promising. There are many factors which define a good fruit to be sold in the market.

Seedling use for planting is not a common practice anymore, where use of combination of rootstock and variety is better (Di Vaio et al., 2009). Root pruning can be used to reduce control growth of trees in orchards (Ferree, 1997), which is an effective method of reducing tree size in an ultra-high density planting system (Khan et al., 1998).

Interaction between fruit load and water stress must be taken into account when studying the responses of fruit tree to regulated deficit irrigation (RDI) (Ruiz-Sanchez et al., 2010).

Thinning increases the efficiency of nitrogen and light use of leaves in densely planted orchard (Sun et al., 2016), this will result in higher biomass

production, where composting of tree biomass increase the overall sustainability of fruit production (Fiore et al., 2018). The interaction between young apple trees are obviously complex, orchards as well provide food and shelter for predatory beetles (Merwin, 1994; Markó et al., 2017).

Suitable technique for mitigation the adverse effects of a water deficit on fruit growth should produce an improvement in tree water status and least maintain assimilation capacity (Lopez et al., 2006). There was a significant irrigation x cropland interaction on fruit weight at harvest (Ebel, Proebsting, & Evans, 1995) and using irrigation could be used to save significant amounts of water.

Correct use of drip irrigation can save water, reduce groundwater pollution, and improve water use efficiency and harvest index, irrigation-deprivation treatments made significant enhancing effects on fruit quality (Lampinen et al., 2001). The smaller canopy volume per tree of “Delicious” variety in each system indicates the planting density for this cultivar should have been closer than for “Empire” for optimum performance which resulted with losses for “Delicious”(T. L. Robinson, Lakso, & Carpenter, 1991).

Correspondingly, greater light penetration was positively related to redness of the bark, total leaf (N), flower bud, fruit yield, fruit skin colour, soluble solids, and firmness as well as reduced diseases occurrences in the leaves of “Fuji” apple (Jung & Choi, 2010). The equation which should be used to predict weight from crown volume depends upon the plant species and the sampling date. For robust species with ample edible biomass per plant but with inherent variability among plants, the log-log function may yield best results (Bryant & Kothmann, 1979).

One-year tree growth determines productivity of the orchards, but to consolidate a good orchard one should maintain tree growth and crown shape and apple productivity, measurements should be made. Tree canopy growth and other relevant factors will define how will be the productivity of the orchard. I evaluated the vegetative growth of apple trees hence I will observe in the coming year the yield response which would come from the effects of pruning.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Orchard management require process to reach the productivity. On the researched orchard which was planted in the fall of 2013 are planted apple varieties Idared and Red Delicious grafted in vegetative rootstock with average of growth MM-106 (Malling-Merton 106). Planting distance were 3.80 by 2.0 m. Crown type formation is with “Central Leader”.

For the growth and development of fruit trees are important climatic and soil conditions and applied common agricultural techniques. For the place where orchard is an average yearly temperature of 10.4 °C average of rainfall of 600 mm. In June we have and average of temperature of 30 °C while in January from -0.6 °C.

Based on the agro-pedological research which has been done in the area where the orchard has been planted, that the soil type is alluvium. Other chemical soil factors like pH is weak acidic, favourable for the orchard, good infiltration rate, water holding capacity.

Rootstock MM-106 is an apple rootstock with average growth. MM-106 is the best vegetative rootstock. It is resistant against bloody tree louse *Erisoma lanigerum* and its easy multiplied. Apple varieties which are grafted in MM-106 rootstock have average growth. Rootstock MM-106 is relatively resistant against Fire Blight (*Erwinia amylovora*) and frost. Sensitive to apple collar rot (*Phytophthora cactorum*) and apple powdery mildew (*Podosphaera leocotricha*).

Idared and Red Delicious variety are well spread varieties and likely planted tree types from farmers. Have an average close blooming time it is well spread variety around the world. They are diploid varieties with average early blooming an important factor for fruit production. Variety has average growth. Its fruits are ripened at the end of September and successfully can be saved for a long period of time. These trees have good growth in narrow crown, until goes into fruitification.

Measurement of the growth of the apple orchard was done at the end to vegetation, estimation of their growth was done. As further research in the same trees where the samples were taken we will follow for the next coming year their growth. Measurements were done for their canopy volume growth, numbers of fruits and their weight and number of new shoot found in the new places where the pruning has been applied. Canopy is a factor which determines how much fruit can a tree can hold. Depending on the volume of the apple canopy the higher it will be the higher the productivity of the fruits will be.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Orchards with the passage of time have changed the way of cultivation of crown type, needs of farmers and creativity made them and researchers finding the best crown by the request of the farmer and economising. “Central Leader” crown type is a new crown type which is being applied where it is more favourable for farming since it takes less time to form it per tree and harvesting quicker. The system has a pyramid-shaped tree with its tiers of branches spaced along the trunk, each

distribution of the branches makes impact on fruit quality and production (T. Robinson, Lakso, & Ren, 1991).

The consistent production of the fruits in the trees and their quality can be accomplished when we have done the right pruning. Researched orchard resulted for crown formation of “Central leader” and the influence of pruning at apple trees, has included data for vegetative growth parameters before and after apple pruning (Table 1).

Table 1

Apple tree measurements						
Variety	Rootstock	Trunk diameter	Trunk height	Width between rows	Width in rows	Crown heights
Idared	MM106	44.1	66.6	166.5	192.8	208.8
		44.1	66.6	132.3	154.3	192.7
				20.5%	19.9%	7.7%
Red Delicious	MM106	43.93	59.1	161.1	187.7	201.9
		43.93	59.1	130.6	163.1	188.3
				18.9%	13.1%	6.7%

Trunk diameter is continuously thickening. Its width is depended from parent’s traits and rootstock where variety has been grafted. The biggest diameter of trunk had Idared variety and thinnest Red Delicious. On the table can be seen that an average they had a close thickness of trunk in two varieties.

Trunk height, it determines the height between the grafted place to the first tree branches coming out of trunk. Highest height of trunk was at Idared variety while lowest was for Red Delicious in average. “Central leader” is crown type with average height of the trunk. Based on the research of Zajmi et al. (2006) “Central leader” crown has trunk height of 50 – 60 cm above soil surface. Where in our research we can see that there is a significant increase of trunk height which be a change from the crown height.

Crown width between rows – highest width between apple trees was at Idared variety while smaller at Red Delicious has been decreased for 18.89 %. In this case is important to have smaller numbers since this is the path between rows where gives the ability to easily access the orchard.

Crown width in row – the highest width in the row has been at Idared variety for 192.7 cm while it was smaller at Red Delicious for 209.7 cm. We must consider to now have large number of stems in-rows, but we can leave branches longer as much this does not cause any problem.

Crown height is important for crown formation. The differences could be seen to be minimal before and after pruning. Decrease of the height after pruning for Idared variety was from 7.72 %, while at Red Delicious was 6.74%. In case of applying manual pruning it should be kept at the level of human reach height for easily/faster harvesting. Light distribution generally improves as tree size and canopy depth decrease. Efficiency of fruit management and biological efficiency are greater for small trees (T. Robinson et al., 1991).

One-year growth of the branches, it has been proved that because of not being in a relationship of the one-year growth and fruit-bearing it brings trees to the condition, so they produce one year and another one is failure for fruit production. In this case without successful vegetative growth we would not have fruit production. Based on the analysis of vegetative growth of one vegetation of the apple varieties, Idared and Red Delicious we have concluded that: Idared had higher number of shoots but shorter while Delicious had less shoot but longer.

Idared variety had better shoot growth and smaller number of their growth, while Red Delicious had bit less shoot and their growth in length was longer. In this case in one-year vegetation growth was found higher at Red Delicious (sample 2) compared to Idared variety (sample 1) (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. One year branch growth of apple trees

With random selection from each cultivar has been taken 5 apple trees in three repetition respectively 15 apple trees from each cultivar, and based on the measurement of some parameters where we considered as important to determine tree growth:

Trunk diameter of 20 cm from the grafted place, height of trunk from grafted place to first branches, crown width between rows, crown width in the rows, crown height, crown dimension of apple varieties before and after pruning, one-year growth of branches.

From our starting point of the research to determine the growth of apple cultivars and find how will be their response to the growth we need to calculate what is the canopy volume of apple crown for fruit bearing. Since our crown type is with central leader the shape can be considered as circular cone which the formula for calculation is relevant for the measurement which has been done (Bryant & Kothmann, 1979).

ig. 2. Equation for volume calculation

$$V = \pi r^2 \frac{h}{3}$$

r Radius

h Height

Results for

“Red Delicious” variety, respectively the radius average and the volume of canopy after and before pruning.

Table 2

Measurements on Red Delicious variety			
Radius average	Before Pruning	Radius average	After Pruning
146	3.0	128	2.3
110	2.3	119	2.2
100	1.9	99	1.6
132	2.6	127	2.3
170	4.5	172	4.3
147	3.2	145	3.0
130	2.9	138	2.9
175	4.1	166	3.8
107	2.1	123	2.3
122	2.3	128	2.4
cm	square metre	cm	square metre

Table 3

Measurements on Idared variety			
Radius average	Before Pruning	Radius average	After Pruning
138	2.6	132	2.3
158	3.5	140	2.7
162	3.6	114	2.5
120	2.9	89	1.9
147	3.4	115	2.4
135	2.5	96	1.8
142	3.3	112	2.4
115	2.2	90	1.7
122	2.8	96	2.1
137	3.5	114	2.5
cm	square metre	cm	square metre

Results above show us that the decrease of the crown on the each varieties pruned although has been in an increased value at Idared Variety for 80% compared to Red Delicious where it has been for 16 % in average.

Fig. 3. Differences between tree growth of varieties

In both cases where has been applied pruning the canopy of crown was done higher and in some less as seen in the graph where the samples have been shown.

Since the intensity of pruning was achieved at this point and the orchard was planned to get into production in the next vegetation the pruning was done properly. From this we achieve a normal growth of the crown and the fruit bearing can be at the maximum capacity.

Fruit quality of these two cultivars might be the highest quality which can represent the market demand of these two apple cultivars. And the percentage distribution of the apples in the size classes on the fruit trees which is randomly the weight of the fruits it is bigger in lower canopy and lower in higher canopy but in the case when we would apply this specific pruning method we would have the same amount of the weight for each fruit in the same position inside the canopy. Considering relevant weather conditions we would have a proper growth of apple trees, a continuous fruit production in the coming year and renewing each apple branches with new tree shoots.

CONCLUSIONS

The researched vegetative parameters from pruning of apple varieties of Idared and Red Delicious grafted in vegetative apple rootstock MM-106, we can conclude that:

- Diameter and height of the trunk was bigger at Idared variety compared to Red Delicious variety which had the diameter and trunk height also crown diameter in rows and height was higher at Idared variety compared to Red Delicious variety. Crown dimensions after pruning at Idared variety has been decreased on average of 17%, while at Red Delicious has been decreased for 13%.
- Annual growth of the shoots has been higher at Red Delicious while for Idared variety had shorter shoot length.
- Since the canopy of the orchard was different and the after pruning we would expect a higher production in the orchard for each varieties
- Volume of the crown has been decreased in both varieties after pruning concluding that orchard is well developed in the previous years.
- Apple fruit growth depends on the leaves which are found in the canopy, best developed canopy of fruit trees higher the productivity of fruits
- Fruit bearing of the trees might be higher in Idared variety since from the plantation date we had more vegetative growth, trees are well developed they can support fruit production in higher rate.

Based on the measurement we could have seen that the growth of trees was the same on the year when we started our research, orchard varieties had different growth in previous year which might be an indicator that the orchard had varied growth.

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BEHAVIOR OF SOME LETTUCE VARIETIES IN ECOLOGICAL CULTURE WITH FOOD AND DECORATIVE VALUES

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Abstract

Lettuce is much more appreciated by consumers for its low quantity of calories, but high in vitamins and mineral salts and many in parallel, especially when presented throughout the period. The assortment of varieties is very rich, many of them and an ornamental appearance, making them available for landscaping. The study of the behavior of several varieties of lettuce has revealed from time to time while there is a certain variety and potential production as well.

Key words: lettuce, varieties, production potential

INTRODUCTION

Vegetables are of particular importance in nutrition due to the contribution of vitamins and mineral salts, indispensable to the human body; they are the raw material for the canning factories and not least, an important source of income for those who cultivate them (Apahidean Al.; Maria Apahidean, 1994).

Of the green vegetables, the lettuce occupies the first place both in terms of consumption but also of the cultivated areas. The lettuce is of great nutritional importance due to its high carbohydrate content 2-3,5%; protein 1-1,6%; carotene 1-3 mg / 100g fresh product; vitamins B1-0.07 mg / 100 g fresh product; B2-0.12 mg / 100 g fresh product; C - 5-20 mg / 100 g fresh product and phosphorus salts: 1-7 mg / 100 g fresh product and potassium salts 260 mg / 100 g fresh product. The lettuce culture in the field, greenhouses and solariums also makes it available for consumption even in winter and early spring, when vitamin deficiencies are more pronounced. The lettuce is used for consumption, mainly in the raw state, in some culinary dishes, however, it is subjected to the boiling process (Bodea, 1984). Lettuce grown in the field has a higher vitamin C content than forced or protected crop (Horgoș, 2003).

An adverse influence on the health of the consumers is the nitrates of the lettuce. The level of nitrate content in lettuce is influenced by both genetic (cultivar used) and ecological (temperature, light intensity, soil moisture) and technological factors (nitrogen fertilization, use of fertilizers

with gradual release of the active substance). Of these factors, nitrogen fertilization and light intensity were found to have a major influence on the level of nitrates accumulated in the lettuce. (Cantliffe, 1974).

There are several varieties of lettuce, with quantities of vitamins, mineral salts and active principles depending on the variety, Marula is the richest in nutrients between the lettuce varieties, presenting significant quantities of vitamins A, B1, C, folic acid (B9), Mn and Cr. There is a very well recognized discrepancy between the nutritional value of the head lettuce and the other forms of lettuce, in favor of the latter (Rubatzky and Yamaguchi, 1997). The nutritional content of different types of lettuce per 100 g fresh substance is presented in table 1.2. Dr. Jean Valnet describes the main constituents known in lettuce, which are: lactucarium whose effects are comparable to those of opium; lactucarine; lactucine; lactic acid; asparagine; biosciamine; chlorophyll, vitamins A, B, C, D, E, Fe, Ca, P, I, Mg, Zn, with Na, Cl, K, Co, phosphates, sulphates, sterols, carotene. The lettuce has one of the most important qualities, namely the fact that within each type there are red, gold and of course green varieties, offering many possibilities for color combinations and contrast. It should be placed in the foreground because it is a small species. For decorative purposes it is recommended: sown on a single row or in strips between rows of leeks, onions, onions and garlic; making models in the form of circles, in the form of 8 or zigzags between newly planted or large celery plants; sown in the asparagus layers at the end of the harvest period (Larkom, 1997).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experience regarding the behavior of some varieties of lettuce was located in a vegetable micro-farm located in the northwest of Romania, in the town of Husasau de Tinca in 2015. The micro-farm includes culture in solariums and in the field. The varieties were placed in a solarium of dimensions 53m long and 10m wide, in a comparative competition culture with 13 variants in 3 repetitions. The witness was represented by the Domiziana variety. The experimental plots were placed using the subdivided blocks method, each variant had a number of 30 plants. The processing of the experimental data was done according to the single-factor experience model using variation analysis. The biological material was represented by 13 varieties, namely: Lolo Rosa, Red Eared Butterheart, Lettuce Bowl Red, Briscia Rosa, Amish Deer Tongue, Xeno's Density, Emerald Fan, Lettuce Bowl Green, Cressonnette du Maroc, LolloBionda, Blonde Maraichere, Ballon and Domiziana.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the present experience the early production was analyzed for each variety, the average of the distributions being recorded and statistically processed in table 1. Analyzing the overall early production, it is observed that most varieties have a lower early relative to the control. The best early production was recorded in the Lollo Bionda variety with an increase of early production of 59.55%, the difference from the control being statistically assured, very significant positive. With a relative production of 3.75 kg / m², the Emerald Fan variety had a production of 1.08 kg / m² greater than the control. And this difference from the witness was statistically assured, very significant positive.

With a slightly lower production increase of only 17.97%, the Blonde Maraichere variety was in third place in terms of early age. The difference from the witness was statistically positive, distinct, significant. Although the Cressonnette du Maroc and Amish Deer Tongue varieties obtained early yields higher than the Domiziana variety, the difference from the control was quite small, failing to exceed the $p = 5\%$ threshold, thus not being statistically assured. If these were some varieties that had an impurity higher than the control, the rest of the varieties made early productions below the Domiziana variety. Thus the worst early production was recorded in the Lettuce Bowl Red variety, which accounted for only 60% of the control production. The difference from this was ensured statistically, negative, very significant.

Table 1

Early lettuce production					
Nr. Crt.	Variety	Absolute production kg/m ²	Relative production %	±d kg/m ²	Signification
1.	Lolo Rosa	1,89	70,78	-0,78	000
2.	Red Earred Butterheart	2,34	87,64	-0,33	0
3.	Lettuce Bowl Red	1,83	68,53	-0,84	000
4.	Brischia Rosa	2,15	80,52	-0,52	00
5.	Amish Deer Tongue	4,82	105,61	+0,15	-
6.	Xeno's Density	2,24	83,89	-0,43	00
7.	Emerald Fan	3,75	140,44	+1,08	xxx
8.	Lettuce Bowl Green	1,62	60,67	-1,05	000
9.	Cressonnette du Maroc	2,91	108,98	+0,24	-
10.	Lollo Bionda	4,26	159,55	+1,59	xxx
11.	Blonde Maraichere	3,15	117,97	+0,48	xx
12.	Ballon	1,95	73,03	-0,72	000
13.	Domiziana (Martor)	2,67	100,00	0,00	-

LSD 5 % = 0.32 LSD 1 % = 0.42 LSD 0.1 % = 0.5

With early low yields, the varieties Lolo Rossa, Lettuce Bowl Red and Ballon were noted, varieties that made between 68.53% and 73.03% of the production of the Domiziana variety. And in these varieties the differences from the witnesses were provided statistically, negative, very significant. Brischia Rosa and Xeno's Density varieties were slightly earlier with smaller

differences compared to the control of 4.3 t / ha and 5.2 t / ha in Briscia Rosa. These differences from Domiziana were provided statistically negative, distinctly significant. The Red EarredButterheart variety came closest to witnesses, providing 87.64 of its production. The difference was ensured statistically negative, significant.

If, in the case of early production, the differences from the control, both in the positive and negative sense, were quite large, in the case of the total lettuce production it is observed that most varieties obtained higher yields than the control. This denotes the fact that many of them are considered only of ornamental value (by some authors), but also have a high production potential. The only variety that produced a lower production than the control, but which can be taken into account was Briscia Rosa with a relative production of 87.32% of that of the control. The difference from the witness was statistically insured, significantly negative.

Another three varieties had a lower production potential than the respective control LolloRossa, Red EarredButterheart and Amish Deer Tongue, but the differences with the control did not exceed the threshold $p = 5\%$, thus not being statistically assured. There were several varieties with higher yields than the control, but the differences were not statistically assured being very small. These were Lettuce Bowl Red and Ballon.

Xeno's Density variety with an absolute production of 4.78 kg / m² and a production increase of 14.35% was the first variety to be noted with a productive potential that deserves to be recorded compared to the control. The difference from Domiziana was ensured statistically significant positive. In ascending order it is followed by the Blonde Maraichere variety, which compared to Domiziana recorded 8.6 t / ha more. The difference was ensured statistically, positive, distinct, significant.

Table 2

Total lettuce production					
Nr.crt	Variety	Absolute production kg/m ²	Relative production %	±d kg/m ²	Signification
1.	Lolo Rosa	3,84	91,86	-0,34	-
2.	RedEarredButterheart	3,79	90,66	-0,34	-
3.	LettuceBowlRed	4,56	109,90	+0,38	-
4.	Brischia Rosa	3,65	87,32	-0,53	0
5.	AmishDeerTongue	3,96	94,73	-0,22	-
6.	Xeno's Density	4,78	114,35	+0,60	X
7.	Emerald Fan	5,94	142,10	+1,76	Xxx
8.	LettuceBowl Green	5,22	124,88	+1,04	Xxx
9.	Cressonnette du Maroc	6,48	155,02	+2,30	Xxx
10.	LolloBionda	5,10	122,00	+0,92	Xxx
11.	Blonde Maraichere	5,04	120,57	+0,86	Xx
12.	Ballon	4,20	102,94	+0,02	-
13.	Domiziana (Martor)	4,18	100,00	0,00	-

LSD 5% = 0.50
LSD 1% = 0.65
LSD 0.1% = 0.88

Of the analyzed varieties, the highest productive potential was registered the Cressonnette du Maroc variety, whose owners managed to reach a production of over 60 t / ha and a production increase of 55%, compared to the control. This was ensured statistically positive, significant. Quite large yields were also obtained by the varieties Emerald Fan and Lettuce Bowl Green and LolloBionda with significant production increases from 22% at LolloBionda to 42% at Emerald Fan. All the differences from the witness were statistically positive, positive, very significant.

The ornamental appearance of the 13 varieties analyzed

In this experience, the food value and the decorative value of the 13 lettuce varieties were analyzed.

Due to the different size and color varieties of these varieties we were able to make different color combinations and contrasts.

The lettuce border

The edges of the lettuce are about 20 cm high with a very compact appearance created by the interweaving of the ridge leaves. By repeating the 13 varieties on two interspersed rows we obtained the appearance of a different colored and compact border.

The most used varieties of lettuce for curds are Lettuce Bowl Green and Lettuce Bowl Red because these varieties do not form heads but only leaf rosettes, which regenerate after they have been mowed or their leaves have been selectively harvested.

The lettuce boards can be placed along the alleys, or anywhere between vegetables and why not on the lawn making the transition from it to the vegetable garden or shrubs. They can be made from the same variety of lettuce, or from several combinations, from a single color or variously colored.

Lettuce in pots and gardeners

Another way to decorate the garden with lettuce is to use gardeners or pots. The lettuce is beautiful and decorative and in pots. They can be placed in any part of the garden, both on the lawn, tiles and on various supports.

CONCLUSIONS

The research regarding the behavior of some varieties of lettuce grown in the solariums allowed the elaboration of some conclusions and recommendations:

1. The dietary value of lettuce has been known since ancient times, and in recent decades this value has been filled with the decorative appearance of lettuce varieties.
2. Many of the varieties analyzed have their origin in the 20th century, however, their value was only revealed towards the end of the 20th century.

3. With a pleasant appearance with a customized name LolloBionda was also noted with the best early age of all the varieties studied, having an early production of 4.26 kg / m².

4. The chosen pointer proved to have a good early age, of the 13 varieties studied was 6th.

5. Even though most of the varieties studied have shapes and colors that differ more or less from the classic lettuce varieties, their production potential managed to surprise.

6. With a production of 6.48 kg / m² the Cressonnette du Maroc variety has proven to be the most productive, a production difficult to obtain even from the classic lettuce varieties.

7. 3.65 kg / m² is the absolute production obtained by the Briscia Rosa variety, practically the lowest production potential but compared to the productions presented by the specialized literature it is at an average level.

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THE STUDY OF THE ECONOMIC INDICATORS REGARDING THE ESTABLISHMENT AND MAINTENANCE OF A SUPER INTENSIVE HAZELNUT PLANTATION IN IRRIGATED SYSTEM

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Abstract

In the development of agriculture, especially fruit, it can be said that the least attention paid nut fruit species, which includes hazelnut. Our land settled mainly in import and annually tens of millions of dollars are allocated for importing hazelnuts. However, we have very good ecological and economic conditions for growing cultivated hazelnuts. The fact that in Romania the plantation of the peanut has not been extended is explained by the ignorance of the qualities of this tree and of the benefits derived from its features. Hazelnut fixes soil by preventing erosion, purifies the air, is a valuable medicinal plant, and peanut kernel is an extremely valuable food. With rational use of land capacity, we can get rid of import hazelnuts with the promise to become significant exporters. Hazelnut plantation is one of the most profitable agricultural businesses in our country, as it requires an average investment, which is amortized over a relatively short period of time compared to other crops, and generates profits. This paper resembles the importance of cultivating hazelnut and its costs including the establishing and maintaining the culture.

Key words: economic investment, super-intensive yard, hazelnut, harvest, expenses

INTRODUCTION

From the economic point of view, the favorable environmental conditions and with relatively modest economic investment relative to other types of fruit trees, hazelnut gives good yields, and hence a huge contribution. Hazelnut fruit is widely used in both the food industry and household, as well as confectionary industry, where the core of hazelnuts is used as raw material. The hazelnut fruit has great nutritional value and on that basis has the most important place in relation to other types of fruit trees. Hazelnut core contains a high percentage of high quality and easily digestible nutrients such as protein, fat, sugar, vitamins (A, B, and E) and minerals and other bioactive substances (Berar, 2012). It should be noted a very important development in areas with favorable environmental conditions for its development and that is the use of culture erosion field, as hazelnut has a shallow root system that binds land and on abandoned steep terrain can play an important role in the reorientation of the land and hiring labor to care and harvest the fruit hazelnut. With rising living standards especially in advanced industrial countries, the market consumes more fruits of hazelnut. There fore, a number of European countries (Spain, Italy,

Greece, Turkey, France, and Russia) that have favorable environmental conditions for growing hazelnuts, recently significantly increased areas under plantations of hazelnut. These countries along with the United States produce 90% of world production. Hazel has a very high success rate, and due to high energy and low prices as well as the shortage on the world market, many countries are trying to grow the hazel tree plantations over large areas. In our country, several hazelnut plantations were built that are designed for industrial and household use. However, due to deficiency of suitable grounds around, it is necessary to raise plantations of hazelnut throughout the country in order to minimize imports. Just to satisfy Romania's processing capacities it is necessary to raise at least 7,000 hectares of hazelnut plantations. The continuous increase in the consumption of hazelnuts in the world points to the existence of broad prospects for exports. Under natural conditions, hazelnut grows mainly on limestone substrate up to about 1500 meters above sea level. Also in cultures, hazelnuts can breed up to 600 meters in conditions where other fruit varieties and other crops provide less economic impact. Hazelnut requires light and heat to the lowest possible annual and daily temperature amplitude. Average annual air temperature should be above the 9^o C and annual rainfall exceeding 1000 mm (Mihaiescu, 1989). In conditions of severe frosts attention should be paid to the preparation of pollinators that are resistant to low temperatures. Hazelnuts are planted in loose, moist, deep permeable soil which should not be sour (Rosengarten F. jr., 1984).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Taking into account climate, soil and economic and organizational conditions and the possibility of processing and marketing of hazelnut, we need to choose the most suitable varieties. Main focus is to cultivate a native varieties for industrial processing and combined varieties traits that can be used for industrial and for fresh consumption, and also as a pollinator of main varieties. Planting will be done with a well-rooted plants.

The hazelnut variety used for the researched plantation is Gentile Romana. Is of Italian origin. Tree (bush) is a medium-vigorous and develops many offshoots. Blossoms medium early, initially produces very little and later on generously and regularly. It ripens in late August. Shell is light brown with dark stripes. Provides a lot of fruit that are empty or shriveled core. The shell of the fruit is slightly longer than the fruit with deep notches and holes which allows the fruit to fall out easily. The shape of the core is irregular and flat, weighing approximately 1.4 grams. Fruit weight is 3.7 grams. The taste of the core is sweet and without any flavor. Percentage of rancid core after a year and a half is about 4%, and after 3 years 22%. For processing can only be used with other varieties due to lack

of flavor. A good pollinator. Self-sterile variety is well-pollinated by Istria Long and Hallesche Reisen.

For the researched plantation there is used a distance of 4,5 meters between rows and between the terrace and 3 meters between plants . The entire number of planted seedling is 741/ha (super intensive). The most suitable time for planting hazelnut is in autumn, because the root system has significant activity during the winter. It is not rare for hazelnut to flourish in February, under favorable weather conditions (Adams M., 2019) Considering that terraces are made, by pushing and stretching the thick layer of soil with subsequent plowing, there is no need to dig holes in the classic sense. After preparation of soil, there are performed measurements and markings the places for planting. After that pits are dugged, deep enough and wide enough to place root system. Care should be taken that the seedlings from the time of removal from the trap to the planting do not stay more than an hour uncovered to avoid drying the hair roots that are very sensitive. Since the plants are placed in a pit on a depth at which one was in the nursery area, over the hair roots a layer of fine earth is placed (10 to 15 cm). This land is stepped on and over it again, another layer of earth is placed. If the soil is prepared without trenching but ordinary plowing, it is necessary to dig a hole the size of 60x60 cm. (Goian M.& co, 2002).

Crown system for the planted hazelnuts is established in the form of three branch system - branches that depart from one place. In the spring of the first year after planting, the trees are trimmed at 30 cm (Cociu V., 2007). Above the ground in order to foster the outbreak of two to three offshoots that will form the future shape of the crown to form three branch system. In the second year after planting the best secondary branch is selected, which follows the further growth of the shoots shortened to equalize the amount of growth. In the coming years unnecessary branches are removed (Crawford M.,2016). The goal is to provide enough sunlight in all fruiting. From the fifth year onwards, it is considered that the nut has entered in the full yielding potential. Hazelnuts from year 7 to 15 can give yield per tree from 3 to 5 kg, and from year 15 to 25 from 5 to 10 kg per tree. Fertilizer doses depends on the results of the analysis of hazelnut leaf and soil in the plantation. Land in the plantation is maintained in a state of barren fallow discing and herbicide application. The destruction of shoots is done by mechanical or chemical means (Himmelhuber, 2013).

Harvesting should be done as late as possible, at the stage of maximum physiological maturity. For the hazel tree the characteristic is that all the fruits on one tree do not ripen at the same time (Rutter, 2015). That is why waiting for the fruits to reach their physiological maturity is needed and that's when the shell is easily separated from the fruit and the fruit

massively starts to fall to the ground. Then the trees should be shaken with a previously placed sheet under them (Wilkinson, 2005).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Df= 22 years

De= 19 years

It= 95053,43 lei/ ha

Setting up expenses= 47578,15 lei/ ha

- Handmade works= 3580,00 lei
- Mechanical works= 4869,15 lei
- Materials= 39129,00 lei

Maintenance costs= 47475,28 lei/ ha

- Handmade works= 4527,5 lei
- Mechanical works= 2082,78 lei
- Materials = 40865,0 lei

Ca (annual depreciation rate) = 5002,81 lei/year

Operating expenses (Ce) = 21278,05 lei

- Handmade works= 9719,0lei
- Mechanical works= 1310,05 lei
- Materials= 10249,0 lei

Cd = 26280,85 lei/ha

Ci = 1576.85 lei/ha

P = 2000 kg/ ha

Cp= 13,93 lei/ kg

Pv= 20,00 lei/kg

V= 40000 lei/ ha

Pab= 12142,3 lei/ ha

I= 1942,77 lei/ ha

Pn= 10199,53 lei/ ha

R= 36,60 %

T (term of investment recovery) = 9 years

Pt= 193791,07 lei

Rec (economic return on investment) = 204 %

C_d= annual direct expenditure

C_i= annual indirect costs

C_t=annual entire costs

P=Production

C_p=Cost of production =C_t/P

P_v=Selling price

V=Value of annual production

P_{ab}=Gross annual profit

I=Tax= P_{ab} x 16%

P_n =Net annual profit $P_{ab} - I$
 R =Annual profit rate $P_n : C_t \times 100$
 T = Term of investment recovery= I_t / P_n
 P_t = Entire operating profit= $P_n \times D_e$

Fig. 1. Labor costs from the establishment of the culture to the entry on the fruit

Fig. 2. Material expenses from the establishment of the culture to the entry on the fruit

Fig. 3. Direct expenses recorded during the establishment of the hazelnut plantation

CONCLUSIONS

The highest labor costs are recorded at the establishment of the plantation, due to the planting of the seedlings. The highest material expenses are recorded in the 1st year, due to the value of the planting material and in the 2nd year it is maintained at higher values due to the value of the planting material used to fill gaps. The highest weights in total direct expenses, incurred when setting up a hazelnut plantation, have the material ones due to the value of the fruit planting material.

The term of investment recovery for 1 hectare hazelnut plantation is 9 years.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY REGARDING THE REGENERATIVE AND ORGANOGENIC CAPACITY OF EXPLANTS OF *Aylostera heliosa*, CULTIVATED "IN VITRO" IN THE PRESENCE IN THE SUBSTRATE OF THE AIB (3-INDOLEBUTYRIC ACID) AND 2,4-D (2,4-DICHLOROPHENOXYACETIC ACID)

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Abstract

Aylostera heliosa, decorative cactus both the port and the flower is a difficult species propagated by grafting, but has found a viable method of multiplication in vitro micropropagation. For this cactus can be successfully acclimatized need to develop a strong root system.

In order to establish the in vitro culture we harvested buds from *Aylostera heliosa* stems. Inoculation of the explants was done on a culture medium consisting of macro-elements and Fe EDTA Murashige-Skoog (1962), Heller micro-elements (1953), supplemented with 1,5 mg/l auxin, respectively, AIB (3-indolylbutyric acid) and 2,4-D (2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid).

The evolution of the explants was monitored for 90 days. The response of *Aylostera heliosa* explants to the presence in the culture medium of an equal amount of auxin, respectively 1,5 mg/l AIB and 1,5 mg/l 2,4-D, was very different; rhizogenesis was observed only in *Aylostera heliosa* grown on culture medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l AIB (V_1), the largest and largest strains were recorded in plants grown on culture medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_2) also callus formation.

Key words: cacti, vitrocultures, 3 indolylbutyric acid, 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, rootedness.

INTRODUCTION

Aylostera heliosa, cactus, decorative (Fig. 1) both in port - due thorns silvery-white edge aligned comb (Perez et al., 2002) and by red or orange flowers is a very difficult species multiplied by grafting (Myeong et al., 2004). *Aylostera heliosa* like other cacti can multiply rapidly and effectively by micropropagation in vitro (Karimi et al., 2010).

Cacti are considered to be extremely susceptible to the differentiation process when they are grown in mineral environments rich in growth regulators (Copăceacu, 2001), invariably inducing organogenesis processes.

In this experiment, our aim was to study the reactions of the phytoinoculi of *Aylostera heliosa* to the existence in the culture medium of an auxin, respectively, of 3-indolylbutyric acid (AIB) and 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), added at the same concentration of 1,5 mg/l. We thus obtained the following variants: V_0 or control group (medium without growth regulators), V_1 with 1,5 mg/l 3-indolylbutyric acid (AIB) added and V_2 with 1,5 added mg/l 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D).

Fig.1. *Aylosterahelios* stems and flowers

Auxins are phytohormones or growth regulators commonly used in tissue cultures, having stimulatory action on rhizogenesis, considering that the cumulative effect of endogenous auxin with the input of exogenous auxins, results in the greatest number of roots (Juárez et al., 2002). 3-Indolylbutyric acid (AIB) is part of the synthetic auxin class, but it seems to be found in nature, but only in some plant species (according to Moore, from Cachiță et al., 2004).

Among the synthetic auxins, 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) is also included, this being the most used and recommended growth regulator that stimulates the generation of calus in explants. According to Johnson et al. (1979b), callus formation was observed in vitro cultures of *Mammillaria elongata* by addition of auxin 2,4-D in the culture medium.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this experiment to order to initiate the *Aylosterahelios* in vitro culture, the plant material consisted from young stems harvested from mother plants. The material was sterilized by placing for one minute, in alcohol 96°, followed by a submersion operation, in a sodium hypochlorite solution 0,8% in proportion of 1:2 with water (one part sodium hypochlorite, 2 parts sterile water), which were added three drops of Tween 20, shaking continuously (Cachiță et al., 2004). After 20 minutes, the removal of disinfectant agent was achieved by washing the plant material in sterile water, in five consecutive rinses, of five minutes each, after which the plant material was deposited on aseptic filter paper rings, introduced in sterile Petri dishes. Sizing future inocula was performed under aseptic condition in horizontal laminar flow hood, with sterile air. Young stems were cut into spherical slices, which has the following dimensions: about 1 cm long, 0,5 cm thick and diameter of 0,5-1,5 cm, depending on the area from

which they were harvested. Explants modeling (Fig. 2) were done so that each has at least 2-3 areolae (Karimi et al., 2010).

The mineral medium culture used in the experiment consisted of: microelements and Fe-EDTA, (Murashige and Skoog, 1962), microelements (Medeiros et al., 2006), mineral mixture to which were added vitamins: HCl pyridoxine, HCl thiamine and nicotinic acid (each 1 mg/l), 100 mg/l m-inositol, 20g/l sucrose and 7g/l agar-agar, pH of the medium was adjusted to a value of 5.8.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of sectioning method of the young step to obtain *Aylostera* (Speg.) *heliosa* explants (where: a-young strain, b-sizing of young stems, c-explant represented from young stem d-explant represented as spherical rings)

In order to obtain the proposed alternatives, we added new developed nutrient medium devoid of growth regulators (V_0), version control, and variant V_1 to which 1,5 mg/l 3-indolylbutyric acid (AIB) was added and variant V_2 to which 1,5 mg/l 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) were added.

Sterilization of vials with medium was performed by autoclaving at a temperature of 121°C for 30 minutes. The recipients with medium culture capacity of 15 ml, and each were placed 5 ml of the medium. After cooling the media proceeded to inoculate explants, operation conducted in aseptic camera laminar flow, horizontal, with sterile air.

After inoculation, explants were vials were filled with polyethylene folia. Conditions in the growth chamber were as follows: illuminated with white light emitted by fluorescent tubes, photoperiod was under 16 hours light /24 h 1700 lux light intensity, temperature between 20-24°C.

Vitro plantlets reaction after inoculation was monitored for 12 weeks. Biometric assessments were taken at intervals of 30 days. Observations consisted from biomeasure: vitro plantlets leng regenerated from explants, number of callus formation, determining the number of neo stems and branches developed on the initial inocula.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At 90 days after the initiation of the experiment, the absolute value of the basal mean diameter of the *Aylostera heliosa* strains remained constant, respectively 1,3 cm (Fig. 3A), in the phytoinoculars belonging to the control group V₀ (medium lacking growth regulators) as well as those grown on mediums supplemented with 1,5 mg/l AIB (variant V₁) and 1,5 mg/l 2,4 D (variant V₂).

Fig. 3. Graphical presentation of the average values corresponding to the biometric parameters in the viticulture cultures of *Aylostera* (Speg.) *Heliosa*, on the aseptic base modified by us - (V₀ variant) - with 1.5 mg / l AIB (V₁ variant) and 1, 5 mg / l 2,4 D (variant V₂), data expressed in absolute values; (where:A - Average diameter of main stem; B - The average number of newly formed stems; C - The average diameter of the largest newly formed strain; D-Average number of roots; E - The average length of the largest root;F-Average number of calluses; G-Mean diameter of calluses).

Analyzing the tracked data it is found that inoculated and raised explants on mediums supplemented with 1,5 mg/l AIB (variant V₁) did not generate strains, these being generated on explants belonging to variant V₂ (medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l 2, 4-D) with 0,2 buds/variant (Fig. 3B) compared to the same parameter recorded in control V₀ (0,9 buds/variant), represents an increase of 22,22%.

Regarding the basal average diameter of the newly formed strains, we notice new shoots generated at the level of explants inoculated and raised on a medium lacking growth regulators (V_0), which with a value of this parameter of 0,4 cm (Fig. 3C) they marked a 50% increase (Fig. 3C), compared to the values recorded in the explants grown on the medium supplemented with 1,5 mg / l 2,4-D (V_2).

Fig. 4. Inoculates of *Aylostera (Speg.) heliosa*, 90 days after inoculation of explant "in vitro", where: A-on basic medium modified by us and lacking growth regulators (V_0); B-on basic medium with addition of 1,5 mg/l AIB (variant V_1); C-on basic medium with 1,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_2) addition; (iiv-inoc initially viable; nc-newly formed stems; ar-areola; sp-thorn; cl-callus; mc – culture medium).

Regarding the rhizogenesis, this phenomenon was manifested only in the phytoinoculi belonging to variants V_1 (medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l AIB), the average number of roots/variant being 1. In this case, due to the species characteristics, *Aylostera heliosa* has a pivoting root system, the newly formed roots, unlike those generated in explants of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis* grown on the same culture medium, are much thicker (Vidican, 2012).

The addition of 1,5 mg/l AIB (V_1) in the culture medium exerted a stimulatory effect on root growth (Vidican, 2013), the value of the average length of the longest root - in this case - was 0,8 cm.

Calus induction did not occur in *Aylostera heliosa* explants grown on medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l AIB (variant V_1), but it is noted that in explants belonging to variant V_2 (medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l 2,4-D) the average number of calluses/variant is 1,6 (Fig. 3D) higher than the values of the same parameter registered in control group V_0 (average lacking growth regulators), which in percentage values represents an increase of 160% (Fig. 3D). And as for the average diameter of the calus,

the highest values were also recorded in explants inoculated and raised on medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V₂), which exceeded control V₀ by 2,9 cm (Fig. 3E), which represents an increase of 126,1% (Fig. 3E).

The callus generated from the explants cultivated on a medium lacking growth regulators is located on the surface of the explant but also on the level of the culture medium, it shows signs of early senescence, a fact indicated by its creamy color or even its light brown (Fig. A). At the level of explants inoculated on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V₂) the callus was friable, snow-white (Fig. 4B), and due to abundance it covered the entire surface of the culture medium. (Vidicanet al., 2011).

It should be noted that although characteristic of *Aylosteira heliosa* is the comb-like alignment of the marginal spines that are white - silver, with a thickened basal area and a dark brown color, in the case of phytoinocles grown on culture medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l AIB (V₁), the central spines were bristled, long and reddish, depending on the characteristic aspect of the species (Fig. 4C and D). In the case of phyto-inoculants grown on culture medium without growth regulators (V₀), the spines maintained their characteristics in terms of shape, size and color (Fig. 4A).

These results allow us to assume that the presence in the culture environment of a certain amount of growth regulator enhances the great morphological plasticity of the catfish *Aylosteira heliosa*. It should be mentioned that, as regards the characteristics of spines in phytoinoculi belonging to variants V₁ (medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l AIB), they are specific to the traits of the genus *Aylosteira*, in which the central or marginal spines are very different from one species to another, in terms of shape (needles, straight, curved, etc.), their length (0,1-2,0 mm), areola position (seamed, combed in alignment) or their color (from transparent white to black) , passing through a wide range of shades of the other colors).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Comparing the data obtained from the evaluation of the evolution of *Aylosteira heliosa* explants at 90 days of viticulture, we noticed that, by supplementing the culture medium with 1,5 mg/l auxin, respectively AIB (variant V₁) and 2,4 D (variant V₂) there were significant differences in the response of phytoinoculi to the composition of the nutritional environment. Thus, explants cultivated on a medium lacking growth regulators (V₀) were noted by regeneration of new stems and by induction of callus, but did not form roots.

2. The number of newly formed strains at the level of explants grown on culture medium supplemented with 1,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V₂), was higher than the values registered by the same parameter in control group V₀ (medium

lacking growth regulators), by 22,22%, while their average basal diameter was 50% smaller than in the control.

3. The presence in the culture medium of 1,5 mg/l AIB (V_2) was sufficient to stimulate the rhizogenesis, in an average number of 1,0 root / variant that reached an average length of the largest root 0,8 cm.

4. The presence in the culture medium of 1,5 mg/l 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (V_2), favored the induction of calus, so after 90 days of viticulture in their level there is a 160% increase in the average number of calusis/variant and an increase of 126,1% of the value of the average diameter of the calusus compared to those grown on medium without growth regulator (V_0).

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THE INDUCEMENT OF THE ROOTEDNESS PROCESS OF *HIPPOPHAE RHAMNOIDES* CUTTING USING RADISTIM TYPE BIOACTIVE SUBSTANCES

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Abstract

Hippophae rhamnoides is a shrub cultivated as decorative plant for its small, lasting and shining leaves, linear (3-6cm/2.0-2.4 cm), with short tail (1.5-2.5 cm) and for the various colored sepals (green) gathered around the yellow, red flowers with no decorative value. In our country *Hippophae rhamnoides* is not very spreaded because of the shortage of cuttings caused by the low rate of multiplication. In order to increase the efficiency of multiplication on vegetative way, between 2018-2019, in the green houses from Oradea we have watched over the *Hippophae rhamnoides* cuttings rootedness process using stimulating substances of Radistim type.

Key words: *Hippophae rhamnoides*, rooting substrate variants, cuttings

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There were gathered cuttings semi-wooden 10-15 cm long. The experiment was organized in two variants: V₁-untreated standard and V₂-treatment with radistim 2, using 500 cutting per variant in four different times.

Cutting planting for striking roots has been made in perlite with 1-1.5 mm particles, placed on the parapet with a thickness of substratum of 12-14 cm. The treatment was made before planting. First there was renewed the humidity status. Then the cuttings were inserted in the powder stimulating substance (radistim 2) with 3-5 cm of their root.

The cuttings were planted for striking roots in the first decade of May. The distance between cuttings was 5x5 cm and the depth was 4-6 cm. The soil was well ramed in order to remove the air from the rootedness zone.

During the rootedness period the temperature oscillated between 18-27 celsius degrees in air and 20-21 celsius degrees in substratum. The substratum's humidity was 65-75% of total capacity of retaining and the relative humidity was 75-85%.

The light was directed by covering the cuttings with paper and the windows of the green house were whitewashed once the growing process started. For the variants differentiation there were made observations and determinations concerning the length of rootedness period, the proportion of rooted cuttings and the dimensions of new formed roots.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First roots appear at closed intervals of time for the two variants with a slight advantage for the cuttings treated with Radistim 2.

The period of complete rootedness process last 87 days (19.06-15.09).

After the striking root process the cuttings were dislocated from the rootedness substratum and they were passed in clay flower pots which have the diameter of 10-12 cm. In this pots the substratum is formed of: two parts peat, one part earth of leaves, one part compost and one part sand.

The number of rooted cuttings from the total cuttings planted for rootedness, for each variant registered growing values from 350 cuttings for V₁ (control, standard variant) to 440 cuttings for V₂ when the cuttings were treated with Radistim 2 (Table 1).

Table 1

The striking roots proportion of *Hippophae rhamnoides* cuttings at Santandrei's green houses (average values 2018-2019)

Variants	Number of rooted cuttings		±D	Semnification of the difference
	Absolute (pcs.)	Relatively (%)		
V ₁ -untreated standard (control variant)	350	100	-	-
V ₂ -treatment with Radistim	440	125	90	xxx

LSD 5% = 30,1

LSD 1% = 51,4

LSD 0.1% = 87,7

In relativals terms treatment with Radistim 2 increased the rate of cuttings striking roots with 25% comparatively with the untreated variant. From the statistic point of view this difference is considered as very meaningful.

The treatment with radistim 2 stimulates also the quality of rooted cuttings through the number and the dimension of the roots.

From table no. 2 arises that the average number of roots per cutting is growing from 10,5 pcs. at V₁-untreated, to 15,9 pcs. per cutting at V₂-treated with radistim 2.

In relativals terms the treatment with Radistim 2 increased the number of roots per cutting with 42% comparatively with the untreated variant. From the statistic point of view this difference is considered as very meaningful.

Table 2

Average number of roots per cutting (average values 2018-2019)

Variants	Average number of roots		±D	Semnification of the difference
	Absolute (pcs.)	Relatively (%)		
V ₁ -untreated standard (control variant)	10.5	100	-	-
V ₂ -treatment with Radistim	15.9	151,4	5,4	xx

LSD 5% = 4,3
 LSD 1% = 6,4
 LSD 0.1% = 9,6

The increased capacity of striking roots arises also from the number and the thickness of the newly formed plants' roots.

From the table no. 3 we can see that the lenght and the thickness of *Hippophae rhamnoides* cuttings vary between large limits with favor for those treated with Radistim.

Table 3

The lenght and the thickness of *Hippophae rhamnoides* rooted cuttings (average values 2018-2019)

Variants	The lenght of roots-extreme limits (cm)	Grouping the roots in accordance with its thickness		Total
		Pes.<1 mm	Pes. > 1 mm	
V ₁ -untreated standard (control variant)	0,5-11,4	3,9	8,4	12.3
V ₂ -treatment with Radistim	0.5-13,3	5,8	8,7	14,5

For the control variant the newly formed roots registered variable lenght between 0.5 and 11,4 cm. For the cuttings treated with radistim 2 the values were higher, between 0.5 and 13,3 cm.

Grouping the newly formed roots in accordance with its thickness, for the roots with diameter smaller than 1 mm there were registered values in growth from 3,9 pcs. for V₁ to 5,8 pcs. for V₂. For the roots with diameter bigger than 1 mm there were registered values in growth from 8,4 pcs. for V₁ to 8,7 pcs. for V₂.

CONCLUSIONS

* *Hippophae rhamnoides* as decorative species, with useful economic implications, can be multiplied through vegetative way by cuttings.

* The multiplication rate of *Hippophae rhamnoides* through cuttings can be stimulated by using biocative substances of Radistim type.

* Stimulating the rootedness process of semiwooden cuttings of *Hippophae rhamnoides* with bioactive substances of Radistim type guarantee a highly vegetative potential for newly formed plants.

* The stimulate substance Radistim increase the striking roots rate. So the treated cuttings stroke roots in proportion of 88% comparatively to 70% for those untreated.

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SOFTWARE USED FOR A COMPARISON BETWEEN HORIZONTAL AND VERTICAL DRAINAGE SYSTEMS IN ANISOTROPIC SOILS

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Abstract

Choosing an appropriate drainage system on an agricultural land has always been discussed and analyzed from several points of view. But in the case of anisotropic soils, this problem is more sensitive. In this study, a comparison was made between a horizontal and a vertical drainage system in anisotropic soils. For this purpose, using the DrenVSubIR software, the distance between horizontal and WellDrain vertical pipes was determined, as well as calculus of resistance coefficient at water entry in drain tube, with and without filter, the drainage verifying operation calculus in sub-irrigation and the specific investment calculus and for establishing the optimum technical-economic solution of drainage.

Key words: software, water drainage, underground drainage systems, design, groundwater control

INTRODUCTION

The design of the horizontal and vertical drainage, that is to say the arrangement of the channels or the underground drainage pipes, their depth and the determination of the space between them is done by the relation of Hooghout. This also takes into account the effect of pressure losses at the entrance of the water into the drainage channels with or without filtering materials, a value calculated using the experimentally established coefficients given by the Ernst formula completed by David. This allows checking the conventional reversibility of the drainage in the controlled drainage and in sub-irrigation but, only after calculating the distance between the drainage channels and the values determined when designing the distance between the drainage channels.

The calculation of drainage and subirrigation in the frame of reversible functioning of drainage arrangements implies the application of the general concepts of hydraulic leakage of groundwater towards horizontal agricultural drains. So, for sizing horizontal drainage induced in pipes (the principal element in achieving reversible arrangements of drainage – sub-irrigation) are used relations: Hooghoudt, Ernst and David for permanent functioning regime and verifying mode in impermanent regime. Starting from Ernst and David relation the loss of hydraulic losses have been detailed in closed horizontal drainage with working tubes that

lead to thoroughgoing study of theoretical fundamentals researches on total head pressure loss.

A. Wehry et al in 1980 determined the time-dependent drainage from the root zone of a plant and the drainage coefficient at different levels of irrigation management for an underground drainage project in Jud. Timiș and 10 years later realized and presented the underground drainage on an agricultural land in the Western Plain of Romania cultivated with maize.

David (1983), using a field approach to wetland drainage design, improved Ernst's formula by adding an index to estimated runoff coefficients. Thus, we can use a simple flow resistance model that manages secondary drainage/irrigation systems.

With the help of the water drainage equation, analyzed the evolution of the groundwater level in the field studied both permanently and non-permanently. The results obtained with the derivative equation proved to be in close correlation with those obtained from numerical simulations. Using the finite element method, he calculated the constant heights of the water level in the drained soils and determined the variation of the hydraulic conductivity at depth in the drained lands and the design of the drainage installations. (Youngs, 1975, 1985)

Orlescu (1986) investigated in his studies the hydrogeological aspects of agricultural drainage from Timis County. Molen and Wesseling (1991) presented a solution to replace the tables for the equivalent layer thickness in the formula for determining the distance between Hooghoudt's drainage pipes. Thus, the effect of using continuously submerged drainages that have been resisted due to the modified permanent drainage equations in different soil types determined in the underground drainage has been studied. Comparing the drainage equations on a field in permanent regime with those on an equivalent depth in a non-permanent regime it is found that they give results only when used in design using the optimum radius of drain given by the hydrography analysis for a given depth of soil.

The hydrological study conducted by Polse Terras (2000) determined the use curves of the aquifer of the well from several tests given all heterogeneous environments. Hanson and Ayars (2002) presented strategies for reducing underground drainage in agriculture by improving irrigation. Sabau N.C. et al (2002) discussed the depth of groundwater level in homogeneous drained anisotropic soils.

Hunt (2005) discussed the flow of water extracted from the vertical and oblique wells in the aquifer layers from which water can be extracted. Sabău N.C. et al (2006) modeled an underground drainage surface to determine the salt load in the N-V Plain of Romania.

O'Kelly (2006) compared the anisotropy of soft soils. Sabău et al (2007) make comparative forecasts of analytical models and field

measurements for water drainage by pumping in an un-configured aquifer layer. Bodog et al (2007) presented in the doctoral thesis software for designing an underground drainage system successfully used in several systems in Romania. In this software a few simple elements of analysis are used to predict the height of the groundwater level used in the underground drainage.

Bodog, 2009, presented numerical simulations of the underground drainage in permanent regime, with hydraulic conductivity in vertical decrease. The presented results will be used to estimate the depth of the groundwater level resulting from the vertical variations of the hydraulic conductivity.

Man et al., 2010, estimated the unsaturated hydraulic parameters following the infiltration of water in the anisotropic soil and of the internal drainage experiments on the stand made at Fac. Hydrotechnics of the "Politehnica" University of Timisoara. Subsequently, the team evaluated the efficiency of the prefabricated vertical drains using dynamic testing on the same stand. Halbac, 2010, studied agricultural land drainage as a comprehensive research in his own PhD thesis.

Domuța, Sabău et al., 2010, studied the role and importance of water and irrigation development on agricultural land in NW of Romania, Bihor County for 40 years till 2008. Man et al., 2015, studied in depth the application of drainage and irrigation on agricultural lands demonstrated the effectiveness and social and environmental impact of hydro-improvement projects.

Older drainage models predicted relatively rapid dissipation of stored but undrained water, while it showed degradation throughout the entire pumping test. The results indicated that the water level limitation conditions used in these analytical models did not adequately reproduce the mechanisms that control the behavior of water from atmospheric precipitation and infiltrate the earth's crust.

The present study designs a cost-effective horizontal and vertical underground drainage system that can be applied immediately in the field.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this study we use two softwares DrenVSubIR and WellDrain for horizontal and vertical drainage respectively. The calculations on the distance between the drains are based on Darcy and the groundwater level equations, budget or drainage water retention equations. In addition, the results obtained for the space between the drains were manually verified.

Three different layers of soil with different hydraulic conductivity and permeability were considered: one layer above and two below the drainage

tube placement level. The last two layers had different horizontal and vertical hydraulic conductivity or permeability (anisotropy).

Fig. 1. Graphic of horizontal drainage

Fig. 2. Graphic of vertical drainage

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table below represents the calculation of the distance between drains for different values of hydraulic conductivity. According to table 1, if the hydraulic conductivity is changed, the type of drain and the distance between the drains are changed. The largest changes in the initial conditions ($\Delta s/s = 0$) were related to that hydraulic conductivity above the runoff depth (K_a) which was very low (0.1 meters per day) and below the runoff depth (K_b) was very large (10 meters a day).

In this situation, the quantities of water drained and the distance between the wells remain at the initial ones, which were 572.72%, respectively 169.19%.

However, the vertical drainage systems, due to the not so large changes of the spacing, in the anisotropic soils were suitable for the situation in which the hydraulic conductivity of the soil could change. Therefore, given that the hydraulic conductivity of the soil is unstable and can give significant changes over time, the use of vertical drainage will give maximum efficiency if used.

The interpretation of the results was done according to the graphs in figures 3 and 4. Thus 90% of the groundwater was lost on the first 5 meters according to figure 3 and in figure 4, 5 meters away from the first well; a loss of less than 30% was produced from the amount of water. Also, in the vertical drainage, due to the amount of groundwater lost at the first extraction, the hydraulic conductivity values were less efficient in determining the distance between wells than between drains.

Fig. 3. Horizontal drain action

Table 1

Calculation of distance between drainages for different values of hydraulic conductivity

Time (m/day)	Af (m)	Db (m)	W (m)	Aw (m)	D1 (m)	D2 (m)	Ka (m/day)	Kh1 (m/day)	Kv1 (m/day)	Kh2 (m/day)	Kv2 (m/day)	Dh (m)	Δs/s	Dv (m)	Δs/s
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	2.9	5.0	2.0	1.3	1.5	0.9	1.0	173.05	0.0	67.08	0.0
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	20.0	21.0	2.0	1.3	1.5	0.9	1.0	403.47	132.8	90.76	33.7
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	2.1	21.0	2.0	1.3	1.5	0.9	1.0	335.43	94.4	78.37	15.5
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	2.9	5.0	10.0	1.3	1.5	0.9	1.0	241.33	39.7	92.65	36.4
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	2.9	5.0	0.1	1.3	1.5	0.9	1.0	151.57	123	60.0	10.5
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	2.9	5.0	2.0	10.0	0.1	10.0	0.1	471.53	172.5	160.37	135
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	2.9	5.0	2.0	0.1	10.0	0.1	10.0	125.88	261	51.73	21.4
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	20.0	21.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	10.0	10.0	139.76	180	74.68	10.18
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	2.9	5.0	0.1	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	570.70	230.8	168.17	147.3
0.0011	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	10.0	21.0	0.1	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.5	334.40	100.1	54.69	17.19

Fig. 4. Vertical well action

CONCLUSIONS

The results showed that, in the same situation, the horizontal drainage systems, due to the larger spacing of the drainage channels respectively the underground pipes were more efficient than the vertical drainage systems.

However, vertical drainage systems, due to the small spacing between wells (wells), in different anisotropic soils, have been adequate to the anisotropic conditions, in which the hydraulic conductivity of the soil may change.

The results of the experiment showed that the controlled drainage (sub-irrigation) of a land improvement system significantly reduced both the volume of run-off water and the quantities of salt in the water compared to the unmanaged systems. However, there have been significant increases in soil salinity, which will need to be carefully monitored and managed.

The results obtained with this software are approximately the same as Hooghoudt analytical solution for the distribution of the total water flow in the ideal drainage channels and for calculating the total flow at half the distance between the drainage channels.

Therefore, it was concluded that the proposed software is good for practical situations and could be used in future work with large scale hydrological models. This software was useful for designing an underground drainage system on a soil with three horizons from which the upper one is slightly permeable. The study showed that the location of soil horizons influences the water flow.

In all previous researches, the design of horizontal and vertical drainage systems was performed separately, and these two systems have never been compared in anisotropic soils. In this article, both horizontal and vertical drainage systems are theoretically compared in anisotropic soils.

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FORESTS VEGETATION, FOREST HABITATS OF COMMUNITY INTEREST IN NORTH-WEST ROMANIA, INCLUDED IN THE PROJECT "PRIORITY HABITATS OF FOREST STEPPE AND HILLY PIEDMONTS", POTENTIAL THREATS AND MONITORING OF CONSERVATION STATUS (I)

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to identify and describe the types of natural habitats of community interest in northwestern Romania.

We have proposed to reach five working goals prior to reaching the proposed objective. The working methods we used consist in the acquisition of informative materials, preliminary evaluation of the forests, field research, and a complete evaluation that led to the elucidation of the scientific content of the proposed objectives.

The scientific information obtained regarding the floral composition, the high conservation values, the state of conservation, the potential threats and the management of the forests included in the five natural habitats of community interest in the northwest of Romania are processed and analysed besides the results and discussions thereof.

The phytocenoses of these habitats were studied from the perspective of their belonging to seven rare plant associations, described for the first time. Four conclusions were formulated summarizing the research results and the original contribution of the authors of this work.

Key words: forests, forest habitats, phytocenoses, plant associations.

INTRODUCTION

Habitats of community interest are those habitats that are of major importance for the protection and conservation of nature according to the Directive 92/43/EEC of 21.05.1992 known as the "Habitats Directive" transposed into the Romanian legislation by the Romanian Government by means of the following legal acts: Law no. 462/2001 on the endorsement of the Government Emergency Ordinance no. 236/2000, Government Decision no. 1284/2007, Emergency Ordinance no. 57/2007 on the regime of the protected natural areas, the conservation of the natural habitats, of the flora and the wildlife, and which contains detailed provisions regarding the setting up of the "Natura 2000" Network and the administration of their sites thereof.

The Habitats of Community Interest Directive is based on the document approved by the Habitats Committee in February 1994, which subsequently approved interpretation manuals as follows: EUR 12 version

from April 1995, EUR 15 from October 1999, and the EUR 25 from 14th of March 2002 "Interpretation Manual of European Union habitats" which also included the habitats in Romania. The purpose of this work is to identify and describe the types of natural habitats of community interest in northwestern Romania included in the Project "Priority forest habitat of community interest of forest steppe and hilly foothills, potential threats and monitoring of the conservation status".

In order to reach the proposed objective we set the following five goals:

- (i) Finding natural habitats of Community importance in the European and Romanian version thereof;
- (ii) Identification of the main plant associations and the types of ecosystems that include endangered, vulnerable, rare and endemic species, while those containing endangered species being considered priority habitats;
- (iii) Identification of high conservation value forests (HCVFs) and their geographical distribution in the territory;
- (iv) Assessment of the conservation status and potential threats against habitats subject to study;
- (v) Establishing protection measures and management of habitats containing high conservation value forests.

In order to solve the objectives of this study we reviewed the scientific papers which have been published more recently and contain information on the habitats and sites of community interest included in the "Natura 2000 Ecological Network" of the following authors: Candrea Bozga et al., 2009; Donița et al., 2005; Drăgulescu et al., 2007 ; Gafta, Mountford, 2008 ; Lazăr et al., 2007; Stăncioiu et al., 2008, those containing information on high conservation value forests, Biriș et al., 2002 ; Ioraș, Abrudan, 2007 ; Jennings et al., 2003; Stanciu et al., 2004 ; Stăncioiu, 2008 ; Vlad et al., 2013, and also sources providing information on habitat biodiversity and plants included in the Red lists by Angelstam et al., 2004; Boșcaiu et al., 1994 ; Coldea et al., 2008 ; Danciu et al., 2007 ; Dihoru, Negrean, 2009 ; Oltean et al., 1994; Radu, 2001; Schulze, Mooney,1993.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

We carried out our research in the north-west of Romania, the foothills of Oradea Hills, the Lăzăreni Hills and the Western Plain of Romania. The total area of the region surveyed by us is about 180 km².

In order to achieve the proposed goals, the research was divided into four successive stages of work.

The first stage of work included the acquisition of informative materials (i.e. tree maps, plot descriptions, Red lists for rare plant species, scientific data from published works on natural habitats and high conservation value forests reported in the area, list and maps of protected areas).

The second stage i.e. the preliminary assessment is based on the analysis of the data collected from the information sources, which acts as a "filter", excluding forests with no high conservation values (i.e. forests containing, endangered, vulnerable, relics, endemic species considered nature monuments) and focus on forest areas with potential for high conservation value forests included in natural habitats and sites of community importance.

The third stage refers to field research of selected forests as high conservation value forests included in the natural habitats of community interest, description of habitats, phytocenoses of the respective forests and their conservation status.

The fourth stage i.e. the complete evaluation aims to definitively establish the types of natural habitats of community interest and the categories of high conservation value forests (HCVFs) for each forest area in the surveyed region. We developed a table (see Table 1) that covers the forest habitats of community interest, the associations of rare plants, the types of ecosystem and the categories of high conservation value forests found in the surveyed territory.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents and analyses seven forest habitats of community interest classified in accordance with Directive 92/43/EEC, 12 equivalent forest habitats of community importance in Romania and classified according to Doniță et al. (2005,2006), 13 plant associations, 12 ecosystems, and six categories of high conservation value forests (HCVFs).

9110. *Luzulo-Fagetum* beech forests

In Europe, the *Luzulo-Fagetum* type beech forests grow in central and northern Europe on acid soils being populated with characteristic species such as: *Luzula luzuloides*, *Polytrichum formosum*, *Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Calamagrostis villosa*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*. PALAEARTIC HAB. 41.1 D54 South Carpathian *Festuca drymeja* beech forest.

In Romania, this habitat benefited from the equivalence made according to Doniță et al (2005, 2006) with the type R4110, South-eastern Carpathian beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*) with *Festuca drymeja*, being spread in the Eastern, Southern and Northern Carpathians, in the northwest

of Romania, the Oradea Hills, Crişul Parade Defile at Şuncuiuş, Vadu Crişului in Bihor County (see Table 1).

Ecosystem type: 4136 Medium productive beech, with mull-moder on brown hydrous luvic (podzolic) soils balanced with *Festuca drymeja*.

Plant association: *Festuco drymejae-Fagetum*, according to Morariu et al. 1968.

The phytocenoses of the association sum up a number of 65 cormophytes, of which there are highlighted the characteristic species for the sub-alliance *Symphyto - Fagenion*, the alliance *Symphyto cordati-Fagion*: *Hieracium umbellatum*, *Ruscus aculeatus*, the order *Fagetalia sylvaticae*: *Luzula luzuloides*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Galium odoratum*, *Lathyrus vernus*, *Lathyrus venetus*, *Sanicula europaea*, *Asarum europaeum*, *Stachys silvatica*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*, *Pulmonaria officinalis*, the class: *Quercu-Fagetea*: *Hedera helix*, *Galium schultesii*, *Melica uniflora*, *Anemone nemorosa*, *Athyrium filix-femina*, *Dryopteris filix-mas*, *Carex digitata*, etc.

The tree layer is dominated by *Fagus sylvatica* with 62% overall coverage, along with *Tilia tomentosa*, *Quercus petraea*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Prunus avium*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Quercus cerris*, *Sorbus torminalis*.

The shrub layer with a coverage of less than 1% consists of *Cornus mas*, *Corylus avellana* and *Sambucus nigra*.

High conservation values are met in the case of *Ruscus aculeatus*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*, *Cephalanthera longifolia* and *Platanthera bifolia* classified as HCvFs 1.2, HCvFs 1.3.

Conservation status and potential threats: Conservation of these forests suffers from the lack of a specific Natura 2000 management plan, illegal logging, harvesting of berries and mushrooms, grazing and transit of domestic animals.

9130 *Asperulo-Fagetum* beech forests

This type of habitat consists of beech trees (*Fagus sylvatica*) with many sycamore maple stands (*Acer pseudoplatanus*). It is a typical habitat for the oceanic climate dominating the western, central and northern Europe. These forests are populated by grass species such as *Anemone nemorosa*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Galium odoratum*, and *Melica uniflora*, which form a grass layer that is more populated by species than that of the *Festuco drymejae-Fagetum* association. PALAEARTIC HABITATS 41.1224 Dacian *Dentaria bulbifera* beech forests. In Romania, this type of habitat corresponds to R4118 Dacian beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*) and European hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*) with *Dentaria bulbifera* and which is spread in the outlying regions of the Carpathian Mountains, especially in western Romania at the Oradea Hills, Crişul Repede Defile, Şuncuiuş-Vadu Crişului, Bihor County (see Table 1).

Ecosystem type: 4216 Beech with high and medium hornbeam productive with mull on brown eumezobasic soils, populated with *Asperula odorata* - *Asarum europaeum* - *Stellaria holostea*.

Plant association: *Carpino - Fagetum* Paucă, 1941.

The physiognomy of the association is given by the characteristic species i.e. *Carpinus betulus* with a general coverage of 34% and *Fagus sylvatica* with a general coverage of 33%, and which are codominant species. Alongside the two aforementioned characteristic species the following species are present in the tree layer: *Tilia tomentosa*, *Prunus avium*, *Acer campestre*, *Acer platanoides*, *Quercus petraea*, *Quercus dalechampii*, *Quercus robur*, *Quercus cerris* and *Sorbus torminalis*.

The layer of shrubs with an overall coverage of 4% is poorly represented, and consisting of the following species *Cornus mas*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Corylus avellana*, *Cornus sanguinea* and *Ligustrum vulgare*.

The herbaceous layer with a general coverage of 48% comprises a number of 59 cormophyte species, of which the most frequent are highlighted, and characteristic for the sub-alliance *Lathyro hallersteinii-Carpenion*, the alliance *Symphyto cordati-Fagion*: *Lathyrus vernus*, *Ranunculus auricomus*, *Stellaria holostea*, *Scilla bifolia*, *Festuca drymeja*, the order *Fagetalia sylvaticae*: *Allium ursinum*, *Sanicula europaea*, *Galium odoratum*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Pulmonaria officinalis*, *Carex pilosa*, *Asarum europaeum*, the class *Querco-Fagetea*: *Anemone nemorosa*, *Ranunculus ficaria*, *Viola reichenbachiana*, *Geum urbanum*, *Dentaria bulbifera*, *Carex digitata*, *Melica uniflora*, etc.

High conservation values: this habitat contains high conservation value forests classified as HCVPs1.2 and HCVPs1.3.

Potential threats: lack of a specific "Natura 2000 Management Plan", grazing and transit of domestic animals through the habitat, inadequate management of forests within the habitat.

91HO* Pannonian woods with *Quercus pubescens*

The "Interpretation Manual of European Union Habitats" EUR25 describes this type of habitat as xerophyte oak woods of the periphery and hills of the Pannonian plain dominated by *Quercus pubescens* which is an extremely dry, southern exposed location on shallow, calcareous soils. Because of these extreme site conditions, woods are often fragmentary and low-rowing, sometimes only shrubby.

In general, this habitat is associated with other dry grassland ecosystems with which it intersects and forms mosaic structures.

PALAEARCTIC HABITATS: 41.7373 Intra-Carpathian insular *Quercus virgiliana* woods.

In Romania, this habitat is equivalent to "R4160-Dacian pubescent oak forests (*Quercus pubescens*) with *Lithospermum purpureoeruleum*" spread in the Transylvanian Plateau in the area of Aiud-Mirăslău, Copșa Mică-Petiș, in the west of Romania at Șuncuius –Vadu Crișului, Dealul Șomleu, Băile 1 Mai Oradea, Dobrești Forest District, Lunca Sprie-Valea Toplița, where the typical conditions described above are met (see Table 1).

Ecosystem type: 8771 Venetian sumach (smoke tree) stands (*Cotinus coggygria*), weakly productive with calcic mull, on rendsinic, eubasic, carbonate soils, facing a periodic water deficit, and populated with *Lithospermum purpureoeruleum*.

Plant association: *Corno-Quercetum pubescenti* Jakucs et Zólyomi ex Máthe et Kóvacs 1962.

The physiognomy of the association is given by the two characteristic species *Quercus pubescens* and *Quercus virgiliana* which are in codominance relationship.

The habitat presents itself as a mosaic made of pubescent oak open wood (*Quercus pubescens*) with sinuous trunks, barbed crowns not exceeding 4-6 m in height and portions of closed stands that alternates with steppe mesh dominated by typical grass species (i.e. *Carex humilis*, *Stipa capillata*, *Pulsatilla montana*, ssp. *dacica*, *Iris aphylla*, *Fritillaria orientalis*, *Allium senescens* ssp. *montana*, *Allium flavum*, *Anthericum ramosum*, *Teucrium montanum*, *Dictamnus albus*, *Peucedanum oreoselinum*, *Lithospermum purpureoeruleum*, *Centaurea stoebe* ssp. *australis*, *Jurinea mollis* ssp. *mollis*, *Jurinea glycacantha*, *Festuca rupicola* ssp. *sulcata*, *Koeleria macrantha* ssp. *transsilvanica*, *Phleum montanum*, *Brachypodium pinnatum*, *Veronica spicata*, *Thymus comosus* ssp. *transsilvanicus*, *Sesseli oseum*, *Sesseli peucedanoides*, *Stachys recta*, *Inula conyza*, *Arabis turrata*, *Arabis hirsuta*, *Arabis recta*, *Peucedanum cervaria*, *Laserpitium latifolium*, *Asperula cynanchyca*, *Galium erectum*, *Clinopodium vulgare*, *Vincetoxicum hirundinaria*), see Table 1.

The layer of trees with a reduced consistency i.e. of 20-40% in open wood and of 40-50% in the forest consists of pubescent oak, mainly *Quercus pubescens* and *Quercus virgiliana* mixed with *Quercus cerris*, *Acer campestre*, *Sorbus torminalis*, *Fraxinus excelsior* and *Fraxinus ornus*.

The well-developed shrub layer with an overall coverage of 30-40% consists of the following species: *Viburnum lantana*, *Cornus mas*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Spiraea media*, *Prunus tenella*, *Prunus fruticosa*, *Rhamnus catharticus*, *Rhamnus saxatilis* ssp. *tinctoria*, *Cotoneaster integerrima* and the undershrub species *Cytisus nigricans*, *Cytisus hirsutus* ssp. *leucotrichus*.

Pubescent oak stands have a very high biodiversity, the phytocenoses of this association bringing together 113 mostly relict, Mediterranean, xerophilic-xeromezophilic plant species.

Conservation value: very high (see Table 1). The habitat contains high conservation value forests classified as HCVFs 1.1, HCVFs 4.1, and HCVFs 4.2, containing rare, endangered, relicts, species considered as monuments of nature, such as: *Pulsatilla montana* ssp. *dacica*, *Fritillaria orientalis*, *Ruscus aculeatus*, *Iris aphylla*, *Dianthus carthusianorum* ssp. *puberulus*, *Silena heufelii*, *Saxifraga paniculata*, *Jurinea mollis* ssp. *dacica*, *Centaurea stoebe* ssp. *australis*, *Allium flavum*, *Allium senescens* ssp. *montanum*, *Anthericum ramosum*, *Koeleria macrantha* ssp. *transsilvanica*, *Helictotrichon decorum*, *Cleistogene serotina*, *Stipa capillata*, *Prunus tenella*, *Prunus fruticosa*, *Rhamnus saxatilis* ssp. *tinctoria*.

Conservation status and potential threats: conservation of these forests is guaranteed by their classification in protected areas and the functional Group 1 - Forest vegetation with special protection functions.

Among the potential threat categories, we mention the following:

- (i) Repeated regeneration from root shoots affecting the vitality and genetic variability of the pubescent oak population;
- (ii) Changing vegetation conditions can endanger habitat stability, case3 in which pubescent oaks can be competed and eliminated by sessile oak, Turkey oak, European hornbeam and even beech stands;
- (iii) Grazing and transit of domestic animals through habitat;
- (iv) Fire of vegetation on the bordering agricultural lands with a possible spreading also in the pubescent oak habitat;
- (v) The small size of the pubescent oak stands combined with the geographical and reproductive isolation may cause disturbance in the dynamics and evolution of these species;
- (vi) Damage caused by entomofauna (phytophagous insects) phytopathogenic agents (parasitic fungi) that can cause abnormal drying in such trees.

9110*Euro-Siberian forest steppe s with *Quercus* sp.

In Europe, this habitat comprises forest steppe s enclosing different xero-thermophile oaks species that develop on the loess sublayer in a continental climate with high temperature variations; such species are widespread in the plains of south-eastern Europe. The dominant species in the tree layer are the following: *Quercus robur*, *Quercus cerris*, *Quercus pubescens*, *Quercus petraea* accompanied by *Acer tataricum*, *Acer campestre*, *Sorbus torminalis*, *Tilia tomentosa*, *Prunus mahaleb*, *Ulmus minor*, *Cornus mas*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Euonymus verrosa*. The herbaceous species specific in these forests are as follows: *Carex michelii*, *Dactylis polygama*, *Lithospermum purpureocoeruleum*, *Lathyrus niger*,

Geum urbanum, *Tanacetum corymbosum*, *Polygonatum latifolium* and *Pulmonaria mollis*. Currently, these forests present a very fragmented habitat (especially in Central Europe) or are degraded following the invasion of *Robinia pseudacacia* species.

In the northwest of Romania this habitat is represented by two types of forest ecosystems: R4138 Dacian sessile oak forests (*Quercus petraea*) and pedunculate (common) oak (*Quercus robur*) with *Acer tataricum*. PALAEARCTIC HABITAT 417A225, Sarmatic *Acer tataricum-Quercus robur-Quercus petraea* forest steppe s.

The Ecosystem R4148 Pannonicplain forrest of Psamophile pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*) with *Convallaria majalis*, PALAEARCTIC HABITAT 417A213 Pannonic sand steppe oak woods (see Table 1).

The Ecosystem R4138 Dacian sessile oak forests (*Quercus petraea*) and pedunculated oak (*Quercus robur*) with *Acer tataricum* is widespread in the northwest of Romania along the Oradea Hills, the Lăzăreni Hills and the Transylvanian Plateau.

Ecosystem type: 6716 medium productive sessile – common oak stands with mull on typical luvic and brown soils, mesobasic, hydricly balanced with *Asperula odorata-Asarum europaeum-Stellaria holostea* (see Table 1).

Plant association: *Aceri tatarico-Quercetum roboris* Zólyomi 1957, facies with *Ruscus aculeatus*.

The tree layer with a general coverage of 78% is dominated by the characteristic species *Quercus robur*, *Quercus petraea* and *Quercus dalechampii*, which are in different co-dominance relationships and which instil a characteristic appearance of this association.

To the afore-mentioned one add the following species: *Carpinus betulus*, *Prunus avium*, *Quercus polycarpa*, *Acer tataricum*, *Malus sylvestris*, *Pyrus pyraeaster*, *Staphylea pinnata*. The well-developed shrub layer consists of *Crataegus monogyna*, *Cornus mas*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Sambucus nigra* and *Prunus spinosa*.

The well-developed herbaceous and undershrub layers encompassing a floristic composition of about 70 species are made up of plants characteristic of the alliance *Genisto germanicae-Quercion*, the order *Quercetalia roboris*: *Lathyrus niger*, *Genista tinctoria* ssp. *ovata*, *Solidago virgaurea*, *Rumex acetosella*, the order *Fagetalia*: *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Asarum europaeum*, *Sanicula europaea*, *Carex sylvatica*, *Mercurialis perennis*, *Lathyrus venetus*, *Alliaria petiolata*, *Lathyrus vernus*, *Corydalis cava*, the class *Quercio-Fagetea*: *Pulmonaria officinalis*, *Dentaria bulbifera*, *Anemone nemorosa*, *Melica uniflora*, *Ruscus aculeatus*, *Convallaria majalis*, *Polygonatum latifolium*, *Geum urbanum*, *Galium odoratum*,

Stellaria holostea, *Arum maculatum*, *Pulmonaria mollis*, *Melittis mellisophyllum*.

High conservation values: this habitat contains high conservation value forests classified as HCVPs 1.1 and HCVPs 1.2, and populated by rare, endangered, relict species treated as monuments of nature: *Ruscus aculeatus* which has a boosting growth forming a facies, *Convallaria majalis*, *Polygonatum latifolium*, *Arum maculatum*.

Conservation status and potential threats:

The conservation of these forests is affected by the lack of a specific Natura 2000 Management Plan, illegal logging on large areas, reduced size of pedunculate oak surfaces combined with reproductive isolation, damage caused by entomofauna and phytopathogenic agents.

The Ecosystem R4148 psamophile Pannonic forests of pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*) with *Convallaria majalis*.

This type of ecosystem is spread on the sands of the northwest of Romania at Săcuieni, Șimian, Valea lui Mihai in Bihor County, Carei in Satu Mare County, and across very small areas in Oradea Hills.

Plant association: *Polygonato latifolio – Quercetum roboris* (Hargitai 1940) Borhidi 1966 (Syn.: *Convallario-Quercetum roboris* Soó 1957).

The Dacian & Pannonic forests of pedunculate oak stands (*Quercus robur*) with *Polygonatum latifolium* and *Convallaria majalis* develop on a clay and sand sublayer, gleyed gumiferous, eubasic, eutrophic preluvisols facing water deficient during summer time.

The tree layer with a consistency of 0.7-0.8 is dominated by *Quercus robur*, along with *Carpinus betulus*, *Prunus avium*, *Acer campestre*, *Quercus petraea*, *Quercus polycarpa*, *Quercus dalechampii*, *Quercus cerris*, *Tilia cordata*, *Acer platanoides*, *Ulmus minor*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Sorbus torminalis*, *Acer tataricum*, *Populus tremula*, *Malus sylvestris* and *Pyrus pyraster* (Table 1).

Table 1

Forest habitat of community interest in north-western Romania and the categories of high conservation value forests (HCVFs) they contain

No	Habitats			Plant associations	Type of forest ecosystem	High conservation values forest categories	Location
	Habitats codes according to Directive 92/43/EEC	Romanian equivalent code	PALAEARCTIC code				
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	9110. <i>Luzulo-Fagetum</i> beech forest	R4110. Southeast South-east Carpathian beech forests (<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>) with <i>Festuca drymeja</i>	41.1 D54 South Carpathian <i>Festuca drymeja</i> beech forest	<i>Festuco drymejae</i> – <i>Fagetum</i> Morariu et al. 1968	4136	HCVF 1.2, 1.3	Oradea Hills, Măgura Vadu Crișului Hill
2	9130. <i>Asperulo – Fagetum</i> beech forests	R4118. Dacian beech forests (<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>) and European hornbeam (<i>Carpinus betulus</i>) with <i>Dentaria bulbifera</i>	41.1D224 Dacian <i>Dentaria bulbifera</i> beech forests	<i>Carpino-Fagetum</i> Păucă 1941	4216	HCVF 1.2, 1.3	Oradea Hills, Măgura Vadu Crișului Hill, Lăzăreni Hills
3	91 HO* Pannonian woods with <i>Quercus pubescens</i>	R4160. Dacian pubescent oak forests – open wood (<i>Quercus pubescens</i>) with <i>Lithospermum purpurocoeruleum</i>	41.7373 Intra-Carpathian insular <i>Quercus virgiliana</i> forests	<i>Corno – Quercetum pubescentis</i> Jakucs et Máthé et Kóvacs 1962	8771	Șeica Mică, Mirăslău Transylvanian Plateau, Crișul Repede Defile, Băile 1 Mai, HCVF 1.1, 3., 4.1, 4.2.	Măgura – Șuncuiuș Hill, Valea Toplița-Lunca Sprie Valley, Șomleu Hill – Băile 1 Mai Oradea
4	9110* Euro-Siberian forest steppes with <i>Quercus sp.</i>	R.4138. Dacian Sessile oak forests (<i>Quercus petraea</i>) and pubescent oak (<i>Quercus robur</i>) with <i>Acer tataricum</i> . R. 4418. Psamophile Pannonic forests of pedunculate oak (<i>Quercus robur</i>) cu <i>Convallaria majalis</i>	41.7A225 Sarmatian <i>Acer tataricum</i> – <i>Quercus robur</i> – <i>Quercus petraea</i> forest steppe 41.7A213 Pannonic sand steppe oak woods	<i>Aceri tatarico – Quercetum roboris</i> Zólyomi 1957 facies with <i>Ruscus aculeatus</i> , <i>Polygonato latifolio-Quercetum roboris</i> (Hargitai 1940, Borhidi 1966) (Syn.: <i>Convallario-Quercetum roboris</i> Soó 1957)	6716 -	HCVF 1.1, 1.2 HCVF 1.2, 1.3, 4.2	Oradea Hills Lăzăreni Hills, Nort-west Romania sandy areas, Șimian, Valea lui Mihai, Oradea Hills

No	Habitats			Plant associations	Type of forest ecosystem	High conservation values forest categories	Location
	Habitats codes according to Directive 92/43/EEC	Romanian equivalent code	PALAEARCTIC code				
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
5	91LO. Illyrian oak - hornbeam forest (<i>Erythronio - Carpinion</i>)	R4127. Mixed Dacian sessile oak (<i>Quercus petraea</i>), beech (<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>) and silve limetree (<i>Tilia tomentosa</i>) with <i>Erythronium dens-canis</i> .	41.2A12. Illyrian neutrocline sessile oak hornbeam forests.	<i>Tilio tomentosae - Quercetum dalechampii</i> , Sârbu 1979, <i>ruscetosum aculeati</i> subas. nova. <i>Fago-Quercetum petraeae</i> R.Tüxen 1955	5416 4516	HCVF 1.1, 1.2, 3, 4.2	Oradea Hills Vadu Crişului
		R4132. Pannonic and Balkan sessile oak (<i>Quercus petraea</i>), Turkey oak (<i>Quercus cerris</i>) and beech (<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>) forests with <i>Melittis melissophyllum</i> .	41.7696. Pre-Carpathian <i>Quercus cerris - Quercus petraea</i> forests.	<i>Quercetum petraeae - ceris</i> (Soó 1957)1969 - <i>ruscetosumaculeati</i> Morar - Burescu 2012	7724	HCVF 1.1, 1.2, 3, 4.2	Oradea Hills Măgura – Şuncuiuş Hill, Lăzăreni Hills
6	91 Mo. Pannonian - Balkan Turkey oak - sessile oak forest	R4140. Dacian – Balkan Sessile oak (<i>Quercus petraea</i>) forests, Turkey oak (<i>Quercus cerris</i>) and silver lime tree (<i>Tilia tomentosa</i>) forests with <i>Lychnis coronaria</i> .	41.7696. Pre-Carpathian <i>Quercus cerris - Quercus petraea</i> s.l. forests.	<i>Tilio argenteae - Quercetum petraeae cerris</i> Soó 1967 - <i>ruscetosum aculeati</i> Morar - Burescu 2012	7114	HCVF 1.1	Oradea Hills, Şomleu Hill, Băile 1 Mai Oradea
		R. 4152. Dacian Turkey oak (<i>Quercus cerris</i>) and European hornbeam (<i>Carpinus betulus</i>) forests with <i>Digitalis grandiflora</i>	41.769. Getic sub-continental thermophilous oak forests	<i>Carpino-Quercetum cerris</i> Klika 1938 (Boşcaiu et al. 1969)	7214	HCVF 1.2, 1.3, 4.2	Oradea Hills, Lăzăreni Hills, Măgura Şuncuiuş Hill
		R.4154. Pannonic and Balkan of Hungarian oak (<i>Quercus</i>	41.76814. Danubian - Balkan <i>Festuca heterophylla</i> forests	<i>Quercetum frainetto - dalechampii</i> (Bărcă 1984) Chifu et al. 2006	7535	HCVF 1.2, 1.3	Oradea Hills, Lăzăreni Hills

No	Habitats			Plant associations	Type of forest ecosystem	High conservation values forest categories	Location
	Habitats codes according to Directive 92/43/EEC	Romanian equivalent code	PALAEARCTIC code				
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
		<i>frainetto</i>)					
7	91YO. Dacian oak – hornbeam forests	R 4124. Dacian sessile oak (<i>Quercus petraea</i>), beech (<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>) and European hornbeam (<i>Carpinus betulus</i>) forests with <i>Lathyrus hallersteinii</i>	41.2C12. Dacian <i>Lathyrus hallersteinii</i> oak – hornbeam forests	<i>Carpino – Quercetum petraeae</i> Borza 1941	5216	HCVF 1.2, 1.3	Oradea Hills
		R 4143. Dacian pedunculated oak (<i>Quercus robur</i>) forests with <i>Melampyrum bihariense</i>	41.2C11. Dacian <i>Melampyrum bihariense</i> oak – hornbeam forest	<i>Quercu robori – Carpinetum</i> Borza 1937	6216	HCVF 1.2, 1.3	Oradea Hills, Lăzăreni Hills

The relatively well-developed shrub layer with a coverage of 15-20% consists of *Crataegus monogyna*, *Cornus mas*, *Cornus sanguinea*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Euonymus europaeus*, *Acer tataricum*, *Staphylea pinnata*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Corylus avellana*, *Prunus spinosa* (see Table 1). The herbaceous layer with a coverage of 75% is dominated by *Polygonatum latifolium* and *Convallaria majalis* species which are characteristic for this association, together with the recognition species for the alliance *Aceri tatarico-Quercion*: *Campanula rapunculus*, *Carex brevicollis*, *Pulmonaria mollis*, *Arum maculatum*, the order *Fraxino orni-Cotinetalia*: *Rubus caesius*, *Circaea lutetiana*, *Potentilla micrantha*, *Tamus communis*, *Primula veris*, the class *Quercetea pubescenti-petraeae*: *Melittis melissophyllum*, *Polygonatum odoratum*, *Ruscus aculeatus*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*, *Lathyrus niger*, *Lychnis coronaria*, *Platanthera chloranta*, *Vincetoxicum hirundinaria*, *Viola hirta* (see Table 1).

High conservation values:

This ecosystem contains high conservation values forests classified as HCvFs 1.2, HCvFs 1.3 and HCvFs 4.2 where the following rare and endangered species, considered as monuments of nature found, their shelter: *Ruscus aculeatus*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*, *Platanthera chloranta*, *Convallaria majalis*.

Conservation status and potential threats:

Current habitat conservation status is favourable but some threats may also arise due to the lack of special legal provisions for the management of forests included in the Natura 2000 habitat ecological network, the lack of a specific Management Plan, improperly performed wood extraction, grazing and passage of animals through the habitat, afforestation with species other than dominant species of this habitat, allochthonous species such as *Quercus rubra*, *Prunus serotina*, *Robinia pseudacacia* and *Pinus nigra*, the wind erosion of the psamosoils caused by the clear cutting and the lowering of the groundwater level caused by prolonged droughts, etc.

91LO Illyrian oak – hornbeam forest (*Erythronio - Carpion*)

Illyric oak forests (*Quercus robur*), European hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*) with *Erythronium dens-canis* are less known and researched in Romania being spread on small areas, western peri-Carpathian hills at Vadu Crişului, Oradea Hills and sporadically in Transylvania Plateau.

This type of habitat corresponds to R4127 mixed Dacian forests of sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*), European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) and (European) silver lime (*Tilia tomentosa*) with *Erythronium dens-canis*. PALAEARCTIC HABITAT 41. 2A12. Illyrian neutrocline sessile oak hornbeam forests (see Table 1).

Ecosystem type: 4516 medium productive mixed beech and sessile oak (silver lime, European hornbeam) with mull, on typical brown soils, luvic, eutrophic, hydrically balanced soils with *Asperula odorata* - *Asarum europaeum* - *Stellaria holostea*.

Plant associations: *Tilio tomentosae* – *Quercetum dalechampii* Sârbu 1979 – *ruscetosum petraeae* subas. nova, *Fago-Quercetum petraeae* Tüxen 1955. Cenosis occupies both flat lands as well as those with gently to medium slopes with sunny exposures on clay-sandy soils on the surface, clay and weakly humiferous pre-luvosoils and luvosoils present in the deep layers. The tree layer is dominated by the two Mediterranean and Balkan species i.e. *Quercus dalechampii* (Delechampsessile oak) with a coverage of 43.84% and *Tilia tomentosa* (silver lime) with a coverage of 30.96%.

Alongside these are scattered *Carpinus betulus* (European hornbeam), *Quercus petraea* (sessile oak), *Acer campestre* (field maple), *Prunus avium* (European sweet cherry), *Quercus robur* (pedunculate oak), *Tilia cordata* (small-leaved lime tree), *Fagus sylvatica* (European beech), *Acer platanoides* (Norway maple), *Fraxinus excelsior* (European ash), *Ulmus minor* (smooth-leaved elm), see Table 1.

The well-individualized shrub layer with 18% coverage consists of *Crataegus monogyna*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Cornus mas*, *Staphylea pinnata*, *Acer tataricum* and *Sambucus nigra* (see Table 1).

The herbaceous layer with 80% coverage comprises 60 cormophyte species subordinated to the sub-alpine alliance *Aro orientalis* - *Carpinenion*, the alliance *Symphyto cordati-Fagion*: *Symphyto cordati-Fagion*: *Ruscus aculeatus*, *Stellaria holostea*, *Dactylis polygama*, *Corydalis cava*, *Festuca drymeja*, *Arum maculatum*, ordinului *Fagetalia sylvaticae*: *Allium ursinum*, *Carex digitata*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Veronica hederifolia*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Mercurialis perennis*, *Symphytum tuberosum*, *Galium odoratum*, *Scrophularia nodosa*, *Carex sylvatica*, *Corydalis solida*, *Sanicula europaea*, clasei *Querco-Fagetea*: *Geum urbanum*, *Dentaria bulbifera*, *Anemone nemorosa*, *Melica uniflora*, *Melica nutans*, *Pulmonaria officinalis*, *Astragalus glycyphyllos*, *Polygonatum latifolium*, *Lathyrus niger* etc.

We have separated the population of sub-shrub, semi-evergreen plants of *Ruscus aculeatus* (butcher's-broom) with a general coverage of 18.3% spread on the plateaus and the ridges of the hills crossed by roads, Dalmatian thermophile turkey oak, silver lime tree, European hornbeam with different species i.e. *Arum maculatum*, *Melica nutans*, *Carex digitata*, *Isopyrum thalictroides* into the sub-association *Ruscetosum aculeate*, Sub-association nova Holotypus hoc loco, see Table 1, position no 3 that we subordinate to the basic association.

A small number of species are transgressive in the class *Quercetea pubescenti-petraeae*: *Sorbus torminalis*, *Quercus cerris*, *Polygonatum odoratum*, *Melittis melissophyllum*, *Vincetoxicum hirundinaria*.

High conservation values:

The ecosystem contains high conservation value forests classified as HCVFs 1.1, HCVFs 1.2, HCVFs 3 and HCVFs 4.2, which contain rare, endemic, relict species considered as monuments of nature such as butcher's-broom (*Ruscus aculeatus*), Lily of the Valley (*Convallaria maj*), Turk's cap lily (*Lilium martagon*), *Silene nutans* ssp. *dubia*, *Smyrniium perfoliatum*, *Potentilla micrantha* and *Sanicula europaea*.

Conservation status and potential threats:

The conservation of these forests can be affected by the lack of a specific Natura 2000 Management Plan, improper management, improper wood extraction, inappropriate use of roads that affect the habitat, harvesting of plants in particular of *Ruscus aculeatus* for commercialization purposes, changes in vegetation conditions (deforestation, clear cutting) affecting for the mild and warm climate conditions specific for the species *Ruscus aculeatus* habitat, grazing, and transit of domestic animals through the habitat in question.

CONCLUSIONS

We identified five types of forest habitats of community interest in European version and eight types of equivalent habitats on the Romanian territory.

The phytocenoses of forests included in these habitats are subordinated to seven rare plant associations, described for the first time for that territory.

The species inventory was made establishing the floristic composition and the classification of the species by cenotaxa corresponding to each plant association.

The habitats surveyed contain high conservation value forests classified as HCVF 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 3, and 4.2.

Notes: The classification by forest ecosystems types (4136, 4216, 4516, 5216, 5416, 6216, 6716, 7114, 7214, 7535, 7724, 8771) was done according to the Romanian typological system elaborated by Doniță, Chiriță, Stănescu (coord.) 1990, Doniță, Gafta (1992):

High conservation value forests (HCVFs) were grouped into six distinct categories after processing, with comments to the practical guidelines by Stanciu, Mihul, Dinicu (2005), Vlad, Bucur, Turtică (2013) as follows :

HCVF 1.1. Forest areas from natural areas protected with role in the conservation of natural habitats and biodiversity, including forests of scientific interest in subgroups 1.5.a, 1.5.d, 1.5.f (taken after the Ministry of Forestry 1986, with comments and notes from Stăncioiu et al. 2008)

HCVF 1.2. Forests that contain rare, threatened or endangered species;

HCVF 1.3. Forests formed in natural habitats for endemic flora species and relict species;

HCVF 3. Forests that contain rare, threatened, endangered ecosystems or species included in rare plant associations;

HCVF 4.1. Forests with special role for the protection of drinking water sources and the prevention of floods with excessive alluvium transport;

HCVF 4.2. Forests with an important role in controlling soil erosion.

The classification of habitats by types was made according to European Directive 92/43/EEC which is legal framework for the implementation of the Natura 2000 Ecological Network, (9110, 9130, 91HO, 91IO *, 91LO, 91MO, 91YO) and according to the Romanian typology (R4110, R4118, R4160, R4138, R4148, R4127, R4132, R4140, R4152, R4154, R4124, R4143) adapted to the specific conditions of our country by Doniță et al. (2005).

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SOLUTION FOR NORMALIZATION PRODUCTION FUND, DETERMINATION AND ANALYSIS EVOLUTION IN DIFFERENT ASSUMPTIONS

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Abstract

A real production fund reaches the state of normality, respectively a normal production fund when the growth in volume of the forest becomes equal to the volume of wood mass exploited, both being reported at the same time period.

The normalization of the production funds by the method of the age classes is a desire which any responsible forest administration tends because it ensures the continuity in time of the crops and a better management of the forests in time without too much effort in certain periods of time. concerns the application of the respective care works and treatments. The paper presents the calculation algorithm respectively the solutions that are the basis of the normalization of the production funds.

The paper contains analyzes regarding the normalization of the production funds in different working hypotheses, with the presentation of the solutions that can be the basis of their normalization. An important thing regarding normalization is the time period required for normalization.

Key words: production fund, normalization, age classes, normalization period

INTRODUCTION

The forest as a forest ecosystem performs simultaneously several functions of both ecological and economic nature, the fulfillment of these functions in their fullness being conditioned by the achievement of the normal structure of the production fund (Leahu, 2000). Meeting the needs of wood under the current conditions is becoming more difficult due to the strong deviation from the structure of certain production funds on the one hand and the increased demand for wood on the other, which makes it difficult to find a sustainable balance between demand and offer. On the other hand, small steps have been taken regarding the replacement of wood still widely used as fuel which makes the pressure on the wood extracted from the forests of Romania extremely high (Dorog, 2007).

A real production fund that is actually the the mirror of the forest management reaches the state of normality, respectively normal production fund when the growth in volume of the forest reaches equal to the volume of wood mass exploited, both being reported at the same time period (Kevin, 1998). This fact is quite difficult to achieve in most situations due to the

deviations accentuated from the normal structure and on the other are the economic interests that reduce the possibilities of reaching the desired management goal (Giurgiu 1972).

The normalization of the production funds by the method of the age classes is a desire to which any responsible forestry administration tends because by this it ensures the continuity in time of the harvests and the fulfillment in good conditions of the ecoprotective functions (Giurgiu, 2004). Normalization is achieved in time by consistent application of care and treatments, the starting point being the forest structure at a given time, the calculation algorithm for normalization, deviations from the normal structure and the manifestation of disturbing factors during the normalization period (Leahu 1998, 2001). The latter may affect the structure of the fund to a greater or lesser extent and may increase the time period for normalization (Dorog, 2008).

The production funds have extremely different structures due to the seasonal conditions and the of forestry actions undertaken over time. The forestry interventions undertaken within the arboretums throughout their existence have as their primary role the approximation of the arboretum structure to the structures that best satisfy the assigned functions (Andrici A., et al., 2017).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Regarding the determination of the normal production fund, there are several cases of determination, from the simplest when the forest is made up of pure stands of the same productivity, the forest is made up of pure stands of different productivity, to the most complex case when the forest it consists of mixed stands with different productivity. The paper analyzes the most complex situation that we also find in nature.

The determination of the normal production fund was carried out by the method of the age classes, which implies the distribution of the surface of each species by production classes and age classes. After this distribution, the total areas will be determined by age classes, total production for each species and production class. The determination of normal production is made by dividing the total production into six because the production funds are generally structured into six age classes. The actual production by age classes will continue to be determined.

The production funds have different structures in relation to the natural conditions, vegetation and the household measures taken. The measures proposed by the forestry arrangements, both care works and treatments, have as main role besides the forestry nature the management of

the production fund towards the structure of maximum functional efficiency, ie the normal structure (Piticar et al., 2015).

Different structures of the production funds were analyzed with their evolution over certain periods of time in relation to the size of the differences between the real and the normal structure. Following the analyzes carried out, two situations are distinguished, one in which there is a surplus of exploitable stands in the 6th class of age and the other in which there is a deficit of exploitable wood mass.

To determine the normal surface by age classes was applied the relation:

$$S_n = \frac{P_n}{P_r} \times S_r \text{ in which:}$$

- S_n represents the normal surface of an age class;
- P_n represents normal production;
- P_r represents real production by age classes;
- S_r represents the real surface by age classes.

The determination of the normal distribution by age classes for the mixed stands is performed through the following steps:

- the distribution of each species by production classes and age classes;
- the total area for each age class is calculated;
- the total area for each production class and species is calculated;
- it is taken from the production tables by species and by the production class the normal production;
- the total production for each species and production class is calculated;
- the normal production by age classes is determined;
- the actual production by age classes is determined;
- the normal area for each age class is determined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following the analysis of the situations presented above, the following discussions can be made. For production funds with exploitable timber surplus the normalization is generally easier due to the fact that only a part of the exploitable trees will be switched to cutting, while the others will complete up to the normalization of the V age class while the exploited areas will be they will join the 1st grade age group.

For production funds with exploitable timber shortage the normalization of the production fund is extremely difficult due to the fact that it involves a long period of time that can reach or even exceed the value

of the production cycle. Most often during these extremely large periods, unforeseen situations may arise which again modify the structure of the age classes with implications of course on the normalization of the production fund.

Table 1

Variance, standard deviation, Anova and Bartlett's Test in different calculation hypotheses

Calculation variant	Variance		Standard deviation		Bartlett's Test	Anova
	Initial	After applying the normalization algorithm	Initial	After applying the normalization algorithm		
I	1037.5	21.11	32.2	4.59	111.577 *** (P<=0.001) 0.000667	0.3008 N.S. (P>0.05) 0.9814
II	1037.5	21.06	32.2	4.61	111.588 *** (P<=0.001) 0.000663	0.3034 N.S. (P>0.05) 0.9804
III	1037.5	20.08	32.2	4.72	111.572 *** (P<=0.001) 0.000659	0.3038 N.S. (P>0.05) 0.9817
IV	1037.5	19.89	32.2	4.67	111.568 *** (P<=0.001) 0.000657	0.3035 N.S. (P>0.05) 0.9812
V	1037.5	20.03	32.2	4.69	111.574 *** (P<=0.001) 0.000665	0.3036 N.S. (P>0.05) 0.9817
VI	1037.5	19.97	32.2	4.68	111.564 *** (P<=0.001) 0.000655	0.3034 N.S. (P>0.05) 0.9809
VII	1037.5	20.05	32.2	4.63	111.566 *** (P<=0.001) 0.000654	0.3035 N.S. (P>0.05) 0.9806
VIII	1037.5	21.11	32.2	4.59	111.577 *** (P<=0.001) 0.000667	0.3008 N.S. (P>0.05) 0.9814

Regarding the surfaces by age classes that exist before normalization and those that are determined in the normalization process, some details can

be made based on the table below obtained from the statistical processing of type Anova. What is interesting to note from the table below is that the standard deviation has values over 32 for the surfaces by age classes before normalization and values close to 5 after applying the normalization algorithm. By applying the Bartlett test to verify the homogeneity of the variant in several hypotheses, it was concluded that the results are insignificant (see table 1).

CONCLUSIONS

In the case of production funds where there is a surplus of timber that can be exploited, the normalization operation is relatively easy as some of the stands will be switched to exploitation and the rest will start balancing in the five age class. What is important to mention is the fact that the possibility of main products plays an active role in the normalization of the production funds.

In the case of production funds where there is a deficit of exploitable timber, the normalization operation is performed relatively harder as in the previous case because it involves a relatively long period of time that can reach or exceed the value of the production cycle, which does not guarantee that this period will not produce disturbing phenomena that again affect the structure of the production fund.

Applying the Anova statistic in the five calculation hypotheses by comparing the statistical ranges of data formed by the surfaces by age classes the differences are insignificant in all cases, which suggests that the production fund normalization can be achieved in a relatively long time. The insignificant differences between the data ranges that represent the distribution of the surfaces by age classes from the initial moment and after the application of the calculation algorithm show that in a period of 10 years the differences regarding the normalization of the effects are extremely small.

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MODAL ANALYSIS STUDY OF RECTANGULAR WOOD PLATES

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Abstract

This paper aims is to determine the modal responses and the total responses of an isotropic rectangular flat plates. As is known, for the rectangular flat plates, the modal analysis method is applied to an infinite number of degrees of freedom. The plate studied in this paper was considered subjected to the action of a disturbing system of forces variables uniformly distributed in time. In applying the modal analysis damping was considered neglected. From analysis carried out were determined the modal and total responses in displacements and the modal loadings.

Key words: plate, vibration, shape, functions, method.

INTRODUCTION

In the paper the problem of dynamic calculation of flat plate was formulated into the theory limits of engineering plates assumptions (Kirchhoff model). The material of the studied plate studied is considered to be isotropic. Considering the principle of D'Alembert the differential equation of plate motion have the form (Catarig, 2001, Fetea, 2010, Martian, 1997, Missir, 1999):

$$\nabla^4 w(x, y, t) = \frac{\rho h}{D} \ddot{w}(x, y, t) = \frac{p(x, y, t)}{D}$$

(1)

Where:

∇^4 - double Laplacian operator [1]

$$\nabla^4 = \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4}{\partial y^4}$$

(2)

ρ - material density.

h - constant thickness of the plate.

$$D = \frac{Eh^3}{12(1-\mu^2)}$$

(3)

D - bending strength stiffness of the plate.

μ - Poisson ratio.

$p(x, y, t) = p(x, y) \cdot f(t)$ - distributed harmonic disturbing force.

$w(x, y, t)$ - transversal displacement rectangular plate point

The objective in this work is to determine the plate numerical values of modal and total displacements, the own pulsations and dynamic multiplier functions using an analytical method. It was also followed the solving of algebraic equations system resulting from imposing the boundary conditions. The analysis was performed for the vibration modes ij (1,1) and (1,3). The objective in this work is to determine the numerical values of their movements and pulsation functions multiplier dynamic modal and total plate using an analytical method.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The plate considered in the paper have two opposite sides clamped and the others two simply supported. The plate considered is loaded with a system of distributed harmonic forces on the surface having the intensity P_0 and pulsation Ω . Material of rectangular plate is homogeneous and isotropic considered. Median plate surface dimensions considered are:

$a = 4[m]$ - plate length.

$b = 2[m]$ - plate width.

$h = 0,2[m]$ - the plate thickness.

The plate considered have the following boundary conditions:

- for $x = 0, x = 4$, the boundary is simply supported.
- for $y = 0, y = 2$, the boundary is clamped.

Fig. 1. Plate simply supported and clamped

For determining the own pulsations and vibrations shapes functions it starts from the free vibrations differential equation (Catarig, 2001), (Ciofoaia, 1986), (Goia, 2000):

$$\nabla^4 w(x, y, t) = \frac{\rho h}{D} \ddot{w}(x, y, t) = 0$$

(4)

Differential equations of free vibration has the following general solutions form (Catarig, 2001), (Ciofoaia, 1986), (Goia, 2000):

$$w(x, y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \Phi_{ij}(x, y) \cdot \eta_{ij}(t)$$

(5)

Where:

$\Phi_{ij}(x, y)$ - the shapes functions plate.; $\eta_{ij}(t)$ - the time functions.

After replacing the general solution into the differentials equations of free vibration will be obtained the normal modes differential equation of vibration. The form is (Fetea, 2010), (Ivan, 1997), (Posea, 1991):

$$\nabla^4 \Phi_{ij}(x, y) - \frac{\rho h \omega_{ij}^2}{D} = 0$$

(6)

ω_{ij} - the rectangular plate own pulsations

For the normal modes differential equation of vibrations was adopted the following solutions

$$\Phi_{ij}(x, y) = Y_j(y) \cdot \sin \frac{i\pi x}{a}$$

(7)

Differential equation of free vibration becomes [1], [4], [5]

$$Y_j^4 - 2 \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2} Y_j^2 + \left(\frac{i^4 \pi^4}{a^4} - \frac{\rho h \omega^2}{D} \right) Y_j = 0$$

(8)

Differential Equation characteristic equation (8) has the form:

$$r^4 - 2 \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2} r^2 + \left(\frac{i^4 \pi^4}{a^4} - \frac{\rho h \omega^2}{D} \right) r = 0$$

(9)

The roots of this equation are the following

$$r_{1,2} = \pm \sqrt{\omega \sqrt{\frac{\rho h \omega^2}{D} + \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2}}}$$

(10)

$$r_{3,4} = \pm i \sqrt{\omega \sqrt{\frac{\rho h \omega^2}{D} - \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2}}}$$

(11)

For the determined solutions are adopted the following notations:

$$\alpha_i = \sqrt{\omega \sqrt{\frac{\rho h \omega^2}{D} + \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2}}}$$

(12)

$$\beta_i = \sqrt{\omega \sqrt{\frac{\rho h \omega^2}{D} - \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2}}}$$

(13)

General solution of differential equations can be written as (Rosca, 2002), (Sandu, 2003):

$$Y_i = A_i ch \alpha_i y + B_i sh \alpha_i y + C_i \cos \beta_i y + D_i \sin \beta_i y$$

Where:

A_i, B_i, C_i, D_i - unknown integration constants to be determined.

The unknown integration constants of plate equation are determined by imposing the boundary conditions. For clamped sides of plate $y = 0$, $y = b$ with the length $b=2$, the boundary conditions are written as [5], [6]:

$$y = 0 \rightarrow \begin{cases} Y(0) = 0 \\ Y'(0) = 0 \end{cases} \quad y = b \rightarrow \begin{cases} Y(b) = 0 \\ Y'(b) = 0 \end{cases}$$

Following the calculation algorithm adopted are obtained 4 homogeneous algebraic equations having 4 unknowns. The unknowns of these equations are the constants of integration. The system of equations has the form:

In order to have non-zero solution the homogeneous system of equations must have the determinant equal to zero. Corresponding to the own pulsations of their normal modes of vibration considered are determined the parameters pulsations values λ_1, λ_3 .

The expression for calculus of the own pulsations has the form (Gheorghiu, 1998), (Munteanu, 1998):

$$\omega_{ij} = \frac{\lambda_{ij}}{a^2} \sqrt{\frac{D}{\rho h}}$$

(14)

Dynamic multiplication functions for normal modes of vibration considered was determined using the relationship (Catargiu, 2001), [9], [10]

$$\Psi_i = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\Omega^2}{\omega_i^2}}$$

(15)

Using the expressions presented is determined the modal and total displacements points plate for normal modes of vibration considered.. Tthe modal responses into displacement was determined using relations

$$w_i = \Phi_1 \Psi_i$$

(16)

The total plate response in displacements was determined using equation (16) by applying the principle of superposition:

$$w(x, y, t) = w_1(x, y, t) + w_3(x, y, t) \quad (17)$$

For the studied case of dynamic plate is also determined the total and modal value loading. The relation are:

$$p_i = P_0 \cdot \Psi_i \quad (18).$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At conducting numerical study analysis were considered the following initial data of the problem presented.

Are taken into consideration the following values

1. Young's modulus $E = 2,1 \cdot 10^6 \left[\frac{daN}{cm^2} \right]$

2. Poisson ratio $\mu = 0,2$

3. Distributed uniformly disturbing force module on the surface plate $P_0 = 10 \left[\frac{KN}{m^2} \right]$

4. The disturbing force pulsation $\Omega = 10 \left[\frac{rad}{sec} \right]$

5. The value bending strength stiffness plate value determined is

$$D = 2,181 \cdot 10^4 \left[\frac{daN}{cm^2} \right]$$

Substituting into (14), are determined their own pulsations values. The pulsations parameters determined are [1]

$$\lambda_1 = 54,8$$

$$\lambda_3 = 69,3$$

$$\omega_1 = \frac{\lambda_1}{a^2} \sqrt{\frac{D}{\rho h}} = \frac{54,8}{a^2} \sqrt{\frac{D}{\rho h}} = 24,65 \left[\frac{rad}{sec} \right]; \omega_3 = \frac{\lambda_3}{a^2} \sqrt{\frac{D}{\rho h}} =$$

$$\frac{69,3}{a^2} \sqrt{\frac{D}{\rho h}} = 31,17 \left[\frac{rad}{sec} \right]$$

The coefficients of the general solution for normal vibration modes considered are:

$$\alpha_1 = \sqrt{\omega_1 \sqrt{\frac{\rho h}{D} + \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2}}} = 2,01 \quad \beta_1 = \sqrt{\omega_1 \sqrt{\frac{\rho h}{D} - \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2}}} = 1,675$$

$$\alpha_3 = \sqrt{\omega_3 \sqrt{\frac{\rho h}{D} + \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2}}} = 3,141 \quad \beta_i = \sqrt{\omega_i \sqrt{\frac{\rho h \omega^2}{D} - \frac{i^2 \pi^2}{a^2}}} = -1,1$$

The unknown integration constants determined by the homogeneous algebraic system for the mode number 1 of vibration are:

$$\begin{cases} A_1 + C_1 = 0 \\ \alpha_1 B_1 + \beta_1 D_1 = 0 \\ A_1 ch \alpha_1 b + B_1 sh \alpha_1 b + C_1 \cos \beta_1 b + D_1 \sin \beta_1 b = 0 \\ \alpha_1 A_1 sh \alpha_1 b + \alpha_1 B_1 ch \alpha_1 b - \beta_1 C_1 \sin \beta_1 b + \beta_1 D_1 \cos \beta_1 b = 0 \end{cases}$$

By performing the algebraic calculations by the system equations are obtained the values

$$ch \alpha_1 = \frac{e^{\alpha_1} + e^{-\alpha_1}}{2} = 27,308 \quad sh \alpha_1 = \frac{e^{\alpha_1} - e^{-\alpha_1}}{2} = 27,29$$

$$\cos \beta_1 = 0,998; \sin \beta_1 = 0,058$$

By following the calculations are obtained the constants of integration values.

$$A_1 = 1; B_1 = -0,966; C_1 = -1; D_1 = 1,16$$

Following the same algorithm for vibration mode $i = 3$, by solving the homogenous algebraic equations system integration constants obtained are:

$$\begin{aligned} A_3 &= 1; \\ B_3 &= 1,01 \\ C_3 &= -1 \\ D_3 &= 2,88 \end{aligned}$$

For the shape vibration functions corresponding to the normal modes of vibrations considered, we obtained the following values

$$\Phi_1 = 1,507, \Phi_3 = 2,26$$

The corresponding dynamic multiplier dynamic functions (Catargiu, 2001), (Fetea, 2010) for the studied vibration modes are:

$$\Psi_1 = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\Omega^2}{\omega_1^2}} = 1,19$$

Using expressions of the modal responses in displacement are obtained the following numerical values

- for mode number 1 $w_1 = \Phi_1 \Psi_1 = 1,804[cm]$ and for mode number 3 $w_3 = \Phi_3 \Psi_3 = 2,5[cm]$

The total plate response was determined by applying the principle of superposition (Catargiu, 2001), (Fetea, 2010)

- for mode vibration number 1 and 3

$$w(x, y, t) = w_1(x, y, t) + w_3(x, y, t) = 4,304[cm]$$

The determined corresponding loads for the normal modes of vibration are:

$$p_1 = P_0 \cdot \Psi_1 = 11,9 \left[\frac{KN}{m^2} \right]; p_3 = P_0 \cdot \Psi_3 = 11,1 \left[\frac{KN}{m^2} \right]$$

Watching the results obtained by the modal analysis (displacements and loadings) for the rectangular plate, can be expressed some conclusions with theoretical and practical aspects. Maximum bending moments for static and dynamic loadings are presented for rectangular sections (table 1)

As a conclusion from the results obtained in paper:

- for mode 1 of vibration the dynamic multiplication factor is about 7% higher than for mode 3 of vibration;

- the modal responses into displacement values are inversely proportional for mode 1 and are about 27% lower than for mode 3;

- regarding the modal loads is ascertained that for vibration mode number 1, the loading mode is about 7% higher than for the vibration mode 3

CONCLUSIONS

The paper is intended to be an example of analytical calculation of rectangular plates type structures using the modal analysis method. The modal analysis method allows the determination of total and the modal responses into displacement and the modal and total responses into sectional efforts. The work follows and shows detailed calculation algorithm through

a detailed presentation of the work stages. Thus, following the steps algorithm presented in the paper, can be determined the dynamic modal responses depending on the product of the static bending moment and static shear forces static with the dynamic multiplication factor determined (Catariu, 2001), (Fetea, 2010), (Missir, 2002)

The expressions are

$$M_{ij}(x, y, t) = M_{ij}(x, y)\Psi_{ij}$$

$$T_{ij}(x, y, t) = T_{ij}(x, y)\Psi_{ij}$$

$$M(x, y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n M_{ij}(x, y)\Psi_{ij}$$

The application of modal analysis using analytical or numerical methods for structure strength is a very important mathematical engineering calculus regarding the dynamical study of different types of structures.

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CONTRIBUTIONS REGARDING THE PROCESSING OF A CRAFT OBJECT WITH THE CNC STEPCRAFT – 2D.840

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Abstract

This paper presents the processing of an craft object with the CNC STEPCRAFT-2 / D.840 where the ASPIRE program was used to design the object. The ease with which it can be processed, the fine details that can be carved in wood of different types and the beauty that this raw material has, has helped people to perfect their processing techniques.

Key words: ASPIRE, CNC STEPCRAFT-2/D.840

INTRODUCTION

Wooden handicraft products are sought for their uniqueness. Wood was one of the main raw materials that the people tried to model with increasing skill.

Due to human evolution, the objects that his hand created were perfected with the progress made in the electronic industry. This is possible with the help of computers and high-performance machines where special craft objects can be processed. In order to deserve the sacrifice of wood cutting, people process wood to perfection by creating real objects of art.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The craft object was processed on the CNC STEPCRAFT-2 / D 840 which is a machine for processing wood, plastic or non-ferrous metals.

The machine has three axes which are offset by 90°. Each axis is equipped with a stepper motor and a reference switch.

The STEPCRAFT milling motor is a quiet technical product of high stability and precision. It is a cylindrical motor with direct transmission system in a compact housing. It ensures high concentricity at the tip and a long life of the cutting tool. The engine used for processing the handmade object is brushless and starts directly from the program. It stops automatically at the end of the program and goes up to 20000 speeds.

Fig. 1. CNC STEPCRAFT-2/D (<https://www.stepcraft.ro/stepcraft-2-d-840-ready-to-run-system.aspx>)

The Aspire software was used to achieve the handicraft object processed with the CNC STEPCRAFT-2 / D. Aspire has been developed to allow the production of decorative and artistic dimensional carved parts. As well as drawing and modeling tools, it includes both 2D and 3D machining, along with 3D V-Carving / 3D Engraving to allow a huge variety of jobs to be produced as quickly and easily as possible.

Aspire includes drawing and editing tools that allow designs to be created and modified. Once the 2D design is ready, 3D components can be created from 2D drawings.

Aspire's interface makes the drawing and modeling tools easily accessible.

Aspire provides simple interface buttons to toggle screen layout to assist the shift in focus from design to toolpathing. (<https://l.facebook.com/l.php?u=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com%2Fs%2Fsearch%3Fq%3Daspire%2520tutorials%2520pdf>)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to achieve the handicraft object, the Aspire program was opened in which, as shown in figure 2, the working field is created and the material thickness is selected. Then select point 0 to highlight the start of the program and the "ok" button to work in the field created.

Fig. 2. Creating the work field

Figure 3 shows the model of the craft object. It will have to take into account the operations that are inside and those will be cut first. The thickness of the physical piece must be 8 mm.

Fig. 3. Model of the craft object

In figure 4 shows the saving of both profiles in a single program. Here, too, we can observe the post selection of the processor that recognizes the CNC machine, namely STEPCRAFT 840.

Fig. 4. Saving profiles

In the CNC machine directly loading the nc code of the profiles where the material and the milling used are highlighted.

(Profile 1)
 (File created: Thursday October 24 2019 - 02:20 PM)
 (for Mach2/3 from Vectric)
 (Material Size)
 (X= 80.000, Y= 330.000, Z= 8.000)
 ()
 (Toolpaths used in this file:)
 (Profile 1)
 (Tools used in this file:)
 (1 = End Mill 2 MM)
 N100G00G21G17G90G40G49G80
 N110G71G91.1
 N120T1M06
 N130 (End Mill 2 MM)
 N140G00G43Z20.000H1
 N150S19600M03
 N160(Toolpath:- Profile 1)
 N170()
 N180G94
 N190X0.000Y0.000F1000.0
 N200G00X5.399Y-14.325Z10.000
 N210G00Z2.000
 N220G1Z-0.125F1000.0
 N230G1X11.799Y-14.325


```
.....  
.....  
N15660G1X44.607Y-23.183  
N15670G1X44.437Y-23.444  
N15680G1X44.232Y-23.590  
N15690G1X44.092Y-23.621  
N15700G00Z10.000  
N15710G00Z20.000  
N15720G00X0.000Y0.000  
N15730M09  
N15740M30  
%
```

Figure 5 shows the profiles made at CNC - STEPCRAFT 840.

Fig. 5. Profiles made at CNC

In continuation for making the craft object the characters are mounted in outside the glass.

Fig. 6. Mounting the craft object

For the object to be inserted into the glass, a spring clip is used, a bent and sharp electrode and a thin piece of wood to fit into the mouth of the glass. This must be long enough that the characters can be pressed.

Fig. 7. Tools

The last operation is to place the characters that are put in the glass from its bottom to the lid archeving the final craft object.

Fig. 8. The final craft object

CONCLUSIONS

By using the current programs used in high performance CNC, you can make special craft objects, true works of art.

With the help of the Aspire software used to make this craft object, the design time was considerably reduced.

At the same time, a craft object was made with high accuracy and a flawless finishing surface.

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SAXICOLOUS VEGETATION FROM THE VÂRTOP MASSIF - THE MOUNTAINS OF BIHOR. PHYTOCENOSIS OF THE ASPLENIETUM VIRIDAE. AS. NOVA. ASSOCIATION

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Abstract

The *Asplenietum viridae* association gathers the phytocenoses of the subalpine saxicolous vegetation of the Biharia Massif, Bihor county. The relief on which the phytocenoses of the association develops is one consisting of massive rockland, located on the northern slopes, with limestone rocks, at altitudes ranging between 1140-1160 m. In the surveyed territory, the phytocenoses of the association are located on some small areas (1-4 m²), on the shady rockland, with strips and cracks on the Vârtop Massif and the Seaca Valley. The specific and dominant species are *Asplenium viridae* and *Ctenidium moluscum*. In addition to the two aforementioned we encounter in the floristic structure different elements of the association *Cistopteridion* (*Asplenium scolopendrium*, *Cystopteris fragilis*), of the order *Tortullo-Cybarietalia* (*Geranium robertianum*, *Polypodium asgara*) and class *Asplenieta trichomanis* (*Doronicum columnae*, *Moehringia muscosa*, *Veronica urticifolia*), bringing together a small number of taxa (see Table 1). The floristic index of the association summates 13 species of which hemicryptophytes (75%), followed by geophytes (16.6%) and therophytes (8.33%), circumpolar (33.33%), followed by cosmopolitan species (25%). With regard to ecological indices moisture (M), temperature (T) and soil chemical reaction (R), mesophilic (66.66%), micro-mesothermal (58.33%) and acid-neutrophilic species (41.66%) are dominant. The cariologic analysis highlights diploid species (50%), which forms the genetic reserve for evolution purposes.

Key words: saxicolous vegetation, phytocenosis, floristic elements, bioforms, karyotype, ecological indices

INTRODUCTION

The saxicolous vegetation dominated by *Asplenium viridae* and *Ctenidium moluscum* grows on massive, steep slope (60° - 90°), calcareous rockland, located on the northern slopes, at an altitude ranging between 1140 m and 1160 m in the Bihor Mountains. At lower altitudes this vegetation decreases in terms of consistency or even disappears.

Research on the saxicolous vegetation was carried out in the basin of the Arieș River Valley by Ursu, 2013, on the *Asplenietum septentrionali - adianti - nigri* coenosis from which *Asplenium viridae* is missing, and by Togor, 2016, on the Padiș Plateau rockland, which describes the *Asplenio*

trichomani- Poëtum nemoralis association; the species *Asplenium viridae* is also missing from this coenosis.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The surveyed material consists of the subalpine rockland populated with the species *Asplenium viridae* and *Ctenidium moluscum* from the Biharia Massif, Bihor county, located especially at the Vârtop Massif and Băița Plai village. A total of five surveys (phytocenological relevés) were carried out on the most representative phytocenoses. In the Association table (see Table 1 below) all the species we found are listed and classified according to the corresponding cenotaxonomic units (sub-alliance, alliance, order, class) by constancy (K), while observing the criteria of the works of Borza et Boșcaiu, 1965, the requirements of the eco-floristic systems developed by Tüxen, 1955, Braun-Blanquet, 1964, and based on the information provided in the most recent papers of Coldea et al., 1997 and Sanda et al., 2008, with an assessment of abundance and dominance (AD) of each species according to the Braun-Blanquet and Pavillard scale, 1928. Phytocenosis of rock vegetation consisting of *Asplenium viridae* and *Ctenidium moluscum* was analyzed, and characterized ecologically, phytocenologically and cytogenetically based on the Association table and histograms with regard to the distribution of bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices and genetic categories.

Classification and description of the associations were made on the basis of the floristic criterion, with the help of characteristic, dominant and differential species. The name of the association is given in accordance with the provisions established by the International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature developed by Weber et al. (2000)

The ecological and phytocenological characterization of the species within the surveyed area was done according to Sanda et al., 2003, Ciocârlan, 2009, and Sârbu et al., 2013.

The information on the level of ecological indices, bioforms, floristic elements, number of chromosomes, are presented according to the synthesis works developed by Ellenberg, 1979, Pop, 1977, 1982, Sanda et al., 1983, 2003, 2008, Cristea et al., 2004, Ciocârlan (2009), Burescu and Toma, 2005, and Doiță et al., 2005

We analysed the phytocenoses in terms of categories of ecoforms, moisture (M), temperature (T) and chemical reaction of the soil (R) according to the works of Sanda et al., 1983, 2003, who adapted the ecological index values for the plants in Central Europe classified on a scale ranging from 1 to 9 according to Ellenberg, 1979, to the specific pedoclimatic conditions of Romania using, this time, a scale ranging

between 1 and 6. Cytogenetic analysis of the species by karyotype was done according to the works of Sanda et al., (2003).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is about a casmophytic plants association that grows in the cracks and on the belts of shady limestone rockland, covered by a thin layer of loose soil.

The dominant, specific species of the association i.e. *Asplenium viridae* (ADm=19%) and the bryophyte *Ctenidium moluscum* (ADm = 51%) have an overall coverage range of 70%.

The floristic inventory of the association *Asplenietum viridae* adds up to 13 species. Nine species belong to the basic coenotaxa of the association, of which two species are enclosed into the *Cistopteridion alliance* (*Cistopteris fragilis*, *Asplenium scolopendrium*), two species are included in the order *Tortullo-Cybarietalia* (*Geranium robertianum*, *Polypodium vulgare*), three species are part of the *Asplenieta- Trichomanis* class (*Doronicum columnae*, *Moehringia muscosa*, *Veronica urticifolia*). Four species belong to the *Querco - Fagetea* transgressive class (*Dryopteris filix - mas*, *Mycelis muralis*, *Oxalis acetosella*, *Polystihum aculeatum*), which are species that are characteristic for the vegetation of that area' forests.

The holotype of the association is the survey no 1 (see Table 1).

Fig. 1. The bioforms spectrum of the *Asplenietum viridae* association
Caption: H = Hemicryptophytes, G = Geophytes, Th = Therophytes

The bioforms of the *Asplenietum viridae* association (See Chart no 1 above) are dominated by hemicryptophytes (75%), followed by geophytes (16.6%), and to a smaller extent by the therophytes (8.33%).

Table 1

Asplenietum viridae *As. nova*.

Bioform	Floristic elem.	M	T	R	K	Survey no	1	2	3	4	5	K	ADm
						Altitude (m)	1160	1154	1152	1140	1145		
						Exposition	N	N	N	N	N		
						Slope (°)	70	90	80	60	70		
						Vegetation coverage (%)	80	80	80	70	80		
						Surveyed area (m²)	4	4	1	1	2		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
H	Cp	4	2	4	D	<i>As. Asplenium viridae</i>	2	3	2	1	2	V	19.0
						<i>As. Ctenidium moluscum</i>	4	4	4	1	4	V	51.0
						Cistopteridion							
G	Cp	3.5	3	5	D	<i>Asplenium scolopendrium</i>	+	+	+	1	+	IV	0.6
H	Cosm	3.5	0	0	P	<i>Cistopteris fragilis</i>	.	+	.	.	.	I	0.01
						Tortullo- Cybarietalia							
Th-TH	Cosm	3.5	3	3	D	<i>Geranium robertianum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.05
G	Cp	3.5	3	4	P	<i>Polypodium vulgare</i>	1	I	1.0
						Asplenietea- Trichomanis							
H	Alp-Carp-B	3.5	2	3.5	CN	<i>Doronicum columnae</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II	0.2
H	Ec	4	2	4	P	<i>Moehringia muscosa</i>	+	I	0.1
H	Ec	3	2.5	4	D	<i>Veronica urticifolia</i>	+	I	0.1
						Querco- Fagetea							
H	Cosm	4	3	0	P	<i>Dryopteris filix- mas</i>	+	.	.	.	+	II	0.2
H	E	3	3	3	D	<i>Mycelis muralis</i>	+	I	0.1
H	Cp	4	3	3	D	<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	.	.	+	.	.	I	0.1
H	E	3.5	3.5	3.5	P	<i>Polystichum aculeatum</i>	+	I	0.1

Place and date of surveys: 1-3 Vârtoș Massif; 4-5 Seaca Valley - Băița Plai village, 16.09.2018.

Fig. 2. Floristic elements spectrum of the *Asplenietum viridae* association
 Caption: Cp = Circumpolar, Cosm = Cosmopolitan, Ec = Central European, E = European, Alp-Carp-B = Alpine - Carpathian - Balkan

With respect to the geographical area and the current distribution of species (see Chart no 2 above) in the case of phytocenoses of the *Asplenietum viridae* association, circumpolar species (33.33%) are dominant, followed by cosmopolitan ones (25%), and the European and Central European species each with an equal share of 16.16%. The Alpine - Carpathian - Balkan species are present in small share (i.e. 8.33%).

Fig. 3. Diagram of ecological indices for the *Asplenietum viridae* association

The analysis of ecoforms (see Chart no 3 above) shows that mesophilic species (66.66%) are dominant in relation to soil moisture, followed by mesohygrophilic species (33.33%). Regarding the temperature factor, the micro-mesothermal species (58.33%) are dominant, followed by

microthermal ones (33.33%) and eurithermal species (8.33%). By the soil chemical reaction, the acid-neutrophilic species (41.66%) are dominant, followed by weak acid-neutrophilic (33.33%), euryionic (16.66%) and neutrophilic species (8.33%).

Fig. 4. *Asplenietum viridae*

Caption: D = Diploid, P = Polyploid, DP = Diplo-Polyploid, UK = Unknown karyotype

The karyological spectrum of the *Asplenietum viridae* association shows that diploid species (50%) are dominant and form the genetic reserve to secure the evolution thereof, followed by polyploid species (41.66%), which provides adaptation to habitat conditions and by unknown karyotype species (8.33%).

Phytocenoses of saxicolous vegetation populated with *Asplenium viridae* have not been surveyed and analyzed phytocenologically so far. It turns out that no comparisons can be made with other research works of foreign or domestic authors.

Therefore we present for the first time the floristic, ecological, phytocenological description and analysis of a coenosis dominated by *Asplenium viridae* that we subordinated to the association *Asplenietum viridae* as. nova. Holotypus hoc loco: see Table no 1.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The phytocenoses of the *Asplenietum viridae* association go through the adverse season of vegetation, i.e. the cold season, as hemicryptophytes (75%), followed by the geophytes (16.6%) and therophytes (8.33%), thus benefiting from better adaptation possibilities to the temperate-continent region climate.

2. As regards the geographical area of the association *Asplenietum viridae*, the circumpolar plant species (33.33%) are dominant, followed by the cosmopolitan ones (25%).
3. As far as the ecological factors are concerned, in terms of soil moisture the mesophiles (66.66%) are dominant, the micro-mesotherms are dominant (58.33%) in terms of temperature, and the acidic-neutrophils are dominant (41.66%) with regard the chemical reaction of the soil.
4. The genetic structure by karyotype of the association phytocenoses is dominated by the diploid (50%) followed by the polyploid species (41.66%).
5. The described saxicolous coenosis is of scientific importance and is described for the first time.

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STUDY ON THE PASTORAL VALUE OF *AGROSTIS CAPILLARIS* GRASSLAND ON TĂȘAD HILLS (BIHOR COUNTY)

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Abstract

This paper is a study of the pastoral value of Agrostis capillaris grassland in the area of Tășad Hills, Bihor County. The study was carried out in order to optimize the use of grassland, to determine the correct biomass production and load with animals.

The determination of the pastoral value of grassland in the area of Tășad Hills is important in the context of rural development, the preservation of biodiversity, the improvement of soil fertility and the provision of quality feed for animals.

The study of the pastoral value of the Agrostis capillaris grasslands was carried out between 2018 and 2019, with a number of 28 relevées being carried out. The pastoral value was determined individually for all the relevées, and finally an average pastoral value of the studied grassland was also determined.

The determination of the pastoral value of grassland at national level is useful in the context of carrying out pastoral planning, which are useful in the context of the increase in eligible grassland areas and the economic activities of livestock farming.

Key words: pastoral value, grasslands, optimization, qualitative index, species.

INTRODUCTION

Grassland is an essential element of sustainable farming systems that meet the demands of healthy and high-quality food.

In addition to the decisive role of providing animal feed, grassland has an important function in rural development and the environment, reflected by the preservation of biodiversity, improvement of soil fertility, nitrogen symbionts, hydrologic balance, flood and landslides prevention, atmospheric carbon storage, landscape quality and important cultural heritage.

Livestock systems based on the exploitation of grazing land are now facing growing food needs, as the production of feed produced on these areas keeps pace with the growing demands of meat, milk and climate change.

Recent publications on the study of grassland quality in Romania were carried out by Durău, Moisuc, 2006; Durău et al., 2008; Marușca, 1978, 2005, 2008, 2013; Moisuc et al. 2001; Pășcuț, 2017, 2018; Păcurar, Rotar, 2014.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the determination of the pastoral value of the studied grassland, floristic methods of appreciation have been used. The assessment of the participation of the component species and the floristic composition was made in combination with the phytosociological method and the pratological method. The phytosociological method makes use of an appreciation of the abundance and dominance (AD) of species on relevées of 100 m² at key representative points and is marked on a 6-step scale, namely: 5 (coverage average of 87.5%), 4 (coverage average of 62.5%), 3 (coverage average of 37.5%), 2 (coverage average of 17.5%), 1 (coverage average of 5%), + (coverage average of 0.5%), (Ivan, Doniță, 1975; Cristea et al., 2004). The pratological method consists in assessing the percentage participation of botanical components in biomass by economic groups: *Poaceae*, *Fabaceae*, other families, harmful-toxic species, wood species, and is the one used more widely in the study carried out.

The relevées were chosen in the characteristic fragments of the meadows depending on the nature and complexity of their horizontal and vertical structure.

To describe the vegetation as accurately as possible data were recorded on the habitat conditions under which this grassland is developed, namely: altitude, GPS coordinates, exposition, slope tilt, vegetation cover (%). Quantitative participation of each species was also recorded by setting the dominance and percentage (Table 1).

For the determination of the pastoral value the following formula was used as indicated by certain specialists, (Marușca et al., 2014):

$$V.P. = \sum PC(\%) \times IC / 5$$

where: V.P. – pastoral value indicator (0-100);

P.C. – participation in the grassy area (%),

I.C. – forage quality index.

The values of the feed quality index (IC) have been taken over from the work of Rotar et al. (2009) și Marușca et al. (2012, 2014).

After the relevées had been carried out on the field and the percentage share of each species's participation in the floristic composition had been determined, the feed quality index was passed, with values from 0 (without fodder value) to 5 (with excellent fodder value). After determining the pastoral value indicator, grasslands can be appreciated as follows: 0-5 (degraded grassland), 5-15 (very weak), 15-25 (weak), 25-50 (medium), 50-75 (good), 75-100 (very good) (Marușca et al., 2014).

The scientific name of the species identified on the ground was adopted in accordance with the expert work developed by Ciocârlan (2009) and Sârbu et al., 2013.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The grassland of *Agrostis capillaris* occupy the largest surface in the Tășad Hills area. This grassland is found on lands with different expositions, with slope of 6.87-20.57%, at altitudes between 200 m and 440 m. The vegetation of this grassland is mainly occupied by grass species (58-97%), there also being some woody species, especially shrubs (3-42%). The floristic composition of this grassland is rich in species (161 species) (Table 1). The grassy vegetation is largely composed of *Poaceae* species (69.11%, 25 species), where the dominant is *Agrostis capillaris* (54.29%), other species being presentes well such as *Lolium perenne* (3.68%), *Festuca rubra* (2.46%), *Dichanthium ischaemum* (2.32%), *Holcus lanatus* (1.11%), *Festuca pratensis* (0.89%), *Cynosurus cristatus* (0.79%), *Festuca valesiaca* (0.75%), *Festuca rupicola* (0.64%), *Cynodon dactylon* (0.5%), *Poa pratensis* (0.5), *Anthoxanthum odoratum* (0.5%). There are also *Fabaceae* species (5.39%, 13 species), of which the most common are *Trifolium repens* (2.14%), *Lotus corniculatus* (1.61%), *Trifolium campestre* (0,53%), *Trifolium pratense* (0,5%). The numerical weight is held by the species from other families of herbaceous plants (88 species), these having an overall coverage of 8.11%, the following species being highlighted *Thymus glabrescens* (1.68%), *Juncus effusus* (1.14%), *Hieracium pilosella* (1%), *Daucus carota* (0.75%), *Leontodon hispidus* (0.57%). Toxic and harmful species have a weight of 17.4% (18 species), of which we can highlight *Euphorbia cyparissias* (9.21%), *Pteridium aquilinum* (5.82%), *Eryngium campestre* (1.61%) (Table 1).

The woody vegetation has a significant share in some grassland, occupying 16.8% (17 species) in the studied relevées. From the shrubs the following stand out *Rubus sulcatus* (7.29%), *Prunus spinosa* (2.04), *Crataegus monogyna* (1.21%), *Rosa canina* (1%). In some relevées, the occurrence of invasive youth from tree species was found, these are: *Betula pendula* (2.25%), *Populus tremula* (1.29%), *Robinia pseudacacia* (1.25%) (Table 1).

Agrostis capillaris is a valuable grass forage, with a high degree of consumability, with a qualitative index of 3. In general, the pastoral value of this grassland is medium and good, reaching a production of 10-15 t/ha green mass and having a grazing capacity of 1-1.2 large cattle unit/ha, for pastures with good pastoral value and a production of 5-7.5 t/ha green mass and a grazing capacity of 0.5-0.8 large cattle unit/ha for grasslands with medium pastoral value.

Table 1

The pastoral value of *Agrostis capillaris* grasslands from Tășad Hills

No. relevées	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	%PC	IC	PC x IC	
GPS coordonates	Altitude (m)	405	395	400	370	360	320	350	440	245	380	350	350	225	202	200	290	290	315	295	300	300	300	385	230	285	320	315	340			
	Lat. N	46.34418	46.94038	46.93820	46.93701	46.93677	46.94056	46.94053	46.92276	46.97466	46.96839	46.96750	46.96845	46.99686	47.00202	47.01858	46.97999	46.98500	46.99171	46.97878	46.97393	46.96982	46.96143	46.95340	46.97146	46.97866	46.98726	46.98905	46.95923			
	Long. E	22.19380	22.18880	22.19130	22.19492	22.20059	22.20238	22.19864	22.20655	22.17095	22.14998	22.15769	22.16218	22.11307	22.11249	22.12520	22.11971	22.22277	22.24014	22.24999	22.24730	22.24478	22.22995	22.24911	22.18631	22.18811	22.19092	22.20579	22.20909			
Exposition	S	SV	S,SE	N	N	E,SE	S,SE	SV	S,SV	N	NE	NE	N,V,E	-	-	V	S,SV	S,SE	V,SV	V	NE	SV	N,NV	S,SE	S	SE	NV,V	N,NV				
Slope (degree) (%)	15.81	8.77	13.08	15.59	12.34	20.48	17.81	16.44	15.47	17.62	18.51	14.95	11.29	7.97	6.87	10.49	10.46	19.14	17.81	17.21	12.5	15.14	13.46	11.97	8.25	14.47	20.57	13.28				
Herbaceous layer coverage (%)	65	72	58	84	58	84	75	78	90	85	80	96	60	75	93	85	93	92	92	92	95	67	88	91	95	95	97	95				
Shrubby layer (%)	35	28	42	16	42	16	25	22	10	15	20	4	40	25	7	15	7	8	8	8	5	33	12	9	5	5	3	6				
Area (m ²)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100				
<i>0</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	
Poaceae (%)	(62)	(60)	(60)	(78)	(55)	(74)	(65)	(61)	(58)	(75)	(81)	(77)	(70)	(67)	(75)	(72)	(70)	(70)	(63)	(74)	(65)	(79)	(70)	(75)	(69)	(70)	(65)	(65)	69.11			
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	50	50	50	60	50	60	50	50	55	55	60	60	55	50	60	65	50	50	60	50	60	50	60	55	50	50	55	60	50	54.29	3	162.87
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	3	3	+	10	+	5	5	5	+	8	15	5	+	+	5	+	3	2	5	3	3	1	5	2	5	+	7	3	3.68	5	18.4	
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	3	6	+	3	5	3	3	5	+	5	3	3	3	+	2	2	+	+	+	2	5	10	1	+	+	+	5	2.46	3	7.38		
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	2	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	2	1	3	2	+	1	+	+	+	5	3	2	1	+	+	+	+	+	2	0.89	5	4.45	
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	+	+	+	1	+	1	+	+	1	1	+	1	3	+	2	+	+	+	+	2	3	2	2	+	1	+	+	2	0.79	3	2.37	
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	1	5	10	+	5	+	+	+	+	1	+	1	5	+	1	+	+	1.11	2	2.22	
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	1	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	2	2	1	+	3	+	+	+	+	1	1	2	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.5	4	2		
<i>Festuca valesiaca</i>	2	+	10	+	+	1	2	+	1	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	2	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	2	0.75	2	1.5	
<i>Festuca rupicola</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	5	5	+	+	+	+	+	+	3	+	5	+	0.64	2	1.28		
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	3	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.11	5	0.55		
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	+	+	+	1	+	2	+	1	1	+	+	1	2	+	1	+	+	+	+	1	+	1	1	1	+	1	+	1	0.5	1	0.5	
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	2	1	+	+	+	+	+	10	+	+	+	0.5	1	0.5		
<i>Festuca arundinacea</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	3	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.11	3	0.33		
<i>Agropyron repens</i>	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.07	2	0.14		
<i>Dichanthium ischaemum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	5	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	10	10	2	+	+	+	20	+	15	3	+	2.32	0	0			
<i>Calamagrostis epigejos</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	3	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.21	0	0		
<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	1	1	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.14	0	0		
<i>Deschampsia caespitosa</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.04	0	0		
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	5	0	0	
<i>Arrhenatherum elatius</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	4	0	0	
<i>Briza media</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	0	0	
<i>Brachypodium pinnatum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	0	0	
<i>Setaria pumila</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0	0	0	
<i>Vulpia myuros</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0	0	0	
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0	0	0	

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31					
Fabaceae (%)	(5)	(4)	(3)	(4)	(4)	(3)	(5)	(3)	(5)	(6)	(6)	(6)	(7)	(7)	(8)	(6)	(8)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(6)	(2)	(8)	(6)	(7)	(4)	(6)	(7)	5.39							
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	3	1	3	2	2	2	5	3	3	1	+	2	3	2	1	4	1	5	+	4	2	2.14	5	10.7					
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	+	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	1.61	4	6.44					
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	+	+	•	+	1	+	•	+	+	1	1	1	1	+	2	1	+	1	•	1	1	+	2	+	•	•	•	1	0.5	5	2.5					
<i>Trifolium campestre</i>	2	1	1	•	+	1	1	+	2	1	•	1	1	•	+	+	2	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	0.53	2	1.06					
<i>Trifolium hybridum</i>	+	+	+	1	+	+	1	+	+	1	+	+	+	1	•	•	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	+	•	•	•	1	0.18	4	0.72					
<i>Trifolium arvense</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	•	•	1	+	•	+	+	•	+	•	+	•	•	+	+	+	+	+	0.04	2	0.08					
<i>Dorycnium pentaphyllum</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	1	+	•	•	+	+	+	+	3	1	+	+	•	+	+	3	•	2	•	+	0.35	0	0					
<i>Ononis spinosa</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0	0			
<i>Medicago lupulina</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	4	0		
<i>Lathyrus pratensis</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	-	4	0
<i>Coronilla varia</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	-	2	0
<i>Trifolium medium</i>	+	+	+	•	+	•	•	+	+	+	+	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	-	2	0
<i>Genista tinctoria</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	-	0	0
Other families (%)	(6)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(6)	(8)	(10)	(8)	(12)	(9)	(8)	(12)	(8)	(16)	(9)	(10)	(5)	(4)	(9)	(5)	(6)	(6)	(12)	(7)	(9)	(6)	(6)	(9)	8.11							
<i>Daucus carota</i>	+	+	+	1	+	+	•	+	+	•	•	1	3	2	3	3	+	+	•	+	•	+	+	4	3	+	+	1	0.75	2	1.5					
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	+	+	+	•	+	1	+	1	+	1	+	1	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	1	+	1	1	0.32	2	0.64					
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	+	+	1	+	1	+	+	+	1	+	1	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	•	1	+	+	0.29	2	0.58				
<i>Leontodon hispidus</i>	•	•	•	2	+	2	1	1	•	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	+	+	•	2	+	2	+	1	1	1	3	0.57	1	0.57					
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	+	+	•	•	+	2	+	+	1	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	•	•	+	+	+	0.11	1	0.11					
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	+	+	•	•	•	•	+	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	•	•	1	+	•	+	0.07	1	0.07					
<i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i>	+	•	+	•	+	•	+	+	•	+	+	•	+	+	+	1	+	•	+	+	+	+	•	+	+	1	•	+	0.07	1	0.07					
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	•	•	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	1	+	•	•	+	•	•	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	•	+	1	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.07	1	0.07	
<i>Thymus glabrescens</i>	2	2	3	•	+	2	3	2	8	2	1	3	3	+	+	1	2	2	3	2	2	+	1	1	•	1	1	+	1.68	0	0					
<i>Juncus effusus</i>	1	+	•	3	3	+	5	+	+	1	3	1	+	+	+	1	+	+	1	2	+	1	5	+	•	3	2	1.14	0	0						
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	2	2	2	1	+	1	2	2	2	1	2	+	+	+	1	1	2	2	1	+	+	1	+	•	1	+	1	+	1	0	0					
<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	1	3	+	•	+	+	•	+	2	+	+	1	+	+	+	0.25	0	0					
<i>Potentilla anserina</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	7	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.25	0	0	
<i>Carex hirta</i>	+	+	•	+	1	•	+	+	+	1	+	1	•	•	+	1	•	•	+	+	+	+	1	•	•	•	•	1	0.21	0	0					
<i>Carex caryophylla</i>	•	•	+	•	+	+	+	+	2	1	•	+	•	•	•	•	1	+	•	+	+	•	•	+	1	+	+	+	0.18	0	0					
<i>Euphrasia stricta</i>	1	+	1	•	1	1	+	+	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	•	+	+	+	0.18	0	0					
<i>Juncus inflexus</i>	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	+	+	3	+	1	•	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.14	0	0	
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	2	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.11	0	0					
<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	1	+	+	+	0.07	0	0					
<i>Galium mollugo</i>	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	+	+	+	+	+	2	+	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.07	0	0				
<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	2	•	•	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.07	0	0				
<i>Lythrum salicaria</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	2	+	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.07	0	0				
<i>Senecio erucifolius</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	2	+	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.07	0	0					
<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	1	•	•	•	•	•	•	1	•	•	•	•	0.07	0	0					
<i>Typha latifolia</i>	•	2	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.07	0	0					

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	
<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i>	•	•	+	•	+	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	2	•	•	•	+	•	•	0.07	0	0	
<i>Carlina vulgaris</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	2	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.07	0	0
<i>Bellis perennis</i>	+	+	•	1	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0.04	0	0
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Galium verum</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	+	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	+	+	•	•	+	+	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Rumex acetosa</i>	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Prunella laciniata</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Mentha pulegium</i>	+	•	•	+	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	+	+	+	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Filago germanica</i>	+	•	•	+	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	+	+	•	+	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Potentilla argentea</i>	•	•	•	+	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Cerastium holosteoides</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Centaureum erythraea</i>	+	•	+	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Odontites vulgaris</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Gypsophila muralis</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Viola tricolor</i>	+	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Spiranthes spirales</i>	+	+	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Cruciatia glabra</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Verbena officinalis</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Potentilla reptans</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Epilobium roseum</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Juncus conglomeratus</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Polygala vulgaris</i>	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Clinopodium vulgare</i>	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Lysimachia vulgaris</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Filipendula hexapetala</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Scabiosa ochroleuca</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Gnaphalium sylvaticum</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Inula hirta</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Carum carvi</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Senecio jacobaea</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i>	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Inula britannica</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0
<i>Pulicaria vulgaris</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	0

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31				
<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	+	.	+	.	.	.	+	0	0			
<i>Cuscuta campestris</i>	+	.	+	0	0		
<i>Dipsacus laciniatus</i>	+	+	+	0	0		
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i>	+	.	.	+	0	0		
<i>Bupleurum tenuissimum</i>	+	+	0	0		
<i>Linaria vulgaris</i>	+	+	0	0		
<i>Helianthemum nummularium</i>	+	+	0	0	
<i>Picris hieracioides</i>	+	+	0	0	
<i>Veronica spicata</i>	+	+	0	0	
<i>Centaurea scabiosa</i>	.	.	+	+	0	0	
<i>Matricaria perforata</i>	+	+	0	0	
<i>Calystegia sepium</i>	+	+	0	0	
<i>Senecio ovatus</i>	.	.	+	.	+	0	0	
<i>Seseli annuum</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Rorippa sylvestris</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Rhinanthus minor</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Campanula patula</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Stachys officinalis</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Stachys germanica</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Lactuca viminea</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Dipsacus fullonum</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Glechoma hederacea</i>	+	0	0	
<i>Dianthus carthusianorum</i>	+	0	0
Harmful and toxic species (%)	(27)	(30)	(30)	(10)	(35)	(15)	(20)	(28)	(25)	(10)	(5)	(5)	(15)	(10)	(8)	(12)	(17)	(22)	(23)	(15)	(23)	(13)	(10)	(12)	(15)	(15)	(18)	(19)	17.4						
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	2	5	10	4	10	5	10	3	20	2	3	3	10	3	2	8	15	20	20	15	20	8	2	8	10	10	15	15	9.21	0	0				
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	25	25	20	6	25	10	10	25	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.82	0	0	
<i>Eryngium campestre</i>	.	.	+	+	+	2	2	.	2	5	1	5	3	2	2	2	.	3	.	2	3	3	5	2	1	1.61	0	0			
<i>Ranunculus polyanthemus</i>	+	.	+	+	2	.	+	.	1	1	.	+	+	.	+	+	1	.	.	1	1	0.25	0	0				
<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	1	2	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	1	.	.	+	0.14	0	0			
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i>	+	.	+	+	.	+	+	.	1	1	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	.	.	+	+	0.11	0	0				
<i>Ranunculus repens</i>	2	+	+	.	.	+	.	+	+	.	0.07	0	0			
<i>Tanacetum vulgare</i>	+	.	2	+	0.07	0	0	
<i>Sambucus ebulus</i>	1	+	0.04	0	0	
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	+	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	.	+	0.04	0	0			
<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	1	+	+	+	.	+	+	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	.	.	+	.	0.04	0	0			
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	.	+	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	+	.	.	+	.	.	0	0			
<i>Rumex conglomeratus</i>	+	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	0	0		
<i>Polygonum hydropiper</i>	+	.	.	+	+	+	+	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	+	.	.	0	0		
<i>Stellaria graminea</i>	+	0	0		

CONCLUSIONS

In the area under study, considering pastoral value, *Agrostis capillaris* grassland of medium productivity (20 relevées) and good productivity (8 relevées), were found.

The pastoral value of all studied grassland is medium (V.P.=45.92). A significant proportion of toxic and harmful species is observed in some relevées (*Eryngium campestre*, *Pteridium aquilinum*, *Eryngium campestre*, *Ranunculus polyanthemos*, *Cardus acanthoides*, *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*), this decreases their pastoral value. For the removal of toxic and harmful species from the studied grassland, work is needed to combat mechanical, chemical and biological methods, overgrowing the remaining gaps.

The woody species are also present in this grassland in shrub or invasive form of tree species, works to combat them and the overgrowth of the remaining gaps being also necessary.

The overgrowth of the grasslands will be carried out with local species of plants, wishing to preserve their natural composition.

Fertilization work with organic and chemical fertilizers are required to increase the productivity of the grassland studied.

Due to the small number of animals that graze on these pastures in the future, some of them will be covered by woody vegetation, receiving another destination.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE ANTHROPOGENIC COMPONENT ON THE SOIL EVOLUTION IN THE BĂIŢA - ŞTEI AREA FROM THE BEIUŞ BASIN

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Abstract

After 1990 there was a period of transition in Romania. This period was represented by the transition from a socio-political and economic system characterized by collective ownership or from a centralized economy to a market economy. In this context, agriculture as a branch with a strategic role in the market economy required the allocation of considerable financial resources for innovation, reorganization, restructuring and modernization.

Organizing villages and peasant households, as well as in the whole country, and in the Băiţa - Ştei area from the Beiuş basin, with the restoration of land owners' rights and the purchase of agricultural equipment from the former cars batch of the Cooperative (CAP) and of the State agricultural enterprise (IAS), changes since 1990 and the following years.

The effect of subsistence and semi-subsistence is almost entirely manifested in the small and very small forms of private property in which the agri-food products are only for self-consumption, the number of animals decreases due to the lesser workforce, the aging population and the low efficiency of strongly fragmented land, which also leads to higher production costs.

Due to the mechanization performed on the small plots of land, the repeated passage of the machines for carrying out the agricultural works to a high value of the degree of humidity, the degree of compaction of the soils increases, to a lesser or greater extent with the fragmentation of the land surfaces.

Key words: property, profitability, efficiency, mechanization, machinery, compaction.

INTRODUCTION

The * 90s, the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century are characterized by:

- the increasing the greenhouse effect; CO₂ emissions, car parts, expansion of areas and intensification of industrial activities, deterioration of the ozone layer, deforestation, pollution of the plastic component and hydrocarbons;

- the deregulation of weather cycles in different areas of the Earth (climate inversions, floods, torrential rains, with massive flows in a very short time, which is manifested by a very low degree of infiltration into the ground and a very high coefficient of flow to the surface which generates landslides);

- the atypical circulation of air masses, tornado-like events in Central Europe and the Eastern European part, including Romania.

The intracoloniai Beiuș basin is the result of the action of the Crișul Negru and its many tributaries that created a system of valleys with terraces and meadows.

Fig. 1. Bihor County the S-E area (after Google maps, 2019)

The solification process takes place in the S-E area of the Beiuș basin in a specific way. Due to the presence of the weather and the anthropic elements of the relief it is important to mention that they have an equal influence and they place their imprint on the solification process.

Fig. 2. The S-E of the Beiuș basin

Soil compaction is a real problem for the agriculture in Romania. In addition to the primary (natural) compaction, there is a secondary (anthropic) compaction, which occurs during the agricultural work, due to repeated passes with the machines, especially when the soil has a higher degree of moisture. Compaction modifies the soil quality indicators, the porosity and the permeability.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research methods consisted of: field observations, discussions with landowners and owners, consultation of the archived documents, discussions with the staff of local authorities in Băița - Ștei area, sampling and analysis of the soil samples. The samples were made with the pedological probe on land surfaces in Ștei - Băița area, the analyzes were carried out in the laboratories of the Faculty of Environmental Protection Oradea and at OSPA Oradea.

Figure 3. Pedological probe

The granulometric determination method was performed according to STAS 7184 / 10-79.

The humus determination method was performed according to STAS 7184 / 21-82.

Method of determining apparent density (AD)

The soil sampling probe with foot rest was used for this operation, for depth 0-25m, and also the soil sampling probe with hammer head for depth 25-50cm. The probe was then emptied of the soil, which was transferred into bags and transported to the laboratory. Then the soil samples were dried in the drying stove at 105 ° C for 10 hours and finally the dried soil was weighed.

Table 1

Granulometric soil analysis from Câmpani (2000)

Depth (cm)	0-25	25-50
Coarse sand(2.0-0.2mm)%	25.7	26.0
Fine sand(0.2-0.02mm)%	29.1	26.1
Dust(0.02-0.002mm)%	13.4	17.4
Clay(>0.002)%	31.8	30.5
Texture	LN	LL
AD (g/m ³)	1.33	1.82
Humus%	2.38	0.97

Table 2

Granulometric soil analysis from Câmpani (2019)

Depth (cm)	0-25	25-50
Coarse sand(2.0-0.2mm)%	24.8	22.1
Fine sand(0.2-0.02mm)%	32.1	27,4
Dust(0.02-0.002mm)%	12.2	17,8
Clay(>0.002)%	30.9	32.7
Texture	LN	LL
AD (g/m ³)	1.84	2.15
Humus%	2,40	1.08

In the Câmpani area on the land where soil samples were taken (in 2000 and 2019), due to the mechanization on small areas of land, the carrying out of agricultural works at a higher level of moisture and the weather factors, the degree of compaction increased by 38% in the 0-25cm layer and by 18% in the 25-50cm layer.

Table 3

Granulometric soil analysis from Ştei (2000)

Depth (cm)	0-25	25-50
Coarse sand(2.0-0.2mm)%	21.3	21.7
Fine sand(0.2-0.02mm)%	22.8	17.6
Dust(0.02-0.002mm)%	23.7	28.9
Clay(>0.002)%	32.2	31.8
Texture	LL	LL
AD (g/m ³)	1.40	1.87
Humus%	2.43	1.04

Table 4

Granulometric soil analysis from Ştei (2019)

Depth (cm)	0-25	25-50
Coarse sand(2.0-0.2mm)%	13.5	14.6
Fine sand(0.2-0.02mm)%	31.9	26.4
Dust(0.02-0.002mm)%	25.2	27.7
Clay(>0.002)%	29.4	31.3
Texture	LL	LL
AD(g/m ³)	1.99	2.17
Humus%	2,39	0.98

In the area of Ştei on the ground where soil samples were taken (in 2000 and 2019), due to the mechanization on small areas of land, the carrying out of agricultural works at a high level of moisture and the weather factors, the degree of compaction increased by 42% in the 0-25cm layer and by 16% in the 25-50cm layer.

The compaction occurs when pressure is applied to the soil surface when passing agricultural equipment during the soil work.

The mechanization on small plots of land intensifies the compaction process which unfavorably influences the soil quality indicators (the porosity and the permeability), reduces the degree of infiltration and intensifies the one of surface leakage, especially on the inclined surfaces. It decreases the number of pores and capillaries which determines a lower

water and oxygen reserve in soil, higher mechanical resistance to agricultural work, the root system development being hindered.

The presence of a low permeability layer also makes the upper soil layer prone to water saturation and therefore heavier. This upper layer is exposed to a risk of erosion due to the higher amount of surface runoff and landslides.

In the plain area the compaction leads to water supersaturation causing the destruction of the aggregates and the crust forming. The soil structure can be improved with some organic matter, by reducing its predisposition to compaction, erosion and landslides.

The mechanization carried out on small areas of land that replaced more or less the carrying out of agricultural works caused changes in the structure but especially in the texture of the soil in the studied area, a phenomenon that is reflected on our entire country.

Due to reductions in livestock in the area lately, fertilization with manure is declining which changes the chemical mineralogical composition, or mineral dowry of the soil and it had contributed to the intensification of the phenomenon of compaction.

In the area of the existing villages, there are no associative forms regarding agricultural areas.

The compaction can be eliminated by: administering organic fertilizers (manure), incorporating plant residues under the fence, carrying out agricultural works at suitable humidity, scarification, deep plowing, carrying out agricultural work with minimum machine passes and so on.

CONCLUSIONS

The *90s represent the transition from a socio-political and economic system, characterized by collective ownership, to the market policy in which the CAER system is abandoned. This market policy is oriented towards the European Union and its purpose is the development of the market economy. The individual property rights on agricultural land are restored.

The re-ownership restores the rights of the owners from the agricultural areas. The machines with animal traction are gradually replaced. The owners have the possibility to buy tractors at low prices from the car batch of the Cooperative (CAP) and the State agricultural enterprise (IAS).

In a very short period of time the agriculture in Romania changes essentially, from very large areas belonging to the Cooperative (CAP) and to the State agricultural enterprise (IAS), to small and very small farms (individual households) that coexist with the medium and large farms.

Once Romania enters the European Union, the agricultural activities are highlighted and the agrarian economy confirms that small and very small households (family and individual households) are inefficient, unviable and unprofitable in the current European and world context.

Global and local weather phenomena influence the soil quality indicators.

The use of mechanized equipment (tractors, agricultural combine machines and so on) requires wider and consolidated access paths, compatible with the gauge of the used machines.

An annual cycle involves plowing, sowing, maintenance and harvesting, the presence of machinery on agricultural land for a relatively long period of time which determines the modification of the structural indicators: structure and texture.

Due to the strong fragmentation of the lands, the access roads, the maneuvering spaces and the changes of the walking direction remove 10 - 20% of the agricultural circuit.

Mechanization on small batches means higher production costs and deterioration of soil quality indicators resulting in lower productiveness.

Due to the constantly declining workforce, the aging population and the low efficiency of the highly fragmented land areas, it is necessary to reorganize them in the form of associations, establishing a common composting platform.

The vegetal material will be used, either by incorporation under the furrow to improve the compaction effect or by composting for soft materials, grinding and briquetting the cellulose parts that are eventually being used for combustion.

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**EDIFICATIONS FROM THE LEADER PROGRAM BASED ON THE
RESULTS OF A HUNGARIAN MICRO-REGIONI.
INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW**

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Abstract

15 years ago Hungary joined the European Union. The first full financial period for the nation as a member of the European Community was 2007-2013. As a full member, Hungary gained access to many financial sources granted by the European Union. It is necessary to inspect the efficiency of how these sources have been spent on development, focusing on the LEADER program. The best way to do this is by selecting one of the poorer micro-regions and examining it using different methods. Within my research I used inspected different statistics, I looked into the traditional profession of shepherding which has a long history in the region and I interviewed the citizens of the Sárrét microregion. This multidisciplinary research gave more precise results and conclusions for my research. Suggestions made on the on the conclusions can provide a much more accurate help to decision makers in the periods that are ahead of us.

Key words: LEADER program, Hungary, Sárrét, development, shepherding

INTRODUCTION

In Hungary – just like in every other countries – the social or economical investments are all achieved from multiple financial sources. Executing the projects is possible from national or foreign capital, support from companies, private people or the state, or maybe from community contribution. Just like the projects that are financed by the European Union through tenders, and sometimes co-founded by national sources. It is necessary to inspect the changes have been made in Hungary, in its regions and in its subregions, because Hungary became a member of the EU 14 years ago. I am examining the complete process, from the founding of the European Community, through Hungary joining the EU and after that, up until today. Taking the concept of the LEADER programme into consideration and using it to examine the local capabilities, traditions in the villages and towns of the rural micro regions.

During my research I set the goal to examine the projects completed within the LEADER programme in 5 settlements that are located in the micro region called Sárrét. My choice was greatly influenced by the fact that in earlier times I have worked with several people living and working in this microregion and that I personally knew some of the mayors before.

The importance of the Sárrét micro region is shown by the large scale of international transit of goods and passenger traffic (Oláh, 1987). The reason for this is that the Sárrét is located on the eastern edge of the Schengen border (Osváth, 1875). At the same time, it is not a typical tourist attraction, so tourism is not the major source of incomes and cannot support the financial background for developments in the settlements of the Sárrét. In my opinion the local inhabitants have a strong identity and have a strong bond with their village. These are the reasons why I decided that the vicinity and the people living in it are suitable subjects for my research.

Based on my experiences, I am convinced, and this applies to all Eastern European countries, that we can only become full members of the EU if all of Hungary's 7 regions achieve the EU's average (Sarudi, 1997). For this it is necessary to strengthen the macro and micro environment of the local communities by involving all actors who live in them.

Hungary needs to be efficient when using the funding sources, it has won, and since there is a huge disparity between the economical, the environmental circumstances and in the quality of life as well, that makes the sources especially big. Unfortunately, the opportunities ahead of us are limited in time, because we can already see the will to centrally modify and reduce the sources, which is due by 2020.

My research focused on 3 main areas:

The first topic is the distribution of the use of EU funds in the period 2007-2013, especially in the Northern Great Plain region and within it in the Sárrét region.

The first and most important aspect for me was not the size of the source, but the evaluation of the region's independence, creativity, and the micro-regions ability to apply for the sources, so I examined the LEADER programs using the aspects that I presented in the material and method.

The second area of my research was to study the agricultural supporting capacity of the area. For this I chose a real, traditionally operating sector, the shepherding, which partly provided the livelihood of the people living in the Sárrét region for centuries and has a long tradition among the local population.

The third element of my research was the public opinion of the projects made in the Sárrét. Actually analyzing the evaluation of developments based on the opinion of the population (Pálmai, 2013). How do people living, working and originated from the area judge the development of their habitat, its directions and speed. Do they have a vision, how do they feel about the development of the rural existence (Soós, 2004). It was important to determine how much they know about their living space, how much they know about improvements, and whether they feel the

changes in their individual lives. In order to answer these questions, I chose an in-depth interview and questionnaire method.

I did my research at the Doctoral School of History and Ethnography at the Faculty of Humanities of the University of Debrecen. My research was primarily based on the anthropological aspects of the economy. This discipline combines the basics of economics with social science and historical foundations. This required a complex examination, which often set extremely difficult challenges during my research. Not only did I need to be aware of economic concepts and methodology, but I also needed to know a micro-region and its population, past, and habits in order to see the necessary connections properly. I found it important to examine the micro-region not only by itself, but as part of a larger unit, a system, because they interact with each other. Therefore, every decision affects the whole system and all its parts. In order to understand the current economic and social situation in the Sárret micro-region, we need to look into all the details at the European Union's current cohesion and agricultural policy and the process that led to its present form. Due to the interdisciplinary nature of my research, the development of the social and economic and agricultural support system is of great importance for my research. The goal is to understand the background and motivation behind efforts of the poorer regions to catch up with the more developed regions.

Literature review

One of the most important aims of the European Union and its predecessors was to create a strong and uniform entity, which plays a decisive role in international economic and political life, by successfully working together to reduce and eliminate economic and social disparities at regional level. The purpose of the Cohesion Fund, set up in 1993, was to bring about major transport and environmental projects in the then poorest Member States of the Community. Only regions with a GDP per capita below 75% of the EU average are eligible. There are several such regions in Hungary which perform below 75% of the EU average, including the North Great Plain region, which is also home to the Sárret micro-region.

It is important for a country to be divided into territorial units to carry out development, as this is the only way to compare them and produce and analyse statistics to develop a successful development strategy (Szakál, 1999). Regional policy is particularly important for Hungary. Although agricultural subsidies are extremely beneficial for the country due to its special characteristics, the low domestic GDP per capita also means that Hungary is significantly lagging behind in terms of the quality of life.

Europe, home of my country – as the famous saying goes. Going from global to local thinking, the same is true for the North Great Plain region, as the area under investigation in Hungary - the Sárret micro-region - and my

home region, in the narrower sense of the word, is the administrative area in the eastern part of the country. Accordingly, we need to look at the situation in the world, in the Union and in the country.

Regional policy did not begin with the European Union, although the conscious organising activity and the establishment of institutions was performed in parallel to the history of the Union. Schuman dreamed up the necessity of cooperation between European countries and the principles of cooperation and summarised his ideas and concepts in the Schuman Plan (1951). This work laid the foundations for the development and organisation that we today call the European Union.

During the 2000-2006 period, community initiatives have been strengthened, providing EU policy objectives and a common political and economic context for the needs of local-based communities.

The sources for implementing Community initiatives are:

- INTERREG III: support for cross-border cooperation programs
- URBAN II: regeneration of urban areas in crisis
- EQUAL: combating discrimination and inequalities in the labour market
- LEADER +: rural development

LEADER is the name of a program developed by the European Commission as part of the European Union's rural development policy. LEADER is one of the so-called "Four Community Initiatives". The name of the program is derived from the initials of the French name Liaison Entre Actions de l'Economie Rurale (Varga, 2010; Zsigáné, 2013).

LEADER developments can be characterised by the following seven key principles: area-based development, bottom-up approach, tripartite partnerships (business, civil and public), innovation, an integrated sectoral approach, network operation, cooperation (Zsigáné, 2013)

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EDIFICATIONS FROM THE LEADER PROGRAM BASED ON THE RESULTS OF A HUNGARIAN MICRO-REGION II. MATERIAL AND METHODS, OWN ANALYSES

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Abstract

15 years ago Hungary joined the European Union. The first full financial period for the nation as a member of the European Community was 2007-2013. As a full member, Hungary gained access to many financial sources granted by the European Union. It is necessary to inspect the efficiency of how the sources have been spent on development, focusing on the LEADER program. The best way to do this is by selecting one of the poorer micro-regions and examining it using different methods. Within my research I used inspected different statistics, I looked into the traditional profession of shepherding which has a long history in the region and I interviewed the citizens of the Sárrét microregion. This multidisciplinary research gave more precise results and conclusions for my research. Suggestions made on the on the conclusions can provide a much more accurate help to decision makers in the periods that are ahead of us.

Key words: LEADER program, Hungary, Sárrét, development, shepherding

MATERIAL AND METHOD

During the examination of Topic 1, I was looking for answers to the question of how successful the Hungarian regional policy, especially with regard to Community Initiatives, was between 2007 and 2013 (Glatz, 2008). I made a comparative study of the North Great Plain Region, Hajdú-Bihar County and Sárrét. In the case of the 5 settlements selected in Sárrét, I conducted a structured interview with the inhabitants of the settlements, with which I also examined the feasibility of the implemented developments and their adaptation to local conditions. My aim was to reveal whether the use of development funds invested in the examined period contributed to the catching up of poorer regions or they maintained or increased their economic and social backwardness.

Based on the available data and the HCSO databases, I made a comparative analysis of the Hungarian regions. It is important to examine Hajdú-Bihar county and the North Great Plain region, which is the narrower home of the Sárrét, because the economy of a small region is most influenced by the political, economic and social processes of its surrounding region.

The database used for my research was provided by the Institute for Rural Development, Training and Consulting - VKSZI (later NAKVI,

currently Herman Ottó Institute). The data were collected by EPAP Kft. The database was obtained in a Microsoft Excel file and the statistics, graphs and tables used for the analysis were also done in Microsoft Excel. I have tried to choose and use an analytical method that will allow my research results to be used further by others. Continuing the analysis and further expanding the data may provide another perspective for practical use.

The methodology used in the survey of the settlements of Sárrét was the following: Knowing the historical background of the region, I conducted a structured interview in which I asked 26 questions divided into three topics. This interview is shown in Appendix 1. In the first round, I was curious about the individual and their relationship with the community. In the second round, I asked questions about the developments that were made. Finally, in the third part, I was looking for answers to the extent to which the implemented developments fit into the spirit of the LEADER program and local conditions.

Surveying the experiences and needs of locals provides the most accurate confirmation that the proper development has taken place or that there have been "dead-end" investments that are unjustified and their maintenance may even be a burden for the local community and the community budget (Sain, 2010).

As a second topic, I analysed the specific relationship between agriculture and rural development. I chose a long-standing traditional livestock breeding industry, sheep-breeding, which has a strong influence on the culture, heritage and traditions of the Sárrét region.

Peasant culture and traditions are ubiquitous in the Sárrét region, and are an integral part of the lifestyle of shepherds and sheep-keepers and all other attributes.

The large number of Hungarian sheep farms in the less favoured areas can also be well integrated into the rural development instruments by choosing appropriate development directions (Moseley, 2013). According to Madai (2000), the inclusion of support related to rural development and the sector in the strategy could better help the implementation of differentiated forms of support linked to the level of production and efficiency, as the aid linked to rural development could partially replace the income support (KostovandLingard, 2001). It is also important because, according to the calculations of Jávör and Nábrádi (1999), 25.4% of the ewe stock was in socially and infrastructurally underdeveloped settlements, while 15.3% was in settlements where unemployment is 1.5 times higher than the Hungarian average.

The natural maintenance of pasture farming, grasslands and less fertile areas, which is not an easy task for other types of farming, are the main areas where sheep breeding contributes to the maintenance of environmental

balance (biodiversity and water quality, erosion, control of floods, avalanches and fires, storage of carbonaceous compounds in soil organic matter). At the same time, sheep play a key role in the social cohesion of agricultural areas.

In the third topic, which included the inhabitants' evaluation of the developments based on a structured interview, I wanted to examine how the inhabitants of the different villages experienced the development of their place of residence (Kovács and Koós, 2018).

Do they see the adaptation of the development in the life of their community, do they sense the improvement of the quality of life, or the change in the quality of services? Are there any population groups who have different perceptions of the changes in the life of their village? I was also looking for the impact of economic, social and infrastructural investments on village life (G. Fekete, 2013). I also tried to ensure that the respondents reflect the composition of the population in terms of education, age, and gender.

Own analyses

The examined settlements are Bihardancsháza, Bihartorda, Nagyrábé, Sáp and Sárrétudvari. All five villages, as they are often described in technical terms, are disadvantaged. In addition to the interviews, I examined the composition and proportions of the population living in the settlement according to age, education, religion, ethnicity, marital status and employment. These are all important factors for a better understanding of the responses of the inhabitants of a settlement during the interview. They tell a lot about the satisfaction, the standard of living, the mental health of the local people, and the kind of communities that are present in the settlement and how cohesive they are (Uzzoli and Szilágyi, 2013).

In the light of these factors, I analysed and evaluated the interviews and the investments made.

The five settlements under investigation occupy 18,975 hectares, with a total population of 7159 people. Territorially, Nagyrábé is the largest settlement - albeit second only in terms of population -, which covers 8542 hectares, accounts for almost half (45.02%) of the total area, while only 1.38% of the county. The smallest settlement, both in terms of population and its size expressed in hectares, is Bihardancsháza, which occupies only 831 hectares, represents only 4.38% of the examined region and only 0.13% of Hajdú-Bihar County.

In addition to the number of inhabitants and the size of the settlement, the composition of the population is also important. The composition of age, gender, nationality and education largely determines the innovative character and opportunities of young people and their desire to stay or go.

The future of an aging settlement like Bihardancsháza without a drastic intervention can be easily seen. Young people emigrate in a couple of decades and the rest of the elderly disappear, leaving the village depopulated.

An important part of the survey is the analysis of the population of the settlements in Sárrét by population density, marital status, education, employment, gender distribution, and ethnic and religious affiliation, as this gives a more accurate picture of the community and its mental health status. Mental status is greatly influenced by the fact that a person is single, married, or widowed, since there is also a place to belong for a person in a marriage, while a single or widowed person may be negatively affected by loneliness, which he or she may try to compensate for by trying to become an integral part of a community. Such a community can be a religious congregation or even an ethnic group.

Sárrét projects between 2007-2013

To track developments and improvements over the past decade, I have collected projects for the five settlements in the district of Püspökladány in the Sárrét micro-region, which were important to me because I wanted to know how and to what extent the population perceived the developments, how much they knew about them and did they take part in their implementation? As a matter of course, I was also curious about their attitude towards further improvements.

In the assessed cycle, the five villages received a total of 173 million HUF of LEADER support, of which 154.7 million was used. It follows that, unfortunately, two grants received were not used in the case of Nagyrabé. As a result, investments of approximately 18.3 million EUR were not implemented.

The average of the small region was 19,951 HUF, i.e., it did not reach 20,000 HUF per person. I am convinced that this is very little for a pace of development that has the hope of catching up, especially because economic investment and development was only rarely found.

Altogether, economic development in the examined cycle from LEADER resources was negligible. Consequently, long-term job creation was not significant either. The development of accommodation can also have a spillover effect.

Developments are also important in the life of a village because they can improve infrastructure, social conditions, health and schools. They can contribute to transport, environmental quality, job creation, economic attractiveness and income, which are key elements of the quality of life in rural areas. From the aspect of the running projects, it is very important how much investments reach the population and to what extent they are utilised,

contributing to the population's mental state and vision. They also show how much they love their village and the reasons they have when planning to stay or emigrate. To determine these aspects, I developed a questionnaire, which can be found in the attachment.

In addition to personal data, the questionnaire includes the inhabitants' ambition, their relationship to the settlement and community life, and their knowledge of the development of the settlement.

I divided the interview questions into three groups. The first group contained questions that were meant to map the age of the individual and their relationship with the settlement. It was important for me to assess how long they have lived in their place of residence, what has connected them to the settlement, as well as what abilities, skills and opportunities they have had so far to become involved in community life.

The second group of questions was mapping the involvement of the community in the projects. In addition, I intended to reveal how well they know the developments implemented and, if so, how they see their necessity and usefulness.

The third and final group of questions concerns the LEADER program. It assesses the respondents' awareness of the program and the extent to which its developments have been adapted to its principles and spirit. These questions assess current and future needs, the developments being implemented and the opportunities for involving the population.

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THE LEVEL OF AIR POLLUTION WITH NITROGEN DIOXIDE IN THE CITY OF SATU-MARE BETWEEN 2016 AND 2018

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Abstract

This paper presents the study conducted on the level of air pollution with nitrogen dioxide in the city of Satu Mare between 2016 and 2018. The degree of air pollution with nitrogen dioxide is monitored by the Satu Mare Environmental Protection Agency at its four sampling points placed strategically in different parts of Satu Mare. The sampling points are located as follows: in the central area of the city, at the venue of the Satu Mare Environmental Protection Agency (APM Satu Mare), the next one is in Șoimoșeni St (the industrial area found in the north of the city), the third is in the industrial area around Magnoliei St, while the fourth is at the junction of Burdea St and Careiului Rd.

The values recorded at the four monitoring points show that the evolution of the nitrogen dioxide average concentrations, as well as the evolution of the multiannual monthly average concentrations have not exceeded the maximum permissible concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. However, the daily analysis of the level of pollution with nitrogen dioxide shows that between 2016 and 2018 the maximum permissible concentration (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was exceeded 33 times, at two monitoring points, Magnoliei St and Careiului Rd respectively, the highest concentration recorded being 171.47 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Key words: maximum permissible concentration, monitoring, nitrogen dioxide, sampling points

INTRODUCTION

Nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) is a reddish-brown gas, with a strong and pungent odour, being considered an important source of smog. The main pollution sources with nitrogen dioxide are car engines, power plants and the burning of fossil fuels (Mănescu et al, 1994; Ciulache, 2004; Pereș et al., 2011; Köteles, Pereș, 2010). Nitrogen dioxide can be taken by air far away.

A long exposure to this pollutant can cause an increase in the incidence of asthma, an increase in death cases due to pulmonary diseases.

The nitrogen dioxide concentrations have been studied over the years by several researchers, including: Măhăra, 1976; Moza, 2009; Moza, Köteles, 2010; Köteles, 2011; Pereș, Köteles, 2010; Pereș, 2011; Dumiter, 2005.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The data on the level of pollution with nitrogen dioxide were provided by the Satu Mare Environmental Protection Agency. In the area of the city

of Satu Mare there are four monitoring points, located strategically in its important areas.

The first sampling point can be found in the central area, at the venue of the Satu Mare Environmental Protection Agency, the next one in the norther part of the city, in Șoimoșeni St, the third point is in the industrial area around Magnoliei St and the fourth one at the junction of Burdea St and Careiului Rd (apmsm.anpm.ro).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Annual evolution of nitrogen dioxide

The results obtained after processing the data show that between 2016 and 2018 the highest values of nitrogen dioxide were recorded at the Careiului Rd and Magnoliei St monitoring points, $53.44 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (2016) and 48.98 (2016) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively. At the sampling point in Careiului Rd the concentration was higher again in 2018, $43.47 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The maximum permissible concentration of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was not exceeded.

At the monitoring points at the venue of the APM Satu Mare and in Șoimoșeni St the nitrogen dioxide concentrations were lower, between $15.18 - 30.48 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Evolution of the average nitrogen dioxide concentrations in Satu Mare, 2016-2018

The analysis of the average concentration of nitrogen dioxide for the years included in the study, 2016 – 2018, shows that the highest value was recorded at the Careiului Rd monitoring point, $45.44 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. A close concentration was obtained at the Magnoliei St monitoring point, $39.79 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

At the monitoring points located in the centre of the city (the venue of APM Satu-Mare) and in Şoimoseni St, the nitrogen dioxide concentrations were $19.70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $16.93 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Evolution of the nitrogen dioxide multiannual average concentrations at the four sampling points located in Satu Mare, 2016-2018

Monthly evolution of nitrogen dioxide

The analysis of the monthly evolution of nitrogen dioxide concentrations at the monitoring points between 2016 and 2018, shows that the highest values were recorded in 2016, as follows: in January, $61.93 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, in March, $52.43 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, in February, $46.49 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and in April, $45.95 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, as well as in December 2018, $54.86 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. In 2017, the highest concentrations occurred in July, $35.15 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, in June, $34.59 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and in August, $33.05 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

The lowest concentration was recorded in April 2017, $0.50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, followed by $13.59 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in July 2018. Low values were also recorded in December 2016, $20.15 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and in December 2017, $20.81 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (see Figure 3).

The results above show that at the four monitoring points the maximum permissible concentration of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was not exceeded.

Fig. 3. Monthly pattern of the nitrogen dioxide at the 4 sampling points in Satu Mare, 2016-2018

Table1

Number of samplings, of exceedances and the highest value of nitrogen dioxide recorded in Satu Mare between 2016 and 2018

Month/ Year	Total number of samplings	Number of exceedances	The highest value recorded $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Sampling point
I/2016	73	10	129.70	Magnoliei St
I/2017	64	0	-	-
I/2018	76	0	-	-
II/2016	78	3	122.06	Magnoliei St and Careiului Rd
II/2017	70	0	-	-
II/2018	76	0	-	-
III/2016	88	4	114.99	Careiului Rd
III/2017	85	0	-	-
III/2018	82	0	-	-
IV/2016	72	4	125.72	Careiului Rd
IV/2017	74	0	-	-
IV/2018	72	0	-	-
V/2016	72	0	-	-
V/2017	79	0	-	-
V/2018	77	0	-	-
VI/2016	74	1	105.19	Careiului Rd
VI/2017	73	0	-	-
VI/2018	74	0	-	-
VII/2016	78	0	-	-
VII/2017	82	1	104.89	Careiului Rd
VII/2018	84	0	-	-
VIII/2016	80	1	108.57	Careiului Rd
VIII/2017	77	1	105.50	Careiului Rd
VIII/2018	70	0	-	-
IX/2016	80	3	126.95	Careiului Rd
IX/2017	78	0	-	-
IX/2018	78	0	-	-
X/2016	76	2	147.29	Careiului Rd
X/2017	83	0	-	-
X/2018	88	0	-	-
XI/2016	78	0	-	-
XI/2017	83	0	-	-
XI/2018	77	0	-	-
XII/2016	76	0	-	-
XII/2017	73	0	-	-
XII/2018	67	3	171.47	Careiului Rd

The daily evolution of the level of pollution with nitrogen dioxide between 2016 and 2018 shows that out of the 925 samplings taken in 2016 the maximum permissible concentration of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (STAS 12574-87) was exceeded 28 times, the highest value being recorded at the Careiului Rd in October, the value of $147.29 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

In 2017, out of the 924 samplings the maximum permissible concentration was exceeded twice, the highest value was recorded at Careiului Rd in August, $105.50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

In 2018, out of the 921 samplings the maximum admissible concentration was exceeded three times, the highest value being recorded at the Careiului Rd point, $171.47 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (see Table 1).

CONCLUSIONS

Looking at the annual evolution of nitrogen dioxide for the years included in the study it can be concluded that the maximum permissible concentration of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was not exceeded. The highest level was $53.44 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, in 2016, at the Careiului Rd sampling point. In 2017, the highest concentration was $39.41 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Careiului Rd), while in 2018 the highest value recorded was $43.47 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. In the area of this sampling point the traffic is heavy and this is the reason why the level of pollution with nitrogen dioxide is higher as compared with the other monitoring points.

The monthly evolution of the level of pollution with nitrogen dioxide in the period included in the study shows that the average concentration of the four sampling points is higher in January 2016, $61.93 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. In 2017, the highest concentration was recorded in July, $35.15 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while in 2018 the highest value occurred in December, $54.86 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

The daily pattern of nitrogen dioxide shows that during the period included in the study the highest number of exceedances was recorded at the Careiului Rd sampling point, but they were of short duration.

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CLIMATE CHANGE-CAUSES AND EFFECTS

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Abstract

The study analyzes the „global modifications” as a result of the interconnected action of phenomena signalled on Earth, such as: global warming, climate modifications; reduction of the ozone layer; deforestation; reduction of resources; reduction of biodiversity; desertification; environmental pollution; demographic changes, as well as other relevant modifications, caused by other factors that render difficult finding solutions. All these being approached from the perspective of their effect on humans

Key words: ecologic crisis, global modifications, reduction of the Ozone layer, reduction of biodiversity, environment pollution

INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of the XXI century, we are facing rapid modifications on the globe. Modern technologies of preservation of energy and resources, more rapid circulation at the level of present communications may represent only few of the modifications which changed the world in better, but not all of these are beneficial for the environment (Brown R, 1996). The Earth is dominated by human activity, activity which transformed the surface of the planet, appearing new risk factors. Among these, we can mention: approximately 30% increase in the CO₂ concentration from the atmosphere, approximately one quarter of the species of birds from the Earth have disappeared, half of the sweet water being used in human activity; this lead to the so-called „water crisis”(Berca, 2000).

The human activity has affected the planet’s climate, modifying the whole biosphere.

These modifications without precedent in history affect the health and future of all alive organisms.

Some environmental problems are local, others have global implications, but all of them represent the result of the decisions of millions of people, or the result of the action of a small group of people with decision power in a state, government, industrial corporations, so on. (Ionuț et al., 2004).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The analysis of the „ecological crisis” with possibilities to reduce it, from the IPCC’s perspective, as well as the analysis of reasons of optimism in this

field (16). The environmental issues and their consequences on alive organisms have extended, becoming a threat to survival. We are facing a full ecological crisis, crisis which requires an international approach of the environmental issue. The „biocapacity” of the Earth exceeds today with 25% the capacity to support the needs of human kind, thus this crisis is manifested in three directions (8): - in the multiplication 4 times of the globe’s population in the XXth century, from 1,6 billions in 1900 to 6,4 billions in 2000; - in the development of dangerous technologies and their export in the 3rd world countries, poor countries, which lead to the deterioration of their environment due to the lack of instruments for the environmental control; - the replacement of natural products with synthetic, toxic ones, which accumulated in the environment’s biosystem. The result of the interconnected action of of a few phenomenasignalled on Earth are presented in this paper.

Global warming. The phenomenon is signalled starting with the end of the '80s. The green house effect is based on ascertaining the fact that, in time, some gases from the atmosphere absorb the calorific radiation sent out on the surface of the Earth, the gas by interaction with the calorific radiation are heated and resend the heat in all directions. A part of this rows over the atmosphere, contributing to its additional heating. The increase of concentration of these gases determines the heating of the Earth’s surface, creating the „green house effect”

Without the green house effect, the temperature of the surface of the ground would vary from 500⁰C in the sunny days to 40⁰C during the night and during nebulosity. Today, approximately 6 billion Gt. of CO₂ are annually eliminated into the troposphere, the concentration grew with approximately 1,5 ppm/an (0,4%/an), so a general increase of 25% in the past century. The combustion is responsible of approximately 80%, the rest of the percentage are due to deforestation. The increase of concentration of gas will lead to the increase of average temperature in the first half of the XXth century with approximately 0,5⁰C, and around the year 2100 with 20⁰C (16). The most familiar dates for the average monthly temperatures are those registered by C.E.T. (Central England Temperature) which show that the multiannual average in the past 30 years is higher with approximately 0,5⁰ C than the average of the past 330 years. This warming occurred in the past years is more obvious for the winter than for the summer, and from these dates there is a record year for temperature, the year 1990, when the annual average reached 10,6⁰C.

The numerical modelling of the global climate is supported by the laws of physics and has as basis the principle of pyramid. The pyramid illustrates the position of various models, position which emphasizes the complexity of the

three primary processes and the interaction between them. The modified pyramid has an empty basis, the interaction between the primary processes missing, and, once we approach the top, these processes become more powerful (11),

Reduction of the Ozone layer. The Ozone is the gas concentrated in the atmosphere at an altitude of 15.000- 45.000 m, with the role of filter and protector of the biosphere to the action of lethal UV radiations. The major effect of the atmosphere pollution is felt on the modification of the Ozone layer. The Oxygen's photochemistry may represent the cause of formation, but also of the destruction of the Ozone; we have to take into account the implications that the polluting agents and gases with the shape of traces had in the Ozone's survey. During the summer of 1985, in the South Hemisphere a „hole” in the Ozone layer over the Antarctica was noticed. From 1990, the phenomenon was noticed also in the Northern Hemisphere, over Siberia and in the East of North Africa. Until now, the reduction of the Ozone layer is estimated at approximately 3-4% from the atmospherical Ozone and it grows from one year to another (14).

The decrease of content of Ozone in the atmosphere on the global flux of the ultraviolet radiation, as well as on the movements of the spectrum of these waves, to smaller lengths (a reduction of 5 – 10% of the Ozone quantity may lead to an average increase of the ultraviolet radiations with 10 – 20%). If the increase would take place in the field of wave length of 28 – 320 µm, their biological effects would lead to the disorder of the whole planetary ecosystem.

Deforestation. The woods occupied approximately 70% from the surface of the Planet's dry land. Nowadays, we are far from this situation (for example, India lost 2/3 from its woods from 1990 until today, and the USA around 90% starting with the year 1620). With the help of satellites, the annual losses of woods were proved, renouncing to the essential nutrients of the Earth, disturbing water cycles and nourishing elements, impoverishing the soil's fertility reducing agricultural productivity, thus favouring the floods (1).

The wood is the most productive source of oxygen. 1 hectare of wood produces 3 – 10 times more oxygen than 1 hectare of agricultural crop or than 1 hectare of marine phytoplankton. The importance of woods in recycling of oxygen is represented also by the fact that the forest vegetal production, being harvested by humans, this does not decompose, meanwhile the marine ecosystems are consuming in the decomposition process of the organic substance the highest quantity of produced oxygen (4). In the article „*When the wood issues carbon instead of consuming it*” published in *L'Atlasenvironnement -Analyses et solution*, from Le Monde diplomatique

(18), the authors emphasize the fact that the capacity of forest vegetation to absorb carbon will attain the maximum threshold around the year 2050.

The reduction of biodiversity through the disappearance of new species. Nowadays, there are between 3 and 10 million species in the flora and fauna of the Earth, their diversity is an indicator of the ecological health of the Planet. Until the XXth century, few species were destroyed as a consequence of human activity, but, following this period of time, the number of destroyed species increased significantly. Some researchers from the field say that daily there are 3 species that disappear, the disappearance process being irreversible and compared by some scientists with „burning a library before its books are read”.

It was also mentioned that the extensive use of pesticides for herbs and insects harmful to the crops destroy in the same time a large number of useful species (bees), leading to the death or to the interruption of reproductive capacities of several birds. Controversial studies show that the pesticides affect the number of spermatozoids in humans (9),(17).

Desertification. The conversion of agricultural fields into deserts represents a very big issue, the fields for pastures were inadequately used in order to cultivate agricultural species. The tropical forests from Central and South America were eliminated and the clean fields were used as pastures for cows or for the culture of cereals or rice. The cutting of trees in these woods has lead to the interruption of hydrological cycle in the past 10 years the rainfall reduced and the soil’s humidity considerably decreased.

Demographic modifications as well as other relevant modifications cause and other factors make difficult finding a solution. From the demographic point of view, the increase of population and the number of inhabitants on km² represents an issue. If at the end of the XIXth century, on the Earth there were 2 billion people, today there are over 6 billion people, and by 2020, it is estimated that 8 billion people will coexist on the Earth. The population is concentrated in the largest cities, for the needs of which the water must be attracted from large distances, existing large consumers of domestic and drinkable water.

Environmental pollution. The pollution has different meanings and can be defined in many ways, a complex definition belonging to the Scientific Committee of the White House, after which the pollution is a defavourable modification of the natural environment, following the residues coming from human activity and which, through direct or indirect effects alters the life and diversity of alive species (10). The phenomenon is still insufficiently known from the point of view of the capacity to support the ecosystems and the effect of their polluting gas.

The thermal pollution of the atmosphere has an important meteorological meaning, being able to produce severe global climate disturbances if the thermal emissions will exceed 5% from the incidental solar energy to the ground. In agreement with the evolution of world climate and taking into account the violent disturbances in the past years, it is therefore necessary to preserve, by all means possible, the forest ecosystems on the globe, ensuring its necessary viability and stability, reducing its vulnerability by removing the aggressiveness of the polluting agents.

The pollution phenomena are manifesting in two ways. At the beginning, though a green pollution, caused by the invasion of weeds and a brown one, due to the invasion of diseases and pest to sensitive crops, in unfavourable conditions of humidity and heat. The economic loss caused by the brown pollution may sometimes lead to the complete disappearance of crops (during 1991 – 1998, in Romania, due to this, 20.000 ha of trees and 15.000 ha of vine disappeared (Berca, 2000). Another way of manifestation of pollution results from irrational use of pesticides. The pollution affects the vegetation in its vast majority, but the forest is the first component of biosphere affected by atmosphere impurities. In general, the wood species are simultaneously exposed to the mix of polluting agents, their dominant effect being, sometimes, bigger than the individual toxic effect, the mix having synergy effect.

Through the interaction of nitrogen oxides (resulting from the use of airplanes) with freons and with other gases which also produce green house effect, the ozone layer is destroyed. Thus, abnormal quantities of ozone (which exceeds its natural concentration), together with other toxic gases (resulting from burning fuels), determines the formation of photochemical smog (13).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We may ask if the changes in temperature and rainfall quantity which take place at the global level are due to natural phenomena (such as variability of solar activity or the effects of solar explosions) or are the result of the increase of green house effect. The temperature variations in the atmosphere might modify the structure of the troposphere with consequences in changing regional climate and with the modification of ozone concentration, determining increases in temperature on the Earth's surface, effects comparable to those given by the increases of carbon dioxide.

The deforestation, unavoidable phenomenon due to the fact that 60% from the planet's inhabitants use wood for fire, the industry being also a large consumer of wood. The destruction of woods causes global climate changes, reducing the capacity of the Earth to absorb carbon dioxide from the

atmosphere. In parallel to land clearings, the heating reduces the humidity, spreading the fires (the conjunction between El Nino and the increase of forest concessions). The fires from 1997 – 1998 lead to radiations of approximately 2,5 Gt. of carbon in the atmosphere, radiations equal to the annual European emissions (14).

Over the centuries, the water quantities which fell were more or less sufficient to cover the needs of agriculture. In the future, the issue of water will become more serious also due to the fact that in the future decades, the climate conditions risk to be modified (on a large part of the globe) by the increase of values of average temperature of the atmosphere. The destruction of species might have lethal consequences for humans, as well as for the other living beings. The climate changes are linked to a demographic explosion (the middle of the XXth century), which shows that the number of the population of the globe tripled, rising the fear that we will not be able to ensure its needs and that, in the future 30 years, the population of the globe will reach 8 billion inhabitants.

The atmosphere pollution might be regarded under three aspects: the role of meteorological factors on the phenomenon, its effect on the planet's chemism and the effects of pollution on the climate.

The cutting of trees in Sahara, which, 3000 years ago, was, at least in part covered with woods, lead rapidly to the conversion into desert. Similar processes took place in other regions on the globe, which has as consequence the reduction of potential to produce nourishment. A deserted field may become again rich, after several hundreds or thousands of years.

For our temperate climate, flighty and full of unwanted phenomena, we have to practice a forestry and an adequate agriculture, the corresponding means for existent technologies, in order to reduce unfavourable, biological and climate effects of the CO₂ from the atmosphere, possible through some drastic measures, out of which we mention here: the termination of land clearings from forest ecosystems, rational cultivation of all fields (agricultural, forest etc.) and conservation of forest fund still existent on Terra, measures mainly connected to the antropic factor.

CONCLUSIONS

The direct and indirect effects of global warming will be manifested, thus, in several general directions: - *modifications of vegetation*, the appearance of weeds which may become fatal for the ecosystem, in time; - *the increase of the level of seas and oceans* with approximately 50 cm in the year 2050, which might put in danger lots of ecosystems, especially by

an increase of salinity; - *weather abnormalities* manifested through tropical rains, storms, tornados, waves of heat, etc. With an impact on the entire biosystem and on all alive mechanisms; - *the appearance of diseases transmitted through vectors*, in some regions of the globe this phenomenon may lead to incidence, prevalence and, possibly, mortality; - *the food safety is threatened*, high temperatures will affect crops in some regions of the world, especially due to modifications of the rainfall regime and the soil's humidity; - *emphasis on the desertification*, due to the „green revolution” which lead to a dramatic increase of the agricultural production, especially in the past 40 years after the second world war; - *withdrawal of alpine glaciers* has as main cause the increase of green house gas concentration, phenomenon noticed for the first time in the XIXth century, leading to the withdrawal of river flows (used in irrigations and as drinkable water), which generated a real "water crisis” with consequences in the limitation of population increase in many regions from the globe.

Our society must adopt a practical attitude in solving the *environmental issues*, instead of the one adopted until now, a reactive attitude, taken each time when a crisis appears. An optimism reason might be the fact that the great majority of alive organisms from Terra are robust, powerful, which many times demonstrated the ability to adapt to a large scale of precarious weather conditions. Mankind enters into the largest crisis ever encountered, but the man is full of resources and in the best shape, even in crisis moments.

IPCC, in its report from 1995, approached *several options to diminish* these global modifications: non-polluting methods of transportation, reduction of gas emissions of human establishments, preservation of agricultural fields, policies and strategies of management of woods from the Earth, an efficient industry, so on.

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THE RELATIVE MOISTURE OF AIR IN THE CRIȘURI PLAIN

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Abstract

The goal of this paper is to present the multiannual regime of relative moisture in the Crișuri Plain area, as well as the monthly and annual regime of the relative moisture, the lowest monthly and annual values, the mean frequency of days with relative moisture $\leq 30\%$; $\leq 50\%$; $\geq 80\%$, based on data recorded at weather stations located in the area of the study (Salonta, Chișineu Criș, Săcueni and Oradea) from 1970 to 2017 (48 years).

Due to the influence of the wet climate from the west of the continent, the multiannual mean values of relative moisture are high in the area of Crișuri Plain. The relative moisture values vary between 75.3%, in Săcueni and 81.5% in Salonta.

The annual regime of relative moisture is characterized by higher values in winter, especially in December, due to the higher frequency of warm and wet air from the Mediterranean Sea, as compared with January, when the frequency of cold and dry air from the north and north-east increases.

Key words: frequency, monthly and annual regime, relative moisture

INTRODUCTION

Relative moisture is the ratio of the pressure of water vapours (e) to the saturation pressure (E). This value is of practical interest, as it shows the degree of saturation of an air volume with water vapours.

In the lower layer of the atmosphere, the relative moisture of air depends on the moisture degree of the subjacent surface, since the characteristics of the local evapotranspiration alter the character imposed by the general circulation of the atmosphere (Ciulache, 2002; Moza, 2009).

Relative moisture is in inverse correlation to air temperature and in direct correlation to atmospheric nebulosity, being influenced both by the particularities of the moving air masses and the local characteristics of the active surface (Gaceu, 2005; Pereș, 2012).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The characteristics of relative moisture in the Crișuri Plain area were studied using the data recorded at four weather stations: Salonta (95 m), Chișineu Criș (96 m), Săcueni (125 m) and Oradea (136 m). The data were recorded over a period of 48 years (1970-2017) at most of the weather

stations. The weather station in Salonta was closed, it was in operation from 1983 to 1998.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The monthly and annual regime of relative moisture

The relative moisture of air in the area included in the study shows relatively high values, which is due to the influence of the wet climate from the west of the continent.

Within the area of Crişuri Plain the annual mean values give close multiannual mean values, with 75.3% in Săcueni and 81.5% in Salonta (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Distribution of air relative moisture multiannual mean values (%) in the Crişuri Plain

In the period included in the study (1970-2017), in Oradea the annual mean values of relative moisture varied between 69% in 2007 and 2009, and 84% in 1985 and 2001 (Fig. 2). The highest monthly mean values were recorded in January and December, that is, 97% in January 1989 and 95%, in December 1998. In Oradea, the lowest monthly means occurred in April and August. Thus, in April 2007 46%, while in August 2003 47%.

Fig. 2. Relative moisture annual values in Oradea, 1970-2017

In Săcueni, the annual mean values of relative moisture varied between 68% in 2008 and 82% in 1980, 1985, 1988 and 2001 (Fig. 3).

Over the 48 years included in the study, in Săcueni the highest monthly mean values were recorded in January and December, with 96% in January 1989 and 94% in December 1984. The lowest monthly mean values of relative moisture were recorded in April 2009, 46%, and in June 2000, 50%.

Fig. 3. Relative moisture annual values in Săcueni, 1970-2017

The annual mean values show deviations from the multiannual mean, which is due to the general circulation of the atmosphere, physical geographical factors etc.

The highest positive deviations recorded in the area of the study during the 48 years occurred in Oradea, 54.2%, while in Săcueni the percentage of positive deviations is 45.8%.

The highest negative deviations occur in Săcueni, 54.2%, while in Oradea the figure is 45.8% (Fig. 4, 5).

Fig. 4. Air moisture annual deviations from the multiannual mean in Oradea, 1970 – 2017

Fig. 5. Air moisture annual deviations from the multiannual mean in Săcuieni, 1970 – 2017

The relative moisture values of air are influenced by the evolution of the air temperature, thus, in winter, when air temperature has the lowest values, relative moisture shows the highest values, while in summer things happen the other way around.

Looking at the annual regime of relative moisture, it can be seen that it is characterized by higher values in winter, especially in December, for example, 92.9% in Salonta, 90% in Chişineu Criş, 87.9% in Oradea, and in Săcueni 86.2%. Higher moisture in December can be explained by the higher frequency of warm and humid air from the Mediterranean Sea, as compared with January, when the frequency of cold and dry air from the north and north-east increases due to the East-European, Siberian or Scandinavian Anticyclone (Gaceu O., 2005; Pereş A. C., 2012).

Fig. 6. Distribution of air relative moisture monthly mean values (%) in the Crişuri Plain

The lowest values of relative moisture occur in the warm season of the year, with minimums recorded in April and July, with the highest frequency in July. Thus, in the Crişuri Plain, the lowest values of multiannual mean of relative moisture vary between 68.2% in Săcueni and Oradea in April and July, and 73.1% in Salonta in July (Fig. 6).

The monthly pattern of relative moisture is in inverse correlation to air temperature, thus, the highest values of relative moisture are recorded in

winter months (December, January), when the temperatures are the lowest within the year (Table 1).

Table 1

Monthly pattern of relative moisture and monthly mean temperature in the Crişuri Plain

Month/station		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	An
Salonta	Rh%	91.4	86.4	79.3	75.6	75.3	75.9	73.1	74.5	80.2	83.5	89.6	92.9	81.5
	Temp.	-0.8	0.3	4.9	10.9	16.3	19.1	21.5	20.9	15.9	10.5	4.4	0.1	10.3
Chişineu Criş	Rh%	89	86	79	74	73	73	71	72	77	81	87	90	79.3
	Temp.	-1.4	-0.1	5.2	10.3	16.1	19.1	20.9	20.4	15.9	10.3	4.3	0.8	10.2
Săcueni	Rh%	85.1	81.4	72.8	68.2	68.6	69.5	69.2	69.9	73.4	77.2	83.0	86.2	75.3
	Temp.	-0.9	0.9	5.8	11.3	16.6	19.7	21.4	20.8	16.1	10.6	5.2	0.6	10.7
Oradea	Rh%	87.5	83.2	74.8	69.5	70.5	70.9	68.2	69.7	74.8	79.5	84.2	87.9	76.7
	Temp.	-0.8	0.9	5.6	11.0	16.4	19.5	21.4	20.9	16.2	10.7	5.2	0.8	10.7

Source: data provided by National Meteorological Administration archive (A.N.M. Bucharest)

The monthly and annual minimum of relative moisture

Looking at the evolution of the monthly minimum of relative moisture in the period 1970-2017 in the area of the study, it can be seen that the minimum values are recorded in the warm period of the year, thus, the absolute minimum value was recorded in Săcueni, 6%, on 20.04.2009, while in Oradea the absolute minimum was 14%, on 20.07.2007 (Table 2).

Table 2

Monthly minimum values of relative moisture in the Crişuri Plain, 1970 – 2017

Month/station	Month	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Annual
Săcueni	Rh%	15	16	11	6	13	18	14	15	14	13	14	28	6
	Date	29.12	14.94	03.12	20.09	02.07 02.15	05.00 21.00	20.07 20.15	23.07 31.12 23.15	21.11	01.11	25.93	10.11	20.04.2009
Oradea	Rh%	27	28	18	15	16	15	14	15	15	23	25	27	14
	Date	01.73	14.94	26.03 15.12	07.05 22.07 28.09	03.07 18.09	14.09	20.07	31.12	01.12	16.07 03.11	14.70 05.97 05.11	28.72	20.07.2007

Source: data provided by the A.N.M. Archive

The absolute minimums of air moisture resulting from lack of precipitations over a period of 10-15 days can lead to the phenomena of dryness and atmospheric drought.

The mean frequency of days with relative moisture $\leq 30\%$; $\leq 50\%$; $\geq 80\%$

The annual mean number of days with relative moisture $\leq 30\%$ (dry days) and $\geq 80\%$ (humid days) is of important practical interest, thus, the number of days with relative moisture $\leq 30\%$ is considered an indicator of

dry weather, while the number of days with relative moisture $\geq 80\%$ is considered an indicator of humid weather (Pereş A. C., 2012).

The frequency of days with various characteristics of relative moisture shows both a spatial and a temporal variation. The annual mean number of days with very low relative moisture of air, with values $\leq 30\%$ at any time of data collection, varies in the area of the study between 9.4 days in Săcueni and 9.6 days in Oradea.

Over the year, the monthly mean frequency of days with moisture $\leq 30\%$ varies from one region to another depending on geographical conditions. The frequency of these days shows higher values in summer and spring, thus in Oradea the number is 1.7 days in April and 1.6 days in July, and in Săcueni 1.6 days in July (Fig. 7). The higher values in April are the result of temperature increasing as against the previous months, of the frequent presence of the anticyclonic regime, which generates dry weather, but also of the higher frequency of days with warm and dry wind. The same weather characteristics also determine the higher number of days on which relative moisture of air reaches or goes below 30% in summer months, to which the high temperatures of the warm season of the year are also added (Măhăra Gh. et al., 2002; Dumiter A., 2007).

Relative moisture $\leq 30\%$ is least frequent in winter, in December – January (0.0 – 0.1 days).

Fig. 7. Distribution of relative moisture monthly mean values $\leq 30\%$ in the Crişuri Plain

The annual mean number of days with relative moisture $\leq 50\%$ at least at one of the data collection times is 115.8 days in Oradea and Săcueni.

Fig. 8. Distribution of relative moisture monthly mean values $\leq 50\%$, in the Crişuri Plain

The monthly mean frequency of days with relative moisture $\leq 50\%$ shows highest values April, thus, there are 15.8 such days in Săcueni and 15.6 in Oradea. The lowest monthly means in the area of the study occur in December, that is, 2.0 days in Oradea and 2.1 days in Săcueni (Fig. 8).

The annual frequency of days with relative moisture $\geq 80\%$ at noon (the time of highest temperature) is 89.8 days in Săcueni and 91.1 days in Oradea, values which show the influence of the humid climate from the west and south-west of the continent, which is felt in the western part of the country.

Fig. 9. Distribution of relative moisture monthly mean values $\geq 80\%$, in the Crișuri Plain

The monthly mean number of days with relative moisture $\geq 80\%$ reaches a maximum in December, thus, there are 19.7 such days in Săcueni and 19.9 in Oradea. The relative moisture values are higher in winter, as the temperatures are lower and the advection of the humid Mediterranean air is more frequent. The minimum values are recorded in the summer months (July and August), thus, there are: 2.3 days in Oradea and 2.2 days in Săcueni (Fig. 9). The values are lower in the summer, as the air mean temperatures are higher.

The high number of days on which relative moisture reaches and goes beyond 80% is determined by the geographical location of Oradea in the western part of the country, where the influences of the humid climate from the western and south-western part of the European continent is stronger than in other parts of the country (Dumiter, 2007; Köteles, Moza A, 2010; Pereș, Köteles, 2014).

High value relative moisture, as well as the high number of days when it is recorded, is a risk factor for the population, especially in the cold season, when high moisture is accompanied by low temperatures, which leads to the persistence in the atmospheric air of the city of high amounts of pollutants coming from the industrial zone or from the traffic (Erhan, 1979, cited by Dumiter, 2007; Pereș, 2011).

CONCLUSIONS

Due to the influence of wet climate, in the Crişuri Plain area the multiannual values of relative moisture are relatively high, with values between 75.3% in Săcueni and 81.5% in Salonta. The positive deviations from the multiannual mean in Oradea and Săcueni were 54.2% and 45.8%, respectively. The negative deviations varied between 54.2% in Săcueni and 45.8% in Oradea.

The annual regime of relative moisture is characterized by higher values in winter, especially in December (92.9% in Salonta, 90% in Chişineu Criş, 87.9% in Oradea, and in Săcueni 86.2%), due to the higher frequency of warm and humid air from the Mediterranean Sea, as compared with January, when the frequency of cold and wet air from the north and north-east increases. The lowest values of relative moisture occur in the warm period of the year, especially in July.

The absolute minimum relative moisture was recorded in Săcueni, the value of 6%, on 20.04.2009, followed by Oradea, with 14%, on 20.07.2007.

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STUDY ON THE DIVERSITY OF THE SPONTANEOUS FLOWER IN THE PĂDUREA CRAIULUI MOUNTAINS

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Abstract

The present paper is based on the studies carried out both in the field in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains and on the studies carried out by the researchers, regarding the spontaneous flora. The mountain meadows of the Pădurea Craiului Mountains are highlighted by a high floristic diversity, over 1500 species of plants being identified so far. The inversions of vegetation, the floral diversity, the existence of caves, largely accessible to man, create unique mountain landscapes in the country and even in the world.

Due to the floristic variety, the Pădurea Craiului Mountains have a special interest regarding the use of spontaneous flora in the treatment of certain conditions. This is why a detailed study of the different species of plants is required.

Key words: massive, spontaneous flora, climate, forest

INTRODUCTION

The area under study is geographically framed by Valea Crișului Repede (Vad-Borod Depression), in its northern part until Valea Crișului Negru (Beiușului depression), in the south and are bordered by the western hills (Tășadului Hills), in the west and Iada and Meziad valleys (Vlădeasa Massif), in its eastern part. The highest peak in the massif is Hodrâncușa with 1027 m, located in the eastern part, after which, to the west, it drops to 400 m, near Vârciorog. From a geomorphological point of view, they are made of mesozoic limestone (83%). Crystalline shale predominates, subhercinic and laramic magmatites, some conglomerates and Permian sandstone. It is a karst relief that alternates with the uncharacteristic ones. The exocarst belongs to deep dolines of 5-60 m, then pits and karst depressions. The Craiului Forest occupies about 15.2% of the surface of Bihor county, being located in the central-eastern part of the county, with an area of about 1152 square kilometers.

The annual average temperatures are around 6 - 8 degrees C in the higher central part, after which they increase to the periphery, reaching 8 - 9 degrees C. Precipitation increases from 700 mm / year in the western part to 1000 mm / year in their eastern part (Brejea, 2017).

Fig. 1. The Pădurea Craiului Mountains (Pop A., 2018)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study was conducted in the northwestern part of the Piatra Craiului massif, but it also contains general data about these mountains. Most of the Pădurea Craiului Mountains are covered by deciduous forests. Within the deciduous forests, spruce patches appear, interrupted by broad meadows on the karst plateaus. The exception is the spruce forest on the karst plateau at Scalvul Pleș (above the Luncasprie Valley). Beech (*fagus silvatica*) it predominates in the deciduous forests, followed by gorun (*quercus sessiflora*), wild chestnut (*castanea sativa*), birch (*betula avellanca*), banana (*acer pseudoplantatus*) and cherry (*cerasus avium*). Among the shrubs we find the hazelnut (*corylus avellanca*), the horn (*cornu mas*), the pigeon with barbs (*prunus spinosa*). The tufts of sandstone are

covered by large-leaved ferns, in the marshy areas the burns (*arctium lappa*) develop, and in the fields we find daisies (*chrysanthemum leucantemum*), chicory, bells, raspberries and blackberries. The mushrooms are not missing: yolks, ears, beetles and pitons. On the slopes of the hills we find plants such as snowdrops (*Galanthus*), violins (*scilla bifolia*) and hawks (crocus), plants known as spring heralds. Beech forests are decorated with ivory (*allium ursinum*), a plant used for salads. The leaves of leprosy contain allyl sulphide, which imprints the taste and smell characteristic of all species of the genus *Allium*, carotenoids, vitamins A and C, vitamins of complex B, levulose, complex ethereal oil, mineral salts, calcium, iron, phosphorus, sodium, magnesium, copper and protein.

As a peculiarity of the karst plateaus of The Pădurea Craiului mountains, as a result of the thermal inversions, there are areas where the floor of the conifers disappears completely being replaced by beech forests (*fagus silvatica*) that are directly adjacent to the mountain meadows. The boundary between deciduous and softwood forests lies between altitudes of 600 -1300 m, depending on the relief, substrate and microclimate that sometimes lead to vegetation inversions (Brejea R; 2017).

The spontaneous flora of the Pădurea Craiului Mountains presents a great variety of trees, plants and flowers, interesting associations of plants such as the wild stingray (*Iris sybirica* - glacier relic) and Martaloaga (*Calluna vulgaris*), flowers belonging to the mountain floor. In addition to these there are also the juniper (*Pirus mugo*), the blueberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus*) and the blueberry (*Vaccinium vitis-idaea*). The floor of the conifers is around the altitude of 1000 m, with the dominant element being the spruce (*Picea excelsa*), the fir (*Abies alba*), less frequently the mountain hawthorn (*Acer pseudoplatanus*), the scorus (*Sorbus aucuparia*) and the very rare thistle (*Taxus baccata*). The beech floor (*Fagus silvatica*) runs between 600 - 1,000 m altitude, it holds 52.76% of the total wood mass being the dominant element. We also meet the gorun (*Quercus campestris*), the ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*), the peanut (*Corylus avellana*). On the cold valleys we find the Carpathian bat (*Syringa josikaca*) glacier, endemic species, and mountain bulb (*Trollius europaeus*), protected plant. The oak floor extends from the plain area to an altitude of about 500 m. Here pure or mixed forests of peduncular oak (*Quercus robur*), gnita (*Q. Farineta*) together with the Tartar maple (*Acer tataricum*), lime (*Tilia parvifolia*) occur.) to At the foot of the mountains we can also find dogwood (*Ligustrum vulgaris*) and woody wood (*Eronimus verrucosa*). There is also no glitch (*Rosa canina*) or hawthorn, goat's pike in the popular name (*Crataegus monogyna*). After the closure of the bauxite exploitations in this area, the villages became depopulated, the population aged, and the agricultural lands cultivated with potato, wheat, rye, were filled with shrubs and berries. Areas with hay,

agricultural crops and colorful meadows we meet in the localities: Tomnatic, Zece Hotare, Ponoare, Damiş și Călățea.

Fig. 2. Chicera - Tomnatic 2019

However, the same area has not escaped the illegal deforestation. According to the data provided by the National Directorate of the Romsilva Forests, on the territory of the Pădurea Craiului Mountains, there are 4 forest sites: the Aleșd Forest District, the Beiuș Forest District, the Dobrești Forest District and the Remeți Forest District. They manage a total area of 51378 ha, divided according to the table below, where both the surfaces of these oak trees are presented as well as the composition of the wood material that is part of respective area rounded to them.

Table 1

The surface of the forests within the Forest District of the Pădurea Craiului Mountains

Crt. No	Forest District	Aleșd	Beiuș	Dobrești	Remeți
1	Surface	16307 ha	14182 ha	9437 ha	11452 ha
2	Fagus sylvatica	54,5%	66%	54%	36,53%
3	Various hard sp.	16,6%	18%	9%	1,62%
4	Quercus petraea	11,3%	5%	9%	-
5	Quercus cerris	6,8%	2%	5%	-
6	Picea abies	3,7%	5%	5%	47,83%
7	Pinus sylvestris	2,9%	-	-	-
8	Pseudotsuga menziesii	2,5%	-	-	0,54%
9	Various soft sp.	1,2%	2%	2%	0,09%
10	Larix sp.	0,5%	-	-	-
11	Abies sp.	-	-	-	13,39%
12	Quercus robur	-	2%	1%	-

Within the spontaneous flora as curiosities we mention:

- Painted tulip -Fritillaria meleagris, a plant of the family Liliaceae related to tulip. We find it in the Crișului Repede parade, we find dark, white and black-purple specimens. It has no pleasant smell.

Fig. 3. Painted tulip - Vadu Crișului 2019

-Thorn (*Ruscus aculeatus*) is a dioecious plant, the male and female flowers being produced on separate plants (of the same species). The flowers are small, white, and from the female ones, in October, the fruits form like red, glossy balls, which last until March.

Fig. 4. Thorn - Tomnatic 2018

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analyzing the data in Table 1. we conclude that of the total forests, beech is the most widespread species, occupying 52.76% of the total, followed by spruce with a percentage of 15.38% and gorun with a percentage of 6.325%. The remaining 25.53% being represented by the other existing species, but not representing, each taking a considerable percentage. After forests as a stretch follow the meadows and meadows as occupied surface The beauty of the places is given between the contrast between the secular forests, placed on the obvious karsts and the rich and colorful spontaneous flora.

CONCLUSIONS

The Pădurea Craiului mountains occupy the subalpine floor, the species participating in the vegetation composition are mostly species with mountain spread. The deciduous forests alternate with those of conifers, with brightly colored meadows and meadows. The spontaneous flora of the Pădurea Craiului Mountains represents a natural wealth, untapped at its true value. While in the depressed area of Beiuşului whole communities live, from harvesting, processing and marketing of plants of spontaneous flora, in Craiului Forest, medicinal plants, although present in all spontaneous flora, are processed only for personal consumption, in the largest part of the inhabitants of this area.

As a conclusion we can say that, due to the rich diversity of spontaneous flora in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains, it is necessary to take measures to protect the rare species, which can be achieved through an ecological education of both locals and tourists.

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THE INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE AND OF THE STORAGE LIFE ON THE CHINESE CABBAGE

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Abstract

The analysis regarding the influence of temperature and of the storage period on the functional quality of the Chinese cabbage is argued in this study by the importance of minimizing the loss of nutritious compounds during the period of storage. In order to ensure a certain frequency in consumption, these functional nutrients that play an important role on the processes of degradation of the health of the human body can be preserved for periods as long as possible at values very close to the values from the moment of harvesting. Functional nutrients act on reactive oxygen species, reduce angiogenesis and the inflammatory process, being considered chemopreventive agents.

Temperature and storage period are environmental factors with significant impact on preserving the high nutritional value of the Brassicaceae vegetables for fresh consumption. In order to preserve their dietary and therapeutic qualities, it is necessary to run a prospective analysis of the storage conditions so these products be present in consumption for as long as possible. The analysis of the most advantageous storage methods that try to reduce losses led to the observation that food quality assurance and product certification are of great importance. Thus, useful information can be obtained on the content of vitamins, minerals, antioxidants and glucosinolates found in larger quantities in cruciferous vegetables. These environmental factors are influenced by the morphological, biological and productive particularities of the species of different origins, cultivated in the pedoclimatic conditions specific to each area. Establishing the temperature range and the storage period in order to reduce the level of several functional components in the Chinese cabbage has led to encouraging results according to which the Chinese cabbage can be stored in the homemade system at temperatures of 2-8°C for a period long enough to meet consumption demands.

The research on the storage conditions provides valuable information for prospective studies on optimizing the storage of the highest amount of functional components such as glucosinolates and vitamin C in Brassicaceae vegetables, including the Chinese cabbage.

Key words: functional components, Chinese cabbage, storage temperature

INTRODUCTION

A great emphasis has been placed lately on the consumption of vegetables and fruit based on their functional character that plays an important role in nutrition and in maintaining and/or improving health. Being safe sources of vitamins and minerals, they protect the body from various disorders and diseases (Apahidean et al., 2000). When a type of food is recommended in a diet, it is important to know its functional

properties of improving at least one function of the organism. This happens thanks to the content in biologically active compounds which positively affects one or more target functions of the organism, enhancing the health status, reducing the risk of a disease, thus improving the quality of life (Bei et al., 2018).

Based on the strong functional properties against reactive oxygen species, many studies show that the Chinese cabbage is a good adjuvant in reducing the degree of body damage (Fenwick and Heaney, 1983; Akpolat and Barringer, 2015). Vegetables in the cabbage group are growing in popularity thanks to their anticancer, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Cartea et al., 2011).

The nutrients that are so varied and rich in the Brassicaceae group of vegetables depend on many factors such as diversity, harvesting period, keeping and storage conditions, processing and cooking conditions, the environment they grow in. These vegetables have a low content of fat and a high content of vitamins, especially vitamin C and E, carotenoids, minerals, fibres, but also of phytochemicals and antioxidant enzymes such as catalase, superoxide dismutase (SOD) and peroxidase which are mainly found in fresh vegetables (Cartea et al., 2011; Gupta, 2011; Tan et al., 2010). In addition to these nutrients, foods in the cabbage group also contain glucosinolates with sulphur, anthocyanins, flavonoids, terpenes, S-methylcysteine sulfoxide, coumarins and other compounds.

The shredding or the chewing of the cabbage species generate bioactive glucosinolate hydrolysis products such as isothiocyanates that are capable of modifying redox processes at the cellular level (Herr and Büchler, 2010; Ranjan et al., 2015) and indol-3-carbinol, a chemopreventive agent that inhibits the proliferation and increases tumour cell apoptosis, inhibiting inflammation and angiogenesis (Alliegro, 2007).

In the acid environment of the stomach, indol-3-carbinol is rapidly converted by extensive and rapid self-condensation into 3,3'-diindolylmethane which is formed from the dimerization of two molecules of indole-3-carbinol. 3,3'-diindolylmethane has inhibitory effect on the activity of HDAC isoenzymes, a class of target proteins with key mediating effect of cellular signals. Decreased HDAC expression was accompanied by increased expression of B-cell lymphoma (pro-apoptotic Bcl-2) which, associated with X (Bax) protein and CDKNs p21 and p27, led to cell cycle arrest and increased rate of apoptosis (Schnekenburger and Diederich, 2015).

Besides affecting the expression of the HDAC mediator, indol-3-carbinol treatments prevent alterations of miRNA gene transcripts that regulate at least 30% of the protein-encoding genes, effects observed in rodent tests following exposure to cigarette smoke or in chemically induced

tumourigenesis (Robert and Farrell, 2017). Interestingly, indol-3-carbinol sensitizes gemcitabine-resistant pancreatic cancer cells by regulating miR-21, a key regulator of cell proliferation and apoptosis in various cancer models (Begum et al., 2017).

Glucosinolate is present in relatively high concentrations in these vegetables, but the bioavailability of the isothiocyanate can be reduced by cooking, especially by boiling and microwaving. Glucosinolate metabolites can reduce oxidative stress, limiting metastasis, inflammation, endothelial dysfunction and cardiomyocyte death (Jang M, Cho, 2016; Carrasco-Pozo et al., 2017) with beneficial effects on the cardiovascular system. In order to increase the bioavailability of isothiocyanate in the diet, one must pay attention to the cooking method since these vegetables should be steamed and less cooked so that the glucosinolate content be preserved. It is recommended that these cruciferous vegetables be consumed as soon as possible if they are cut.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The biological material analysed consisted of the varieties of Granat Chinese cabbage - scientifically called *Brassica pekinensis* and Vitimo F1 hybrid obtained from an organic vegetable micro-farm and from the supermarket - the conventional sample.

Determining the nutritional quality of the Chinese cabbage requires several determinations regarding:

1. the content in vitamin C, for the role of this vitamin in preserving food quality and for certain storage periods, for the antioxidant properties on the reactive oxygen species.
2. the content of nitrites in order to reduce the risk of transformation into nitrosamines following digestion and metabolism, with increased risk of gastrointestinal cancer in adults.

The determination of the content of vitamin C, glucosinolates and nitrites was carried out every 10 days over a 3-month storage period under controlled temperature conditions at 2-4°C compared to 8-10°C in both variants, the organic sample and the conventional sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Food quality can be affected and influenced by internal factors that refer to the products' chemical composition, biological and physical properties and by external factors that refer to the composition of the atmospheric air, air temperature and humidity, sunshine duration, chemical fertilizers on crop plants, mechanical stress during product handling.

According to the European Union and to the World Health Organization, food safety is a shared responsibility of all actors involved, from food production until it reaches consumers' tables.

Because the domestic production of Chinese cabbage is deficient especially in summer, but also in spring and autumn which are the favourable seasons for its culture, this study tried to determine the best storage conditions for the Chinese cabbage in case of low temperature, with minimum loss of nutrients over long periods of up to 30 days.

Proper storage conditions and techniques are needed to preserve the quality of agricultural and food products as the active trade in agricultural products currently results in long distribution period.

Table 1

Vitamin C content (mg / 100g f.p.) after 10 days of storage at temperatures of 2-4°C compared to storage at 8-10°C

Variety / Hybrid	Vitamin C content before storage at low temperatures (mg/100g p.p)		Vitamin C content after 10 days of storage at temperatures of 2-4°C (mg/100g p.p)		Vitamin C content after 10 days of storage at temperatures of 8-10°C (mg/100g p.p)	
	organic sample	conventional sample	organic sample	conventional sample	organic sample	conventional sample
Granat-variety <i>pekinensis</i>	45.76	41.69	44.12	40.24	42.86	38.87
Vitimo F1	49.84	43.24	47.92	41.73	45.19	40.35
Mean	47.8	42.46	46.02	40.98	44.02	39.61

Table 1 shows the influence of storage temperatures on the content of vitamin C. The levels of vitamin C in the Chinese cabbage stored at temperatures of 2-4°C decreased more slowly compared to the levels of vitamin C in the Chinese cabbage stored at temperatures of 8-10°C after a period of 10 days (table 1). It is considered that the low temperatures in the storage facilities have beneficial effects on the quality of the Chinese cabbage thanks to the inhibited enzymatic activity that leads to the limited degradation of vitamin C, degradation that can be influenced by the harvest season.

The loss of vitamin C in the organic sample stored at temperatures of 8-10°C after 10 days was 2.96% higher than the loss of vitamin C in the organic sample stored at temperatures of 2-4°C. The loss of vitamin C in the conventional sample was 3.31% higher when stored at temperatures of 8-10°C than when stored at temperatures of 2-4°C (table 1). For both samples, the organic one and the conventional one, the decrease of the content of vitamin C after a storage period of 10 days is greater when stored at temperatures of 8-10°C than when stored at temperatures of 2-4°C (table 1).

Chinese cabbage harvested in summer is more difficult to store in warehouses for more than a month due to high temperatures and humidity that lead to the degradation of its functional quality and to weight loss (Bae et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2001). Therefore, maintaining proper storage parameters such as air composition in the storage space, temperature and humidity is essential to prevent quality degradation (Kim et al., 2010, Eum et al., 2013a, Kim et al., 1998). Physicochemical indices such as colour, firmness, sugar content, weight and flavour represent qualitative parameters used to assess the functional food quality of the Chinese cabbage.

Table 2

Vitamin C content after 30 days of storage at temperatures of 2-4°C compared to storage at 8-10°C

Variety / Hybrid	Vitamin C content before storage at low temperatures (mg/100 g p.p.)		Vitamin C content after 30 days of storage at temperatures of 2-4°C (mg/100 g p.p.)		Vitamin C content after 30 days of storage at temperatures of 8-10°C (mg/100 g p.p.)	
	organic sample	conventional sample	organic sample	conventional sample	organic sample	conventional sample
Granat variety <i>pekinensis</i>	45.76	41.69	40.52	36.45	38.63	35.41
Vitimo F1	49.84	43.24	44.29	37.96	41.37	36.79
Mean	47.8	42.46	42.4	37.24	40	35.1

Table 2 shows that, after being stored in the refrigerator at temperatures of 2-4°C, the vitamin C content in the organic sample decreased on average from 47.8 mg/100g FP to 42.40 mg/100g FP. Thus, the loss of vitamin C after a 30-day storage period was of 5.40 mg/100g FP, that means a percentage of 11.29%. Chinese cabbage can be stored for a period of up to 90 days at temperatures of 2-4°C, specifying that vitamin C loss can reach up to 45% of the total.

At temperatures of 8-10°C, the loss of vitamin C in the organic sample after 30 days of storage in the refrigerator was on average 7.80 mg/100 g FP, that means a percentage of 16.31%.

The recorded data shows that the loss of vitamin C in the conventional sample that was stored for 30 days in the refrigerator at temperatures of 2-4°C decreased on average from 42.46 mg/100 g FP to 37.24 mg/100 g FP. The loss of vitamin C after a period of 30 days was of 5.22 mg/100 g FP, that means a percentage of 12.29%.

The amount of Vitamin C in the conventional sample that was stored in the refrigerator for a period of 30 days at temperatures of 8-10°C decreased by 6.28 mg/100g FP compared to the moment before storing in the refrigerator, that means a percentage of 15.06%.

Specialised literature has published several studies on the effects of storage temperature on weight variation and nutrient loss (Klieber et al., 2002; Eum et al., 2013b). It has been repeatedly analysed how changes in pH, storage period, temperature and concentration in vitamin C affect the colour of the red cabbage (Tomczak and Czapski, 2007; Devahastin and Niamnuy, 2010). These studies have recently been motivated by the content of abundant functional components with anti-carcinogenic effect and properties in the carotenoids and glucosinolates present in the vegetables from the cabbage group and which are unique functional components for Brassicaceae (Jahangir et al., 2009; Akpolat and Barringer, 2015).

Nitrate, especially from green leafy vegetables, can be converted to nitrite (NO₂) by the oral commensal bacteria under the tongue or in the stomach which is then converted to nitric oxide (NO) by non-enzymatic synthesis. For the academic community, the determination of the nitrogen content in vegetables is of great importance due to human safety controversies regarding nitrates and nitrites in the diet (Sindelaar, 2012), such as “dietary nitrate - good or bad?” (Gilchrist, 2010) or “harmful or nurturing?” (Weightman, 2013).

Determinations regarding the nitrite content in two varieties of Chinese cabbage obtained in different culture systems, organic and conventional, revealed significant differences between the experimental variants (Table 3). The content of nitrites in the organic sample of Chinese cabbage was on average between 1.93 mg/kg in the Granat variety and 1.84 mg/kg in the Vitimo F1. The content in nitrites in the conventional sample was of 2.79 mg/kg in the Granat variety and of 2.80 mg/kg in the Vitimo F1 hybrid.

Table 3

Nitrite content after 10 days of storage at temperatures of 2-4°C compared to temperatures of 8-10°C

Variety/ Hybrid	Nitrate content before storage at low temperatures (mg/kg FP)		Nitrate content after 10 days of storage at temperatures of 2-4°C (mg/kg FP)		Nitrate content after 10 days of storage at temperatures of 8-10°C (mg/kg FP)	
	organic sample	conventional sample	organic sample	conventional sample	organic sample	conventional sample
Granat variety <i>pekinensis</i>	2.49	2.65	1.93	2.79	2.82	3.97
Vitimo F1	2.38	2.57	1.84	2.8	2.67	3.58
Mean	2.44	2.61	1.89	2.8	2.75	3.78

After 10 days in the refrigerator at 2-4°C, the average nitrite content was 1.885 mg/kg in the organic sample and 2.795 mg/kg in the conventional

one. After 10 days in the refrigerator at 8-10°C, the average nitrate content increased considerably in both samples, reaching 2.745 mg/kg in the organic sample and 3.775 mg/kg in the conventional one.

The average nitrite content in the Chinese cabbage samples after 30 days of storage at 8-10°C recorded values of 3.83 mg/kg in the conventional sample and of 3.415 in the organic sample.

Table 4

Nitrite content after 30 days of storage at temperatures of 2-4°C compared to temperatures of 8-10°C

Variety/ Hybrid	Nitrate content before storage at low temperatures (mg/kg FP)		Nitrate content after 30 days of storage at temperatures of 2-4°C (mg/kg FP)		Nitrate content after 30 days of storage at temperatures of 8-10°C (mg/kg FP)	
	organic sample	conventional sample	organic sample	conventional sample	organic sample	conventional sample
Granat variety <i>pekinensis</i>	2.49	2.65	2.63	2.87	3.58	3.92
Vitimo F1	2.38	2.57	2.49	2.99	3.25	3.74
Mean	2.44	2.61	2.56	2.93	3.42	3.83

CONCLUSIONS

1. The content of vitamin C in both samples, the organic and the conventional one, decreased in a greater proportion when stored at 8-10°C than when stored at 2-4°C for a period of 30 days.

2. The level of nutrients in the Chinese cabbage decreased during storage. However, nutrient reduction rates could be minimized by lowering storage temperatures and by controlling atmosphere conditions.

3. It is important to preserve the nutritional and functional quality of the Chinese cabbage because of the requirements for suitable long-term storage conditions at low temperatures and for maintaining its functional components that are important to human health.

4. The analysis of the influence of temperature and of storage period on the content of nitrites in Chinese cabbage at temperatures of 2-4°C after a storage period of 30 days revealed that the average content in nitrites in the conventional sample was higher than in the organic one, being of 2.93 mg/kg, respectively of 2.56 mg/kg.

5. The nitrite content was on average higher in the conventional samples compared to the organic ones for both temperature variables after a storage period of 30 days in the refrigerator.

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THE MORPHO-ANATOMIC COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TWO SPECIES IN THE MALVACEAE FAMILY

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Abstract

This paper provides information on the species *Althaea officinalis* L. and *Malva sylvestris* L. from the spontaneous flora of Bihor County. Species analysis *Althaea officinalis* L. and *Malva sylvestris* L., began with the collection of samples and their macroscopic characterization of botanical identity for each species. To carry out the experimental part, they were harvested from the spontaneous flora of Bihor County, from different unpolluted areas. The plants were harvested during dry weather, during flowering, in May. The macroscopic study was performed according to FR. X., by establishing the morphological characters of the harvested species, observed with the naked eye, or with the magnifying glass, as well as those that can be determined by the perception of the smell and taste.

Key words: *Althaea officinalis*, *Malva sylvestris*, microscopic control, mucilages

INTRODUCTION

The Malvaceae family, known as the Nalbei family, comprises about 1500 species of grass and woody plants, of which the large nalba (*Althaea officinalis* L.), and the forest nalba (*Malva sylvestris* L.). Are spontaneous species growing in various ecosystems, used in pharmaceutical practice, due to their content in mucilages (Gîtea et al, 2011, Gîtea, 2015). Mucilages act on two planes, reduce inflammation and irritation of the entire digestive tract, reduce sensitivity to gastric acid, prevent diarrhea and reduce peristalsis, but also act on the respiratory system, decreasing tension and coughing and increasing the secretion of aqueous mucus.

Althaea officinalis L. and *Malva sylvestris* L. can be found on the market of food supplements in various pharmaceutical forms (Sîrbu et al, 2013). They mostly contain a combination of moth and other plants with complementary action, depending on the benefits sought. The medicinal plant product is represented by: *Althaeae officinalis folium*, *Althaeae officinalis radix*, *Malvae folium*, *Malvae radix*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Althaea officinalis L. and *Malva sylvestris* L. species from the spontaneous flora of Bihor County were identified and harvested from

different unpolluted areas. The plants were harvested during dry weather, during flowering, in May 2019. Macro and microscopic control was performed (Paşca B. et al, 2016, Pallag A. et al, 2014).

The microscopic control of the plant products was accompanied by a chemical control, which shows under the microscope, following color reactions, certain chemical constituents in the cells, in order to identify the plant products. According to FRX. the mucilages are identified as follows: To 20-30 mg sprayed vegetable product add 0.5 ml methylene blue solution (R); mucilages appear under a blue-violet microscope.

The dyes used were: the reagents used in the microchemical control as well as the Genevez reagent (Congo red + chrysidine) and malachite green. The research has identified the presence of mucilages in the root, stem and leaf (Şipoş, 2004).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the cross-section on the root can be observed under the microscope the bark of both species *Althaea officinalis* L. and *Malva sylvestris* Ls showed cells with a high content of mucilages, colored in blue in the presence of methylene blue, or in yellow-orange in the presence of Genevez's reagent.

Fig. 1. *Althaea officinalis* L. - cross section through the root colored with methylene blue (ob.10x, 40x)(a = exoderm, b = bark, c = cortical parenchyma with large parenchymal cells rich in mucilages, d = endoderm, e = wood, f = free)

Fig. 2. *Malva sylvestris* L. - cross section through the root colored with methylene blue (ob.10x, 40x) (a = exoderm, b = bark, c = cortical parenchyma with large parenchymal cells rich in mucilages, d = endoderm, e = wood, f = free)

Fig. 3. *Malva sylvestris* L. - cross-section through root colored with chrysidine and Congo red, alternatively (ob.10x, 40x) (a = exoderm, b = bark, c = cortical parenchyma with large parenchymal cells rich in mucilages, d = endoderm, p = pericycle, e = wood, f = free)

The stem of both species of hawthorn *Althaea officinalis* L. and *Malva sylvestris* L. in cross-section has a circular outline, without major differentiations. The presence of simple filamentous tectorial pears in the species *Althaea officinalis* L.

The epidermis is made up of a single layer of cells, tightly joined together, between which are also stomatal cells. The cell walls are externally pumped, cutinised, lignified, cerified or mineralized by secondary wall modification.

The bark is located immediately below the epidermis, has parenchymal cells, with intercellular spaces, except for the first outer layer, which is slightly colenchymatized. The cells of the cortical parenchyma contain chlorophyll granules, which turn green, and the deeper layers show starch granules. The central star or cylinder comprises all tissues located inside the endoderm. In the stem is a single central cylinder. It has a peril, free-range conductive bundles, spinal cord and spinal cord.

The pericycle is located below the endoderm and outside the conducting bundles, consisting of one or more layers of cells with cellulose walls.

The conductive bundles represent the most important tissues of the central cylinder. The lumber bundles are collateral, made of woody conductive tissue, inside and Liberian, on the outside. The woody fabric of the bundles is made of wood vessels, parenchyma woody. Liberian tissue is made up of Liberian vessels or suction tubes, attachment cells and Liberian parenchyma.

The primary medullary rays are parenchymal cell cords that occupy the gap between the fascicles and make the connection between the marrow and the danger.

Fig. 4. *Althaea officinalis L.*- cross-section through colored strain with Genevez reagent (ob.10x, 40x)

(a = epidermis, b = bark, c = medullary cortical parenchyma, f = woody bundles, d = free, woody, s = sclerenchymal, r = medullary rays)

Althaea officinalis L. showed the presence of unicellular filamentous tectonic pears, grouped 2-6 in star shape on both epidermis. The same type of bristles are also found in *Malva sylvestris L.*, but in a much smaller number. In the parenchyma there are numerous cells with mucilages.

Fig. 5. *Althaea officinalis L.* si *Malva sylvestris L.* - cross-section through the leaf (ob. 10x) (a = upper epidermis, b = lower epidermis, c = palisadic tissue, d = lacunar tissue, p = simple filamentous hairs)

Fig. 6. *Malva sylvestris L.*- cross-section through petiole colored with methylene blue and Genevez reagent (ob. 10x, 40x)(a = epidermis, b = mechanical tissue of the colenchymal type, c = fundamental parenchyma, d = medullary cortical parenchyma, f = free-woody conductive bundle, p = simple perectors)

CONCLUSIONS

The microscopic study at the level of the vegetative organs was performed on cross sections, longitudinal, or by skinning and stained with Genevez reagent (Congo red + chrysidine), methylene blue, malachite green. The following anatomical structures were determined by optical microscopy: *Althaeae radix*, *Malvae radix*, *Althaeae herba*, *Malvae herba*, *Althaeae folium*, *Malvae folium*, *Malvae flos*, *Althaeae flos*. In the primary root structure of both species *Althaea officinalis* L. and *Malva sylvestris* L., cells with high mucilage content were highlighted, colored blue in the presence of methylene blue, or yellow-orange in the presence of Genevez's reagent. The stem of both hawthorn species *Althaea officinalis* L. and *Malva sylvestris* L. in cross-section has a circular outline, without major differentiations. The presence of simple filamentous tectorial pears in the species *Althaea officinalis* L. At the level of the broad-leaved leaves *Althaea officinalis* L. the presence of unicellular filamentous tectorial pears, grouped 2-6 in star shape on both epidermis, was highlighted. The same type of bristles are also found in *Malva sylvestris* L., but in a much smaller number. In the parenchyma there are numerous cells with mucilages. The correct elucidation of the anatomical structures are very important for the phytotherapy, for the more detailed knowledge of the plant products with therapeutic potential and establishing connections between the morphological particularities and the content in active principles.

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THE ACTION OF THE UNDERGROUND WATER ON HISTORICAL CONSTRUCTIONS

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Abstract

Among the actions of the environment factors on the buildings in general and of the historical structures in particular, the water in the water table is not only the most present factor but also the most aggressive one.

Be it water that is naturally present in the water table, or water that got into the water table through a construction error, it generates the most substantial damages and degradations of the structures of the historical buildings. These damages and degradations are more dangerous as the action of the water is slow, even invisible most of the times and almost without exception a long term one.

The causes that lead to the aggressive action of the water on the historical structures are either natural, due to a soil that is not suitable for construction, or human, due to inadequate construction solutions or to subsequent human actions that generate damaging actions on the buildings.

The presence of the water in the immediate vicinity or contact with the historical structures is impossible to avoid. Because of this, any of the solutions regarding the waterproofing of the buildings have both advantages and disadvantages. The action and/or the contact of the water with the construction is impossible to avoid. The invasive or non-invasive, reversible or irreversible, visible or invisible measures cannot completely avoid the contact of the water with the building. For this reason, the option for a solution or another must have as a purpose the maximum protection effect of the building against the damaging actions of the water.

The identification of the causes, the understanding of the way the water acts on the historical buildings and the correct identification of the solutions regarding the protection of the buildings against the actions of the groundwater are the key points of this study.

Key words: groundwater, degradation, historical buildings, waterproofing, protection

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, whether we are talking about the area of Europe or Asia, the way to build was based on structures made of brick load-bearing walls or stone blocks, wooden slabs and timber frames supported by brick vaults or wooden beam grids. For finishing works, the lime was used in its double form, aerial or hydraulic.

In the 1950s - 1960s a new type of construction system began to spread, based on a structural framework made of cement and iron (reinforcement). This major difference can be expressed as the difference between two absolutely different methodologies of construction. It is therefore obvious that the whole historical real estate heritage has nothing in

common with the new construction methodology. The first and biggest difference is the lack of cement from the first construction typology.

Based on these major historical differences, one might think that, in the general collective mind, but especially of those in the field of constructions (designing engineers and builders alike), everything that represents a historical real estate heritage has a special place, and consequently, any intervention on it must be made in full respect of the monument and with maximum professionalism. Of course, this phrase implies finding the correct architectural, structural and infrastructure solutions, but also applying techniques and materials compatible or even identical with the historical ones. The complexity of such an endeavor is all the more so since, along with the craftsmen, it is known that many of these techniques and materials have disappeared, and the efforts to maintain and/or revive them involve considerable material and human efforts. And yet, the daily practice proves that far from being aware of such a responsible and respectful professional conduct towards the built heritage, humanity is, in many cases, far from the truisms stated.

In principle, humidity is defined as the amount of water vapor or the degree of saturation with water vapor of the air at a given time. Regardless of temperature, the unit of measure defined as a cubic meter of air, may contain a certain maximum amount of relative humidity. Therefore, the actual percentage of humidity in the unit of measurement of air, is called Relative Humidity, and is defined as a percentage. If the R.U. is maximum, the cubic meter of air is defined as saturated, and the Relative Humidity is 100%.

The amount of relative humidity decreases with the temperature, causing the water vapor to be eliminated as the air temperature drops. When this phenomenon happens outside, it takes the form of clouds or dew. If, on the other hand, the phenomenon occurs inside, it is called condensation or the well-known and unpleasant humidity.

Based on the World Health Organization, the ideal relative humidity, either in indoor or outdoor spaces, is in the value range between 40% and 50%, regardless of temperature. Starting with the value of 60% of relative humidity, the states of discomfort begin to appear, while from 70% of relative humidity, phenomena such as dew, condensation and even mold appear. As an expression of how relative humidity can be influenced, it is well known that an average family produces on average 10 liters of water vapor through washing, cooking, etc.

Condensation occurs when the air in a room cools in contact with a cold surface existing in that space. The most illustrative example is the bathroom mirror, having a surface cooler than the indoor air temperature. Another "classic" example is the wall of a room facing North or East. Less

known to the general public, but just as obvious, is that a wall is cooler if through it the phenomenon of capillary ascension of water occurs. For a good example it is useful to know that a gram of water that evaporates, extracts 540 calories from the surface on which it evaporates, resulting in its cooling.

Anyway, the most effective way to combat the emersion of condensation and mold is the intervention of interrupting the capillary ascension of the water in the masonry.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Bringing the discussion at present, we find that after more than 2000 years of use of old types of mortars based on hydraulic or aerial lime, they have disappeared from the market from the 1950s – 1960s, and along with them also disappeared the laying related technology. Obviously, the legitimate question arises: why did this phenomenon happen? The answer is very simple: being able to combine with the old types of mortar, the cement has simply become a stronger mortar, with a faster setting, with a stronger adhesion, and last but not least, cheaper. Looking at the phenomenon from this perspective, naturally, the following question arises: if so, why use the old mortars again? As a first impulse, the answer seems very simple. Even guided by the best intentions, the use of cement has become so widespread that it seems useless to try to find and justify any answer.

Fig. 1. The action of the ascending water in a historic masonry with cement mortar

Fig. 2. The action of the ascending water in a historical masonry with lime mortar

On closer analysis, however, we can differentiate the following nuances of the problem. First of all, cement is not a better mortar. It is a better bonding material than the old mortars. It is a material that, chemically, is radically different from the old mortars. For this reason, applied to the so-called historical masonry, it behaves according to its own physical and chemical rules, most often incompatible with the morphological structure of the historical masonry. In conclusion, here it is that, in practice, the awareness that cement-based mortar is not compatible with the historical masonry structures does not occur. In other words, without special attention paid to historical heritage, hence to old buildings,

attention that inevitably must also be found in national laws, the traditional techniques and materials are destined to disappearance and oblivion. Suggestive for this process subject to change constantly is how cement and its use in the field of construction has been viewed over time. If at the beginning of its widespread use it was perceived as a "novelty" and an exponent of "progress", nowadays, almost exclusively, in the field of restoration, it is excluded a priori from the intervention solutions.

Beyond the cultural and/or moral arguments stated, however, is the use of cement in the field of the conservation and rehabilitation of the historical heritage so serious? The answer is unequivocal yes, precisely due to the superior characteristics of the cement-based mortars.

- 1) NOT REQUIRED. A conventional cement-based mortar is about four or five times stronger than a traditional lime-based mortar (the compression strength is at least 150 kg/cm², compared to 35 kg/cm²). Such strength not only is not required in a masonry that works at a maximum of 7.5 kg/cm², but when used to fill in the missing areas, it generates different behaviors of the historic masonry.
- 2) IRREVERSIBLE LOSSES. Any type/element of historical material, once built or fixed with the aid of cement-based mortar, is irreversibly degraded and thus lost. Why is this happening? Because the cement-based mortar fixing is, in the overwhelming majority of the cases, stronger than its own strength of the historical material itself.
- 3) IT IS NOT PERMISSIVE. Cement-based mortars are much less permissive when the water passes through the masonry structure. This means that, under normal conditions of capillary ascension, the humidity will evaporate from the historical material, instead of this process occurring from the layers of mortar joining the building blocks.
- 4) COMPLEX SALT OF ETTRINGITE. A chemical compound specific to cement, but lacking in traditional mortars, namely tricalcium aluminate, reacts in a humid environment with the sulphates present, thus forming a complex salt of ettringite, in which the crystals formed have a double volume compared to the initial state. This expansion obviously breaks and dislocates the historical material in the immediate vicinity of the cement-based mortar.
- 5) WATERPROOF PLASTERS. It is already proven that a cement-based plaster is much less permissive when evaporating water from the wall structure than a historical lime-based plaster. By default, this implies reduced indoor comfort, generated by increased indoor humidity, humidity deriving through capillary ascension. Finally, in

addition to the harmful effect on the indoor environment, the physical degradation caused to the historical masonry will be massive and most often irreversible.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phenomenon of capillary ascension in historical built structures exists because the constructive system has always been based on the same principles: solid brick or stone masonry, elements joined together by mortars based on aerial or hydraulic lime and sand, placed directly in the natural ground, without any kind of waterproofing. Therefore, in the load-bearing structures the ascension happens automatically, precisely due to the construction system, and this phenomenon occurs both in the vertical direction, through the walls, as well as in the horizontal direction, especially through the floors of the ground floor, or, as the case may be, of the basement.

Fig. 3. Capillary ascension in different types of walls: granite, marble, chalk, cement plaster, lime plaster, medium limestone, new brick, sandstone, travertine

Fig. 4. Waterproof contact

Fig. 5. Hydrophobic contact

Following numerous observations and studies, the existence of two types of contacts between water and the wall support with which it comes into contact was established. First of all, it is about the waterproof contact, in which the contact between the water and the wall is convex, the angle between the horizontal of the liquid and the vertical of the wall being greater than 90° . In the second case it is the hydrophobic contact, in which the contact between the wall and the water is concave, the angle between the horizontal of the water and the vertical of the wall being less than 90° . The type of contact depends on the type of materials that compose and generate

the process. The classic examples are those between water and glass, which generates a hydrophobic contact, while mercury and glass generate a waterproof contact.

According to Jurin's law, in the absence of evaporation, the ascending force of each capillary is given by the type of material, the radius of the capillary, the density of the liquid and not least by the contact angle. Based on the aforementioned law, a capillary with a diameter of 1 micron, can raise the water up to 15 meters high. However, the phenomenon of evaporation existing and also acting concomitantly with that of capillary ascension, the ascending effects of water/humidity are blurred and balanced by all the factors involved and all their actions.

In conclusion, therefore, the amount of water that will be absorbed and risen in a certain time interval (minute, hour, etc.), by a certain type of material, depends on its structure, on the number and type of capillaries, on the connections between them, etc., essentially on its porosity and its absorption coefficient.

In practice, the total amount of water absorbed will continue the ascension process until it finds the first surface capable of allowing the evaporation process. At the limit, in the ideal case, the balance between capillary ascension and evaporation occurs when the amount of water absorbed is equal to the amount of water eliminated by evaporation. Moreover, once the maximum height of ascension is established, the hydrodynamic balance is established between the ascension and the evaporation processes. Otherwise, if the evaporation process intensifies (higher heat or stronger wind), the visible humidity level inside the wall will decrease. On the contrary, if the evaporation process decreases, the visible humidity level in the wall will rise.

Moreover, since we are talking about a continuous process, its effects are continually amplified or diminished, permanently modifying the material and its physico-chemical properties. Why and especially how is this phenomenon happening? Because, in principle, up to this point of the analysis, isolated concepts were discussed. In reality, however, there is no distilled water in the natural environment. Fact for which, without exception, all the amount of water that by ascension and absorption enters the structure of the walls, contains dissolved mineral salts: chlorides, sulphates and nitrates. Further, it is known and proven that the water will evaporate from the surface of the wall, while salts will not, instead they will form salt crystals on the outer surface of the wall. These crystals will clog, block up and seal the surface of the wall, thus diminishing the breathability capacity of the wall in the respective area.

Their origin lies in the water that evaporates from the surface of a wall, originating from the capillary ascent of the water from the

groundwater, either from the capillary ascension or the propagation caused by the defects of the sewers existing inside the building. These waters always contain mineral salts. Through this process, the water evaporates but the salts do not. As a result of this phenomenon, these salts remain on the outer surface of the walls forming increasingly larger and more crystals.

Fig. 6. Invisible subflorescences below the plaster of the wall

Fig. 7. Visible efflorescences on top of the plaster

Fig. 8. Salt crystals that destroy the plaster/wall

However, it is not these salts, respectively efflorescences, that produce the degradation of the parietal surfaces, but the so-called subflorescences. They are located in the first 10 – 12 mm of the thickness of the plaster or wall. Subflorescences, invisible, through their continuous expansion, produce the breaking, dislocation and rupture of the upper layers of the wall or plaster.

The position in which salts form efflorescence or subflorescence crystals depends on two factors:

1. The type of masonry and/or material from which the wall is formed, respectively its plaster. And because these salts occur at the molecular level, also in the case of masonry/plaster we discuss about their capillary structure.

2. Secondly, it is the climatic conditions that the respective wall has to face. These climatic conditions refer to humidity, temperature, exposure or not to solar radiation, exposure or not to the actions of the wind, etc.

As a result of those described above, the following conclusions are obvious: the behavior of the masonry subject to the actions of the inner waters varies during the same day. Under such conditions, two extreme behavioral scenarios can be developed. The first of these refers to the phenomenon of maximum evaporation. It involves high temperatures, strong wind and low-intensity relative humidity. In this way, the air penetrates the masonry in depth, thus favoring the evaporation of the subflorescences. At the opposite pole, the low temperatures, the total or

almost total lack of the wind, respectively the existence of a high relative humidity, will favor the evaporation on the outer surface of the masonry, respectively of the efflorescences.

CONCLUSIONS

The application of cement-based plastering, does nothing but reduce the degree of permeability to evaporation and favors capillary ascension. Similarly, the application of cement-based mortars, either in the structure of the walls or as asphalt layers on horizontal surfaces (markets, sidewalks, roads, etc.), will have the same result on the historical building material. And finally, in order to maximize the destructive effect, the aggressive and invasive methods of "cleaning" and "preparing" the masonry for the application of new mortars based on cement are also worth highlighting.

Finally, it should be mentioned that also in the case of structural consolidation, the use of materials compatible with the historical structure of the building, can generate results at least similar to those that would be obtained if the interventions were carried out with mortars and/or materials based on cement. From the category of the first, the most common are reinforced or cross-linked fiber plaster, based on aerial or hydraulic lime. Less accepted, knowing that these are also irreversible, but certainly not as harmful as those based on cement, epoxy resins in small quantities are another option for structural consolidation interventions.

Therefore, the comprehensive understanding of the whole phenomenon, with all the causes that generate it, respectively with all the implications they generate on the historical structures, represents a good starting point in establishing correct solutions.

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GEOMETRIC MODELING APPLIED IN ENGINEERING

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Abstract

In this work we will present a practical method of application modeling three-dimensional surfaces, useful for shading or protect of precipitation a useful surface. By point of view geometrically it can be modeled any surface of any geometric form, with the condition they know the characteristics of the area and the environment, the odds and positioning of of other landmarks.

Key words: modeling, geometric, pergola, sun protection

INTRODUCTION

The work refers at the shading of a surface of about 850 m² divided into 25 of size areas different, which becomes protected of sun and weather conditions. The goal of work is to highlight parameters review: safety, resistance, maintenance, environment, as well as the geometric method used, conclusions and observations drawn.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Dimensions and characteristics of the area, they have been taken from the place. Useful area is urban, with the purpose must be shadowed, to resist long term to snow, ice, precipitation, weather, sun, which means about 5 years.

Having a metallic structure wich separates distributed areas, the proposed solution is pergola. With a modern design and useful, the fixing is provided so that they can do the role from the point of viewal human security. Maintining another parameter, must be accessible and easy to achieve. Visual obstruction of other adjacent areas, for example video cameras, it is important, this should be minimal.

After the on-site analysis, it was found that each area has other characteristics and each pergola must be personalized, depending on location, the useful surface, positioning, grip and shape.

. From an engineering point of view and in terms of passer safety, a fastening system was created, adapted to the shape that in general is a parallelogram, from different angles, which can withstand shearing tearing, traction, and weight due material mass, of the wind, or other factors extenals such as snow, ice, as in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Metric screw

Thus metric screw was chosen made of galvanized steel and with the larger in fill area that can withstand a breaking force, traction, shear, less than 800 N / mm². Braces, clips were attached, stretchers, key wrenches, eyepieces, to support the whole designed structure. For stretching, metal gloves were designed and steel cables, that it's structure has greater grip resistance. All these were seen in figure 2:

Fig. 2. Metal gloves

The calculations were made according to the size for each area, of the clamping mode, the alleged mass of snow from the climatic zone temperate continental moderate, of the city of Satu Mare, which is located in the plain, and the inclination to the horizontal of the two peaks. Threading must be more permissive that is, on a larger surface because the material has a characteristic of elasticity, which must be taken into account. The characteristics of the manufacturing material are the following: elasticity is 2% the linear 5m, adheres 10 teeth / 5cm, breaking force 32/28 dan, temperature resistance -30°C to +70°C, tensile strength 260/250 dan, total weight 680 g/m².

Perforated metal gloves were created under the different angles, depending on the trigonometric calculations level difference. Certainly, these angles, have moved around 75°, shown in figure 3:

Fig. 3. Pergola

Geometric modeling refers to framing the pergola on the personalized ceilings, of different dimensions, their shape being parallelograms with two diagonal clamping tips on the metal structure established in advance and two peaks one meter down vertically. From mathematical and trigonometric calculations, the following form was established as in figure 4:

Fig. 4. Pergola 3D

Because their size is very large on average, 6m x 6m, the material, must be partitioned into glued pieces, so as to create a greater resistance by bonding. Moreover, they must be established the angles of each peak, of the parallelogram after the curve. The material was cut under a curvature of approximately 30 cm deep, to be stretched without needing help steel cables.

The bonding of the material was done with a special machine at 550°C, with a certain speed of travel, so as to avoid burning.

The mathematical calculations have led to the framing of the well-defined geometric figure, complying with all environmental requirements. For a rigorous arrangement of pergolas on the measured surfaces, from the point of view of geometric modeling, we used Autodesk AutoCad 2020. This geometric modeling software, allowed us to calculate the exact linear quotas, of curvature and angle, as well as level differences. Thus the following final modeling was obtained as in figure 5:

Fig. 5. View of Pergola

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The advantage of the chosen grip is safety, the varied movement due to external factors is minimal, the resistance to any wind force induced by the environment and the distance from the mounting bracket, is as small as possible.

Advantage of the chosen material: flexible, easy to process, excellent welding, durable technology, easy to clean, durable, fine surface, stops the sun's rays.

CONCLUSIONS

The project was put into practice in 2019, corresponds as design, structure and geometric modeling of all the parameters specified during the work, with the specification as maintenance to clean the snow in winter, it is necessary and important to do, when submitting a small layer, because it may influence the entire or partial surface of the deposit, due to the elasticity and the large surfaces of the pergolas.

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METROPOLITAN POLLUTION AND THE IMPACT ON LABOUR EFFICIENCY

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Abstract

The present environment around metropolitan areas because of industries, transport, etc. brings a tremendous amount of pollution that impacts the health of population but also the efficiency of its labour capacity.

Key words: Pollution, labour efficiency, health, metropolitan areas

INTRODUCTION

The paper presents estimation of the health losses and specially labour efficiency from metropolitan air pollution.

The methodology developed by US EPA and adjusted for Eastern European transition countries was applied for health risk assessment. PM_{2.5} more than P.M 10 was identified as the major source of human health risk, based on experience from the USA and EU studies. In the absence of reliable computed concentrations of PM_{2.5}, the study was based on monitoring data of total suspended particle (TSP) emissions. Additional cases of mortality and morbidity were calculated based on reporting data on TSP concentration that was recalculated into PM_{2.5}.

Fig. 1 Estimation of the health losses
source: medicalxpress.com.

Then the concentration–response function was applied to estimate individual risk. Next, individual risk was applied to the population exposed to the concentration reported for each metropolitan areas. For each metropolitan areas it has to considered individual data on baseline mortality and morbidity, population structure, labour efficiency, etc..

In total, air pollution related mortality represents about 6 percent of total mortality around the world.

Since applied method is sensitive to the primary data uncertainties we conducted sensitivity analysis applying Monte-Carlo method. Economic damage related to mortality risk was estimated at about 4 percent of GDP. There was no relevant WTP study in therefore we applied the benefit-transfer method in order to estimate VSL, since mortality attributed to air pollution is major component of health losses (about 94 percent). In order to compare and aggregate mortality and morbidity risks we recalculated them in DALY. Then morbidity represents about 30 percent of total air pollution health load. Data on baseline morbidity is less reliable than data on baseline mortality; therefore the morbidity risk estimates are more uncertain than mortality estimates. It is likely that morbidity risk is underestimated. Regardless of uncertainties mentioned above and some problems with reported data we can conclude that the mortality risk attributed to air pollution is significant. Therefore, costs of air pollution are sizable and in the nearest future may offset the economic growth.

Recovery of the economy based on restoration of polluting industries may lead to stagnation since mortality and morbidity risks not only puts burden on the economy, but also reduce labor force.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Fossil fuel combustion is the main source of PM_{2.5} AND PM₁₀ pollutants. Unfortunately, levels of PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5} are not monitored on a reliable basis in many countries. Hence any assessment of the impacts of the particles has to be based on what is reliably monitored, which is total suspended particles or TSP, and the link between TSP and PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5}.

In this context it is worth noting that huge amount of effort goes into monitoring a large number of pollutants (more than 35) in the FSU countries. The purpose of undertaking such extensive monitoring was to set emissions standards for individual emitters so that actual concentrations of 1 PM₁₀ is particulate matter less than 10 microns in diameter; similarly PM_{2.5} refers to matter less than 2.5 microns in diameter. Small particles, however, are also formed from chemical interactions of SO₂ and other pollutants with ozone. Hence emissions of these pollutants are also important contributors to health impacts. 3 pollutants did not exceed certain health determined maximum allowable concentrations (MACs).

In practice, however, the MACs were not substantiated by practical methods and techniques of air pollution control. It was impossible to attain the desired accuracy of analytical control, to use adequate instrumentation, numerical estimation methods, unit emissions, technological standards,

emission control requirements. Neither was there was adequate financing or professional staffing. The improvements in these areas are very slow.

A large number of epidemiological studies provide evidence that exposure to air pollution is associated with increased morbidity and mortality (WHO, 2004). The most affected are respiratory and cardiovascular systems. The mechanisms “may involve decrements in pulmonary function, effects on heart rate variability and inflammatory response”. Also, there is an evidence of carcinogenicity of some components of urban air pollution. Both acute and chronic biological responses are affected by air pollution, since acute responses exacerbate the severity of chronic diseases. Epidemiologic literature proposes to use Cox proportional hazards model for the long term health risk estimation. Basically, they have the following form:

$$yC = - [y e C] pop B * (-\beta * \Delta - 1) * (1)$$

where:

yC is incremental number of cases of negative health outcome (morbidity or mortality);

ΔC is the change in mean population-weighted annual concentration of criteria pollutant²;

β is concentration-response coefficient;

yB is baseline level of the health outcome;

² PM pollution could be used as an indicator of pollution mix.

⁴ pop is exposed population to which it is appropriate to apply β (the same as in the epi studies, where β was estimated).

For small changes in the annual mean criteria pollutant concentration, it is appropriate to use a linear relationship between incremental health outcome and change in annual mean criteria pollutant concentration:

$$yC = C y pop B \beta * \Delta * * (2)$$

Then, β is concentration-response coefficient that reflects change in health outcome per unit of pollution (slope of concentration-response function).

Air pollution and mortality

For PM_{2.5} pollution, β values were developed for all cause mortality, cardiopulmonary mortality, and lung cancer mortality (Pope et al., 2002) Then β is the per cent change in health outcome per unit of pollution (i.e. the slope of concentration-response function).

It is appropriate to use β from epidemiological studies, when pollution in the focus area is in the range observed in the study used for the estimation. For example, WHO recommends to apply Pope coefficients for PM_{2.5} pollution in the range of 7.5-50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ PM_{2.5}. Beyond 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ the β value is set at zero.

Experts agree that based on the current status of worldwide research, the risk ratios, or concentration response coefficients from Pope et al (2002) are likely to be the best available evidence for the mortality effects of ambient particulate pollution (PM 2.5). This study provided a global estimate of the health effects of environmental risk factors including health risk from environmental pollution. It was the American Cancer Society study within the framework of

Cancer Prevention II prospective study of risk factors for mortality, where 1.2 million Americans from 50 metropolitan areas 30 and older were involved. This study concentrated on long-term exposure to air pollution from fine particulates (PM2.5) that are the most harmful for human health and include sulfates and nitrates. Long-term pollution is more important than short-term, because it include the effects of long-term exposure that can not be captured by a short-term study. The participants were observed for about 16 years. The study controlled for age, sex, weight, height, smoking, alcohol use, occupational exposure, diet, education, marital status, etc. As a result the study came up with the list of concentration-response coefficients, which identify additional risk of non-accidental death, cardio-pulmonary and lung-cancer mortality.

If our goal is to assess total health risk caused by air pollution, one should take into account the difference between observed mortality and baseline mortality. From formula (1) above, y_B should be derived for the baseline situation if we would like to have y_B associated with the ΔC ambient concentration levels (of PM2.5, for example). If y is defined by the equation (2) (choosing a linear specification over the relevant range of C):

$$C B y = \beta * \Delta C * y \quad (3)$$

The baseline y_B however, is not directly observed, and is given by:

$$B C y = y - y_0 \quad (4)$$

where y_0 is the observed or recorded number of all cause non accidental or cardiopulmonary and lung cancer deaths. Substituting equation (4) in equation (3) provides the following solution for

y_B :

$$*() * / \{ 1 * () \} 0 y C y C C = \beta \Delta + \beta \Delta \quad (5)$$

We have applied Pope's all cause non accidental mortality coefficient $\beta = 0.004$ per $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. If $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration is above $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, the value was set at $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Since the Pope estimates apply only to persons over the age of 30, this share had to be estimated.

Air pollution related morbidity

Although available information on mortality is quite reliable, morbidity information is not. Therefore, we had to apply the method proposed by Ostro (1994) to estimate respiratory hospital admissions,

emergency room visits, restricted activity days, lower respiratory illness in children and respiratory symptoms. For chronic bronchitis we applied the approach from Abbey et al (1995). Method from Ostro (1994) doesn't require baseline morbidity. Thus it is applicable even with poor primary data about background morbidity indicators. Abbey's approach requires a baseline chronic bronchitis morbidity. Official data on chronic bronchitis were provided by the Ministry of Public Health of Ukraine. Both studies Ostro (1994) and Abbey (1995) link exposure to PM10 air pollution with additional morbidity end-points. For air pollution related cases of chronic bronchitis we applied the formula similar to (5), where y_c is additional number of chronic bronchitis and y_0 is observed number of cases for Euro B region. For other morbidity end-points we applied the following formula, as in Ostro (1994):

$$Y_c = \beta * C, \quad (6)$$

Where C is observed PM10 concentration and β is concentration-response coefficient.

The burden of health impacts is converted to monetary terms by valuing mortality and morbidity. Valuation is based on robust willingness to pay studies that quantify the value of human health risk reduction. These valuation studies have not been done in any other FSU country. Therefore the only method to apply for valuation is a benefit transfer approach. The physical estimates of mortality and morbidity can be converted in monetary values under certain assumptions. 3 Studies on the valuation of health effects of outdoor air pollution outside the OECD countries are rare. Recent work along this lines, using some benefit transfer has been undertaken in China (Eliason and Lee, 2003), in Russia (Bobilev, 2002) and Peru (Larsen, 2005).

CONCLUSIONS

This paper tried to show that metropolitan areas have more considerable health and mortality costs in human and monetary terms associated with air pollution. At a conservative estimate these costs amount to 4.6 million excess deaths lost annually. ***In monetary terms, we estimate the costs at around 5 trillion \$ from 88.00 trillion\$ the total world GDP or 18.5% of it almost double the economic annual average growth o 9.5%***

Studies in the EU of similar costs, but using much more detailed data and a more sophisticated modeling of the dispersion of air pollution and the creation of particles, comes up with air pollution costs from similar items in the range of 2 percent (Markandya and Tamborra, 2005). At the same time, the level of effort devoted to addressing it is much lower. Public and private sector spending on investment in air pollution control is very small (World Bank, 2003). Studies like these provide a useful guide to where efforts

should be made to reduce air emissions (the focus needs to be on particulate pollution control in certain cities we have identified), and how the air pollution problem compares with other sources of morbidity and mortality (it is more serious, for example, than most social causes of death and more serious than TB). This is not something that is generally appreciated or acted upon.

The paper also demonstrates how the analysis can be done using limited and uncertain information. Therefore, estimates presented in the paper were complemented by sensitivity analysis. Limited data on air pollution is not enough to develop a detailed action plan for environmental costs burden alleviation, however, it is a good way to draw attention to environmental problems ignored by now. Thus environmental degradation may soon become a significant barrier for economic growth and can not be ignored by policy makers.

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RESULTS REGARDING THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT DOSES OF CHEMICAL FERTILIZERS ON THE CONCENTRATION OF ZINC IN WHEAT GRAINS

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Abstract

Wheat grains analyzed come from long-term experiments with chemical and organic fertilizers. A field experiment was carried out at the Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea, Bihor County, Romania. Were analyzed the effect of applying different doses of chemical fertilizers with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium to wheat crop on zinc concentration of wheat grains during three years.

The gradual increase of the doses of chemical fertilizers with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium led to increase the zinc concentration in wheat grains between 1.023 and 2.318 mg/kg compared with the control variant. At the application of chemical fertilizers with nitrogen and phosphorus the increases compared to the control were not significant, being between 0.525 and 0.930 mg/kg.

Key words: wheat, grains, zinc, doses, chemical fertilizers

INTRODUCTION

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is among the top cereal crops cultivated in Romania, together with maize and sunflower.

Zinc is part of the essential metals functioning of animal and vegetable bodies, but beyond certain limits, is carcinogenic and teratogenic potential. Since there is no ability to be absorbed into the digestive tract, zinc has little toxicity, in contrast to its salts, however, are irritating to the mucosa of the digestive tract and high dose toxicity.

Mainly sources of pollution with zinc come from mining, burning of fossil fuels, burning of waste, production of steel, manufacture of paints and tire products (Răuță C. et al., 1992, Dudka S. et al., 1994).

Irrigation with wastewater increase the concentration of heavy metals (Cu, Cr, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn) in the roots, stems and seeds of wheat plants, the most significant increase was registered in the case of manganese and zinc (Ramachandran V. and D'Souza T. J., 1998, M. Karatas et al., 2006, Gao X. et al., 2010,).

In case of the roots wheat roots the translocation of heavy metals is performed in the following order: Mn> Ni> Zn> Cd> Co> Cr> with> Pb, respectively wheat plant distribution of heavy metals is as follows: Mn>

Zn> Pb> Ni> Co > Cd> with> Cr (Gyori Z., 2007, B. Lukšienė and M. Račaitė, 2008).

Research by R. Kastori et al. (2006) shows that the translocation in case of triticale the nickel, copper and zinc in the vegetative parts of the seed was intense, while the molybdenum was average.

M. Francois et al. (2008) suspects that zinc interacts with chemical fertilizers with phosphorus so slow down the absorption of zinc by wheat.

The application of foliar fertilizer on the basis of zinc and iron in various concentrations resulted an insignificant increase in the concentration of zinc in the grain of wheat. Zinc applied alone resulted a significant increases in its concentration in wheat grains (E. Niyigaba et al., 2019).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Laboratory investigations were carried out in the **“Research Laboratory of risk factors for Agriculture, Forestry and the Environment”**, Faculty of Environmental Protection – University of Oradea.

The samples of the winter wheat grains were harvested, in 2010 – 2012 period, in the long term trials at the Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea.

Variants studied

Factor A: nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium combination; a1:

N₀P₀K₀; a2: N₈₀P₄₀K₄₀; a3: N₈₀P₈₀K₈₀; a4: N₁₆₀P₈₀K₁₂₀.

Factor B: nitrogen and phosphorus combinations; b1: N₀P₀; b2:

N₅₀P₀; b3: N₅₀P₅₀; b4: N₁₀₀P₁₀₀

Plant biological material samples were mineralized with a mixture of sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) and perchloric acid (HClO₄) to determine the zinc concentration.

For the determination of zinc concentration in wheat grains, the samples were prepared according to the working methods presented above were analyzed by spectrophotometer with atomic absorption SHIMADZU AA-6300.

Correlations between chemical fertilizers doses and zinc concentrations in wheat grains were calculated using Microsoft Excel and was chosen the function with the highest value of R².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The average zinc concentration in wheat grains over the three years studied, 2010-2012, in the control variant (N₀P₀K₀) was 11.843 mg/kg. In the case of the N₈₀P₄₀K₄₀ variant, a concentration of 12.866 mg/kg was

registered, higher by 8.6% compared to the $N_0P_0K_0$ variant, the differences being statistically insignificant. In the $N_{80}P_{80}K_{80}$ variant, the wheat grains had a higher zinc concentration of 14.4% (not statistically significant) compared to the control variant, of 13.553 mg/kg. In the fertilized variant with $N_{160}P_{80}K_{120}$ the increase in zinc concentration was 19.6% (statistically significant) compared to the unfertilized variant, 14.161 mg/kg (Table 1).

Table 1

The influence of doses and combinations of NPK fertilizers on zinc concentration in winter wheat grains, average data, (2010-2012)

Variant	Zn concentration		Difference		Statistical significance
	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	
$N_0P_0K_0$	11.843	100	-	-	Control
$N_{80}P_{40}K_{40}$	12.866	108.6	1.023	8.6	-
$N_{80}P_{80}K_{80}$	13.553	114.4	1.710	14.4	-
$N_{160}P_{80}K_{120}$	14.161	119.6	2.318	19.6	*
LSD 5%			1.81		
LSD 1%			3.44		
LSD 0.1%			6.07		

Regarding the mathematical modeling of the results regarding the concentration of zinc in the wheat grains collected from the 4 studied variants of the experiment with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, it shows that the power type function best quantifies the connection between the doses of fertilizers with NPK and zinc concentration from wheat grains, $y = 11.81x^{0.127}$, $R^2 = 0.984$ (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Correlation between doses of NPK fertilizers and zinc concentration in wheat grains

The average zinc concentration in wheat grains harvested from variant N_0P_0 (control) was 11.826 mg/kg. In the case of variant $N_{40}P_{40}$ there

was a higher zinc concentration in wheat, by 4.4%, 12.351 mg/kg, than the variant N₀P₀, being statistically insignificant. The wheat grains harvested from the fertilized variant with N₈₀P₈₀ had a zinc concentration of 12.686 mg/kg, higher by 7.3% compared to the control, the difference being statistically insignificant. The zinc concentration determined in the wheat grains harvested from variant N₁₆₀P₁₆₀, was 7.9% higher than the unfertilized variant, not being statistically assured, registering the value of 12.757 mg/kg (Table 2).

Table 2

The influence of doses and combinations of NP fertilizers on zinc concentration in winter wheat grains, average data, (2010-2012)

Variant	Zn concentration		Difference		Statistical significance
	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	
N ₀ P ₀	11.826	100	-	-	Control
N ₄₀ P ₄₀	12.351	104.4	0.525	4.4	-
N ₈₀ P ₈₀	12.686	107.3	0.859	7.3	-
N ₁₆₀ P ₁₆₀	12.757	107.9	0.930	7.9	-
		LSD 5%	0.942		
		LSD 1%	1.253		
		LSD 0.1%	1.772		

The mathematical modeling of the obtained results shows that the polynomial type function, $y = -0.113x^2 + 0.879x + 11.05$, $R^2 = 0.998$, best quantifies the link between fertilizer doses with nitrogen and phosphorus and the zinc concentration in the wheat grains harvested from experience (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Correlation between doses of NP fertilizers and zinc concentration in wheat grains

CONCLUSIONS

The zinc concentration of wheat grains increased with increasing fertilizers doses with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium.

Differences from the control variants were statistically ensured in the highest doses versions, taking values in the case of wheat 14.161 mg/kg in the variant N₁₆₀P₈₀K₁₂₀ and 12.757 mg/kg in the fertilized version with N₁₆₀P₁₆₀.

It is noted, that in the NP experience, the lowest concentration of Zn was recorded compared to the other experience, this fact being explained by the lack of precipitation, the amount of phosphorus remaining in the soil was higher leading to the immobilization of zinc to the plants.

Zinc concentrations did not exceed the maximum permitted limit of 15 mg/kg, according to ORDER (EC) No. 1881/2006.

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